

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages

Final monitoring reports

Deliverable D5.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	D5.1 - Final monitoring reports
Work Package	WP5 – WP Accelerating demonstrators’ transformational adaptation
Dissemination Level	Public
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Date Due	30/09/2025
Date Submitted	30/09/2025
File Name	TransformAr D5.1-5.pdf
Status	Final
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Jan Cools (UA)
Suggested citation	Hnátková et al. (2025) Final Monitoring Report. Deliverable D5.1. TransformAr. H2020 grant no. 101036683.

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This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAr. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

- AP – Action Plan
- AWAR – Awareness-Raising Modules
- BNG – Biodiversity Net Gain
- CAF/CAE – Citizen App Finland / Citizen App Egaleo
- CC – Climate Change
- CCA – Climate Change Adaptation
- CCISC – Climate Change Impacts Study Committee
- CETMAR – Technological Centre of the Sea
- CIH – Climate Innovation Hub
- CIL – Community Infrastructure Levy
- COAST – Coastal Contract
- CoM – Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy
- COTS – Commercial Off-the-Shelf
- CS – Citizen Scientists
- DEFRA – UK Department for Environment, Farming and Rural Affairs
- DSI – Decision Support Instruments
- EEA – European Environment Agency
- ELMS – Environmental Land Management Scheme
- ERDF – European Regional Development Fund
- ESNACC – Elements for a National Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change
- EU – European Union
- GA – Grant Agreement
- GHG – Greenhouse Gases
- GIS – Geographic Information Systems
- HAB – Harmful Algal Bloom
- ICW – Integrated Constructed Wetlands
- INSUR – Urban Climate Risk Insurance
- INTERM – Intertidal Monitoring
- IoT – Internet of Things
- IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- ISPRA – Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (Italy)
- KCS – Key Community System
- KPI – Key Performance Indicator

- LWO – Local Wetland Observatory
- MASE – Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security (Italy)
- MOE – Municipality of Egaleo
- MoEE – Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy
- MRM – Mussel Raft Monitoring
- MRV – Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
- NAP – National Adaptation Plan
- NAS – National Adaptation Strategy
- NBS – Nature-Based Solutions
- NCCAC – National Climate Change Adaptation Committee
- NCM – Natural Capital Marketplace
- NCSR – National Centre for Scientific Research Demokritos
- NN – Nutrient Neutrality
- OECC – Spanish Climate Change Office
- PNACC – Spanish National Adaptation Plan to Climate Change
- RAAP – Regional Adaptation Action Plans
- RASCC – Regional Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change
- RI – Resilience Index
- SAC – Special Area of Conservation
- SCS – Smart Climate Stations
- STH – Stakeholders
- SuDS – Sustainable Drainage Systems
- SWM – Storm Water Modular System
- SWMM – Storm Water Management Model
- TRL – Technology Readiness Level
- URB – Urban Run-off Biofiltration System
- UVIGO – University of Vigo
- WRT – Westcountry Rivers Trust

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TransformAr (Grant Agreement No. 101036683) is a Horizon 2020 Innovation Action designed to accelerate transformational adaptation in Europe and outermost regions. The project involved the deployment and monitoring of integrated portfolios of solutions (Region-Specific Portfolios – RSPs) across six demonstrators: The following regions are represented: Lappeenranta (FI), West Country (UK), Galicia (ES), Oristano (IT), Egaleo (GR), and Guadeloupe (FR). While some RSP focused on Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), others concentrated on digital monitoring, technical, governance finance innovations, considering behavioural approaches, tailored to site-specific vulnerabilities such as flooding, saline intrusion, nutrient pollution, aquaculture risks, urban heat, and hurricane exposure.

The progression of the project has been found to be in accordance with all six Specific Objectives (SO1–SO6). A total of 20 innovations were validated, with the strongest contributions pertaining to SO3 (socio-economic and environmental benefits) and SO4 (real-world testing of innovations). A harmonized monitoring framework was introduced, combining quantitative KPIs (water quality, biodiversity, flooding, energy) with qualitative measures (governance effectiveness, stakeholder awareness), ensuring comparability across demonstrators.

The results of the demonstrator are as follows:

Lappeenranta, FI: The implementation of digital stormwater monitoring systems, biofiltration NBS, citizen application and choice experiment has been demonstrated to result in a reduction of flood risks and increased nutrient retention, as well as enhanced integration within municipal governance and city planning frameworks.

In the West Country of the United Kingdom, the implementation of catchment-scale restoration (by means of NBS) and nutrient neutrality schemes (a financial business model) has been demonstrated to have a positive impact on biodiversity with some limited measurable impacts on water quality. This assertion is supported by monitoring data that has been collected and analyzed, which has confirmed a reduction in phosphate levels and the recovery of ecosystem function.

In the context of Galicia, ES, the enhancement of aquaculture resilience has been achieved through the implementation of mussel raft monitoring, intertidal sandbank modelling, and stakeholder engagement. This approach has facilitated the development of predictive management capacity, which has been asked for by the local authority and aquaculture farmers, in support of the sustainable management of aquatic ecosystems in general and mussel farms and shellfish banks in particular.

In Oristano, Italy, the implementation of wetland restoration initiatives, the integration of Smart Gate systems, and the introduction of governance innovations have been identified as key factors in the reduction of coastal flood and degradation of water quality while also realising joint implementation of adaptation action. These measures have been successful in safeguarding the agricultural and fisheries sectors.

In the context of Egaleo, Greece, the implementation of Smart Climate Stations, citizen applications, and the establishment of a Climate Innovation Hub have been instrumental in enhancing awareness and preparedness against floods and heatwaves, thereby promoting equity and fostering enhanced participation.

In Guadeloupe, France, a local adaptation fund has been setup and tested. Funds from various agencies have been blended and targeted towards climate adaptation in tourism and agriculture. A nudging campaign in hotels focused on reducing water use in hotels.

Key challenges encountered:

The monitoring of the impact of the adaptation solutions in the demonstrator regions led to a number of challenges, barriers and lessons learned, from the technical monitoring design and analysis point of view, and the planning, implementation and design point of view. Highlighted challenges

- Divergent expectations and the inherently different contexts of demonstrators posed challenges for comparability and sometimes created difficulties and misunderstandings in aligning perspectives between monitoring teams and local implementers. The concept of having a harmonious data system to compare the impact of solutions was difficult to fit in the local context of the demonstrators; In practice, demonstrators found it difficult to adjust ongoing activities to accommodate externally defined requirements while maintaining their own established monitoring routines;
- Monitoring the impact of the demonstrators' adaptation solutions require preparatory work (e.g. a baseline monitoring intended to assess the impact of solutions) and closer, continuous support, in order to assess the most suitable way to evaluate impacts while taking into account the specific needs of each demonstrator;
- The duration of the project also restricted the ability to observe long-term effects, especially for some adaptation measures take years to become visible;
- Data ownership remained dispersed across partners, and datasets were fragmented, leading to delays in access and making the harmonization of qualitative and quantitative information particularly complex.
- The wide range of monitoring, data analysis, and evaluation needs meant that the monitoring team should play a central role, to create opportunities for learning by doing and specific training sessions, to strengthen local monitoring capacities;

Recommendations for future projects:

By acknowledging the dual-sided challenges, on both the monitoring experts side and local demonstrator side, future initiatives can design approaches that facilitate common monitoring frameworks while making the most of demonstrators' existing expertise. Recommendations include:

- **Build mutual understanding** between the overarching monitoring team and local monitoring experts in order to both realise a workable common framework while being useful for local demonstrators at the same time;
- **Data governance operationalized:** Although TransformAr established a clear data management strategy, unclarity remained on where, how and by whom data is to be stored. Disperse data ownership in different databases resulted in a fragmented understanding. Future projects should emphasise putting governance agreements into practice, through hands-on technical support, continuous follow-up, and periodic alignment of data flows.
- **Early integration of monitoring requirements:** Demonstrator designs were often completed before monitoring needs could be fully embedded. To avoid costly retrofits and weaker evidence, monitoring design must be integrated into the earliest planning stages and supported throughout implementation.
- **Realistic and flexible KPI frameworks:** Indicators must remain practical under varying project conditions and open to revision when evidence points misalignment. In TransformAr, KPIs were reviewed during the project with strong contributions from demonstrators, which was a positive step. However, the process was not sufficient to align the final set of KPIs to the evaluation needs. This highlights the importance of joint ownership of KPI frameworks by both demonstrators and monitoring teams.

- **Capacity building and training:** Investing in early and ongoing training should be embedded to enhance local ownership of monitoring, reduce dependency on external actors and strengthen policy-relevance. In addition, training should also target the monitoring team itself, ensuring they fully understand the specific context, constraints and objectives of each demonstrator. This dual approach would enable monitoring frameworks to be both technically sound and well-adapted to the realities of implementation.
- **Adequately resourced technical support:** Sufficient budget and expertise for trouble shooting sensor installation, connectivity and processing must be anticipated.
- **Shared and adaptable methodological frameworks:** Developing a common methodological framework that remains flexible to local differences ensures that both direct and proxy indicators are applied consistently while valuing site-specific knowledge.

By bringing together these lessons and recommendations, future projects can be guided to avoid repeating structural gaps where frameworks exist but are not fully operationalized. Monitoring and data systems should be developed not only in design but also through ongoing support, collaborative testing, and continuous adjustment with demonstrators throughout the entire project lifecycle.

1.0 Objectives and infographic

TransformAr pursues six overarching Specific Objectives (SO1–SO6) as defined in the Grant Agreement. These are realized through tailored goals for each demonstrator, reflecting local climate risks, socio-economic conditions, and adaptation needs.

1.1 Demonstrators

West Country, UK (WRT, CZU)

The primary objective is to reduce nutrients, catchment-scale flood risks and enhance ecosystem resilience through large-scale Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). River restoration, wetland creation, and soil conservation measures are implemented to slow runoff, store water, and restore biodiversity. A parallel goal is to increase stakeholder and community involvement through citizen science, ensuring long-term ownership. Expected environmental benefits include improved water quality and biodiversity; socio-economic benefits include reduced flood damage and enhanced recreational and cultural ecosystem services.

Figure 1.1 Infographic - West Country, UK

Guadeloupe Archipelago, FR (ADEME, ACTERRA)

Objectives are to strengthen coastal and island resilience against hurricanes, storm surges, and coastal erosion. The focus is on ecosystem rehabilitation (mangrove restoration), hybrid protection systems that combine natural buffers with engineered structures, and enhanced community preparedness. Environmental goals target reduced coastal vulnerability; economic objectives include protection of tourism and fisheries; social benefits are improved disaster readiness and citizen awareness.

Oristano, IT (MEDSEA, CMCC)

Oristano's objectives focus on tackling coastal flooding, increasing water quality into the lagoon. Actions integrate wetland restoration, sustainable water management, and governance innovations. Goals include protecting fishing productivity, ensuring water quality, and conserving coastal ecosystems. Anticipated environmental benefits include restored habitats and improved water balance; economic benefits involve safeguarding agriculture and fisheries; social benefits include strengthened governance capacity and resilience of local communities.

Figure 1.2 Infographic - Oristano, IT

Galicia, ES (CETMAR, UVIGO)

The goal is to implement a transformational adaptation process for clam and mussel aquaculture, a sector highly exposed to climate-driven risks such as temperature anomalies, storms, and low salinity waves. Objectives involve equipping the sector with predictive tools, real-time monitoring, and participatory processes. Environmental benefits include more sustainable aquaculture practices; economic benefits involve securing a vital regional industry; social benefits stem from empowering stakeholders with data, awareness, and decision-support capacity.

Figure 1.3 Infographic - Galicia, ES

SCS - Smart Climate Stations | CAE - Citizen App | AWAR - Awareness-raising | CIH - Climate Innovation Hub | DSI - Social services/infrastructures

1.2 Methodological Updates

The TransformAr methodology evolved dynamically, shaped by insights from monitoring, laboratory analyses, and stakeholder engagement.

Key methodological updates include:

The development of a harmonized monitoring framework represented a key methodological advance of TransformAr. Building on the findings of D5.8, which identified discrepancies in monitoring approaches across demonstrators, a unified framework was introduced. This framework combines quantitative KPIs, such as biodiversity indices, water quality, flooding frequency, and energy savings, with qualitative indicators, including stakeholder perception and governance effectiveness. The integration of these elements ensured comparability across sites and significantly improved reporting consistency.

Another major enhancement was the integration of digital platforms. The PIK data visualization platform was upgraded to centralize diverse data flows, thereby enabling real-time access and cross-site analysis. Egaleo the platform linked sensor data from the Smart Weather Station to citizen-facing applications, expanding public access and engagement.

Laboratory analyses were also refined to improve the robustness of monitoring outcomes. In the West Country, soil and sediment testing deepened understanding of nutrient retention and hydrological dynamics. In Oristano, detailed analyses of salinity and water chemistry directly informed wetland restoration design. These laboratory-based insights reinforced the reliability of selected indicators and improved the scientific basis for evaluating adaptation performance.

Stakeholder engagement methodologies were further expanded and diversified. Lappeenranta extended its participatory planning workshops to include private sector actors, ensuring broader involvement in

adaptation pathway development. In Galicia, engagement formats were revised to create a closer connection and participation of aquaculture stakeholders, which ultimately fostered wider acceptance of the solutions and stronger co-design processes.

The harmonized monitoring framework is ready for direct application in other Horizon projects, thereby supporting future standardization and comparability at EU level.

Innovation

TransformAr is distinguished by its cross-sectoral innovation, which brings together the ecological, digital, financial and governance dimensions in a coherent framework for transformational adaptation. Demonstrators have advanced the large-scale implementation of nature-based solutions (NBS), digital integration and sector-specific strategies, while also piloting novel governance and financing models.

In the West Country, TransformAr has pioneered one of the first Horizon-supported, catchment-scale river restoration initiatives, linking biodiversity recovery directly to measurable reductions in flood risk. In Guadeloupe, a French overseas region, hybrid solutions combining ecosystem restoration, particularly mangrove restoration, with physical protective structures have been developed. These solutions can be replicated in other climate-vulnerable island regions.

Lappeenranta has demonstrated how urban green infrastructure can be integrated with digital innovation, combining real-time monitoring tools and participatory platforms to enhance resilience to heavy rainfall and flooding. Galicia, in turn, has focused on monitoring, technical and social innovation within the aquaculture sector. This approach combines real-time data, predictive modelling, and participatory processes to strengthen the resilience of mussel and clam farming in the face of changing environmental conditions (detailed information on specific innovations per solution is available on 5.8 Intermediary Monitoring Report).

Innovation in governance and finance has also been central to the project. Oristano has piloted advanced water governance mechanisms in coastal zones, and Guadeloupe has tested new financing models for protective measures against climate risks. To facilitate knowledge transfer and wider uptake, cross-site learning has been promoted using tools such as the Playbook and the Scorecard. These digital resources capture best practices from demonstrators and provide municipalities and regions with practical support for making decisions about selecting, combining and scaling up adaptation solutions.

Adjustments developed

Several project-specific challenges and adaptations to specific contexts meant that adjustments had to be made to the objectives or methods.

Extreme weather and data gaps:

In Guadeloupe, for example, hurricanes disrupted monitoring campaigns, necessitating the use of proxy indicators and satellite remote sensing. Despite the resulting delays, this improved methodological resilience and highlighted the need for redundancy in data sources.

Technical calibration and deployment:

In Egaleo, the Smart Weather Station and citizen apps required iterative calibration to produce accurate results. While this slowed deployment, it resulted in more robust monitoring systems with higher user acceptance.

Hydrological variability:

In the West Country, unusually dry seasons complicated sediment retention and water quality assessments. Methodologies were adjusted to incorporate adaptive sampling strategies.

Stakeholder engagement adaptation:

In Galicia, the engagement methodologies were adapted with a focus on more participatory formats and trust-building workshops. This improved engagement and data sharing.

Integration challenges:

In Lappeenranta, combining nature-based solutions (NBS) with digital systems created unexpected maintenance requirements for green infrastructure. Operational protocols were updated to include long-term maintenance planning.

Cross-Demonstrator Harmonization:

Initial differences in KPI definitions complicated the synthesis process. However, the harmonization process resulted in a consistent monitoring and evaluation system.

The objectives of TransformAr are being met through demonstrator-specific goals, adaptive methodological updates, innovative integration of solutions, and adjustments to unexpected challenges. Tailored approaches at each site are delivering measurable environmental, economic, and social benefits, while methodological refinements and innovations ensure comparability and scalability.

By combining Nature-Based Solutions, digital monitoring, technological solutions, governance and financing models, and citizen engagement, TransformAr demonstrates practical, replicable pathways for transformational adaptation in Europe. Lessons learned and cross-cutting insights are fed into the project's catalogue of solutions, Playbook, Scorecard, and policy briefs, ensuring that objectives are not only achieved but translated into actionable outcomes for replication and scaling.

2.0 Context

TransformAr demonstrators are located in diverse European regions, each representing distinct climate risks, socio-economic conditions, and governance structures. The following subsections provide site-specific context, including geographical description, key vulnerabilities and challenges, and the state-of-the-art in adaptation at the beginning of the project.

West Country, UK

- Geographical description:

The demonstrator is situated in Southwest England, focusing on the Camel and Axe catchments, both designated as Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) and including Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI).

- Vulnerability and impacts:

Climate risks include diffuse agricultural pollution, flooding, and drought. Water quality is degraded by phosphate and nitrate runoff, amplified during heavy rainfall and reduced dilution during droughts. Sensitive habitats, fisheries, and human health are directly affected.

- State-of-the-art adaptation

Previous initiatives tested riparian buffers, wetlands, and nutrient neutrality schemes. However, integration across sectors (agriculture, water, planning) was limited. TransformAr builds on this by testing ecosystem service markets (phosphate credits, biodiversity net gain credits) to sustain long-term NBS adoption.

Guadeloupe Archipelago, FR

- Geographical description:

An outermost EU region in the Caribbean, Guadeloupe consists of small islands with densely populated coastal zones.

- Vulnerability and impacts

Exposed to hurricanes, storm surges, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise. Tourism, fisheries, and urban infrastructure are concentrated in high-risk zones. Adaptive capacity is limited due to insularity and reliance on coastal economies.

- State-of-the-art adaptation

Previous work included ADEME-led economic assessments of coastal hazards and mangrove restoration pilots. TransformAr expands this with hybrid protection systems and enhanced governance.

Oristano, IT

- Geographical description:

Located in western Sardinia, the Oristano Gulf includes wetlands, agricultural plains, and coastal ecosystems.

- Vulnerability and impacts:

Climate change drives sea level rise, heatwaves, prolonged droughts, and intense rainfall events that cause both inland and coastal flooding

- State-of-the-art adaptation:

Italy's national strategies emphasize integrated water management, and Oristano had initiated a Coastal Contract framework before TransformAr. The project adds a Smart Gate system and NBS for adaptive water management.

Galicia, ES

- Geographical description:

Galicia's Atlantic coast is a global centre for clam and mussel aquaculture, with Ría de Arousa as the largest bay inlet in the southwest coast, and the most productive with 70% of the mussel rafts and 50% clam sales (Xunta de Galicia, 2021a)¹.

- Vulnerability and impacts:

The sector is sensitive to temperature anomalies (mainly heat waves), storms, torrential rains (low salinity waves), and sedimentation changes, all intensified by climate change.

- State-of-the-art adaptation:

National and regional frameworks (PNACC, Galicia Strategy 2050) provide adaptation guidance. Local monitoring exists (Coastal Observatory), but aquaculture faced a shortage of predictive, real-time management tools. TransformAr introduced the Resilience Index, Mussel Raft Monitoring, and Intertidal Monitoring solutions.

Lappeenranta, FI

- Geographical description:

A city in southeast Finland with mixed urban, industrial, and green areas.

- Vulnerability and impacts:

Facing heavier rainfall, stormwater flooding, and pipeline capacity limits, with risks to water quality and infrastructure.

- State-of-the-art adaptation:

National monitoring is coordinated by SYKE and the Flood Centre, with stormwater flood risk maps and hydraulic modelling already available. TransformAr builds on this with URB NBS biofilter systems, real-time monitoring of systems, citizen apps, and choice experiments.

Egaleo, GR

- Geographical description:

A dense municipality in the Athens metropolitan region with limited green space.

- Vulnerability and impacts:

The city is highly exposed to urban heatwaves, flash floods, and extreme weather. Vulnerable groups face compounded risks.

- State-of-the-art adaptation:

Greece's PNACC and RAAP provide the national framework, but municipal-level adaptation was limited. Egaleo's TransformAr actions introduced a Smart Climate Station, Climate Innovation Hub, citizen apps, and AWAR awareness modules, establishing a first-of-its-kind local adaptation ecosystem.

Across the demonstrators, baselines show high exposure and diverse risks, but also opportunities for innovation. TransformAr's Region-Specific Portfolios (RSPs) respond to these contexts with tailored combinations of Nature-Based Solutions, digital monitoring, governance innovation, and participatory approaches. This contextual diversity provides a robust testbed for scaling transformational adaptation across Europe.

¹ Xunta de Galicia. (2021, a). Enquisa sobre a poboación ocupada nos sectores da pesca e da acuicultura mariña en Galicia - OCUPESCA 2019, https://www.pescadegalicia.gal/Publicaciones/pdfs/Ocupesca_2019.pdf

2.1 Geographical Description

This chapter provides a geographical overview of each TransformAr demonstrator site, highlighting the specific environmental, climatic, and socio-economic features that shape local vulnerabilities and opportunities for climate adaptation. Each site has been selected because its geographical characteristics directly relate to priority risks identified in the project, such as coastal flooding, saline intrusion, nutrient pollution, urban heat, oceanographic alterations (Temperatura, salinity, winds...), or stormwater management.

The demonstrator regions represent a diverse set of European and outermost environments, ranging from northern urban centers and Mediterranean coastal lagoons to Atlantic aquaculture areas, rural catchments, and outermost island regions. This diversity ensures that the project tests solutions under a wide spectrum of climatic pressures and socio-ecological contexts.

The use of these specific locations is justified by their strategic relevance for EU adaptation policy:

- They provide representative testbeds for challenges faced across Europe (urban flooding, coastal resilience, agricultural adaptation, aquaculture sustainability).
- They offer scaling and replication potential, as lessons learned in one region (e.g., nutrient neutrality in UK catchments, NBS integration into Finnish urban planning) can be transferred to other European contexts.
- They reflect a balance between scientific monitoring capacity and stakeholder engagement, ensuring that adaptation solutions are grounded in both robust evidence and societal readiness.

2.1.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

Lappeenranta (61-06°N, 28-19 °E) is a Finnish city with a population of 73000 covering an area of 1,724 km² situated in the region of 'South Karelia' (aka. Etelä-Karjala) on the south-eastern frontier of Finland, 30 kilometers away from the Russian border (Figure 2.1). The city is located on the shores of Lake Saimaa, which is the biggest lake in Finland and the fourth biggest lake of Europe. The city's main water intake is

the lake water, which a decade ago was polluted by the proliferation of algae. Since, water conservation has been a major area of interest for the city. According to the latest national water quality classification (Finnish Environment Institute, 2019), the water quality of Western Saimaa is fair to intermediate. The objective is good ecological status.

Figure 2.1 Lappeenranta’s boundaries within South Karelia in relation to the map of Finland

The city center is located on the First Salpausselkä ridge, which is an ice-marginal formation laid down by the last Ice Age. Salpausselkä is mainly formed of sand and gravel and holds massive reserves of high-quality groundwater.

According to the Köppen climate classification, Finland has a continental subarctic/boreal climate and Lappeenranta has a southern-boreal climate. The city’s climate is influenced by Salpausselkä, the lake areas of Saimaa and Laatokka (in Russia) and the Gulf of Finland.

Typical of the city’s climate are four distinct seasons, each season lasting approximately three months. In Lappeenranta, winter is longer than summer. Precipitation has an annual average of 614 millimeters of which 40-50 % usually falls as snow. The snow cover typically melts in April and May which can contribute to flooding. In this context it is important to underline that meltwaters are recognized to consist of large amounts of nutrients and heavy metals. These substances are mainly from prevention of icy roads and yards, and from vehicles, which are more polluting in winter due to corrosion caused by road salt. In addition, the rain or melting snow washes with its pollution from all other impermeable surfaces, such as roofs or construction areas.

2.1.2 Oristano, Italy

The coastal area of Oristano (Sardinia, Italy) is a complex and high-density system of rivers, lagoons, and salt marshes. Most of the wetlands are shallow eutrophic water bodies (approximately 0.5-2 m depth), around 7,700 hectares of which (over 60% of Sardinia’s wetlands) are protected by the Ramsar convention⁴ and the Natura 2000 network⁵. The Gulf of Oristano is characterized by the tight integration

between the existing settlement structure and the environment characterized by the system of coastal wetlands. It is a low-density area, characterized by small concentrated urban zones, most of them located in the inland areas, and sprawl urbanization related to fishing cooperatives, agricultural and livestock farms and small touristic villages located along the coast (Satta, 2014).

The population of the 11 municipalities located in the area, around 85 thousand in 2022, is decreasing as people are moving to the main cities of the island or to the north of the country mainly driven by more employment opportunities. The rivers and wetlands are amongst the most fish-rich inland areas of Sardinia, possibly in the entire Mediterranean, and they also hold significant cultural heritage value. In several ponds and lagoons, there are operating fishing cooperatives and some aquaculture production, often derived from traditional practices.

Figure 2.2 General map of the Gulf of Oristano

Figure 2.3 Zoom of the NBS area (Oristano)

The southern wetlands of the Gulf are the Marceddì-San Giovanni lagoon compendium, which appears as a deep marine inlet artificially separated from the sea by a fishpond bridge and divided into two different wetlands: the Marceddì lagoon (900 ha), closer to the sea with brackish water, and the internal pond of San Giovanni (700 ha), characterized by freshwater inputs from the rivers Rio Mogoro, Rio Mannu, Rio Sitzerri, and from some artificial canals.

The surrounding territory is dominated by the agricultural plain of Arborea on the north-east side, an expanse of regular fields bordered by the reclamation infrastructure (canals and roads), while to the west it is surrounded by the mountainous complex of Monte Arcuentu. The fishing activities in the Marceddì-San Giovanni lagoon are managed by the Consortium Coop. Riunite della pesca di Marceddì. The concession granted by the Autonomous Region of Sardinia under the act rep. 1082/98 dated 07/07/1998, is currently renewed. Covering an area of 2610 ha, the fishing operations involve around 140 operators.

Hydraulic interventions carried out in recent decades have significantly altered the original structure of the entire wetland system. These modifications have disrupted the natural water exchange conditions between marine and freshwater environments, leading to changes in the ecological conditions of the area due to sediment discharge into the water and impacting on the ongoing fishing activities.

Figure 2.4 Sardinia wetlands

Wetland

Landscape of the Marceddi

Wetland

Landscape of the Marceddi

Fishpond bridge that separates Marceddi wetland from the sea

Extreme flooding event in the area

2.1.3 West Country Region, United Kingdom

Figure 2.5 Map of the South West of England showing target river catchments, Study Catchments and Rationale

Two catchments in SW England, the River Camel in North Cornwall and the River Axe in East Devon (Figure 10), were selected as demonstrator sites for the project due to their designations as Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) and including Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI). These are protected by designations given under the Conservation of Habitats and Species Regulations 2017 (part of the [European Council Directive 92/43/EEC](#)), due to a number of primary and qualifying features of interest (Table 2.1), and an array of geological and biological points of interest. Water quality and quantity play a pivotal role in the conservation of the freshwater habitats hosting these protected species, which must be taken into consideration by parties wishing to carry out work that could harm the features of interest. Initially a third catchment was also chosen (the Tone catchment). In this catchment, nutrient neutrality had been enforced for a longer period and therefore there was an existing partnership that was dealing with neutrality locally. WRT’s role as an NGO was already being fulfilled by local NGOs such as the Farming & Wildlife Advisor Group and Somerset Wildlife Trust. Consequently, WRT had a lower knowledge of potential landowners willing to participate in NBS development the Tone catchment.

Table 2.1 Reasons for designation as Special Areas of Conservation for the River Camel and Axe catchments.

Catchment	Primary reason for designation	Other qualifying features
River Camel	Presence of Annex II species Bullhead and Otter	Presence of Atlantic salmon and its Annex I habitats European dry heaths, <u>Old sessile oak woods with Ilex and Blechnum in the British Isles</u>

		and alluvial forests with Black alder and European ash (a priority feature)
River Axe	<u>Water courses of plain to montane levels with the <i>Ranunculus fluitantis</i> and Callitriche-Batrachion vegetation</u>	Presence of Annex II species Sea lamprey, Brook lamprey and Bullhead

2.1.4 Galicia, Spain

Deliverable 1.2 of the TransformAr project provides a detailed and comprehensive explanation of the geographical characteristics of Galicia. This section offers only a summary to contextualise the demonstrator and the solutions.

Galicia (6.4 - 9.6°W, 41.5 - 44.2°N) is located in the North Atlantic region, in the Northwest quarter of Spain. The region covers 29,576 km², representing 5.8% of Spanish territory, with a coastline of 1,659 km (32.8% of the Spanish coastline). The intricate Atlantic coast of Galicia is mainly characterized by the presence of multiple coastal inlets known as Rías. Their geomorphology and circulation favour the efficient use of the nutrients transported by the upwelling process in spring and summer, and provide protection against autumn and winter storms, conditions that make Galicia an exceptional site for the mussel aquaculture on hanging ropes and bivalve extraction in sandbanks. In particular, the Ria de Arousa, the largest bay inlet in the southwest coast, appears as the most productive area with 70% of the mussel rafts and 50% clam sales (Xunta de Galicia, 2021a).

Galicia is located in the transition from the temperate to the subpolar regimes of the North Atlantic, which, among other factors, makes it particularly sensitive to the predicted CC. Its consequences in the regional oceanography systems and the consequent socio-economic impact remains under evaluation.

The territory of Galicia is home to 56 types of habitats of community interest, with 10 of them being considered as priorities. According to the data extracted from the “Master Plan of the Natura 2000 Network” prepared in 2012 by the regional government Xunta de Galicia (Ramil-Rego et al., 2012), 12.7% of the territory of Galicia is considered a Site of Community Interest (SCI) and 3.4% corresponds to Areas of Special Protection for Birds (SPAs), which are usually part of SCIs. Galicia’s regional population includes some 2.7 million people. The region has developed a Galician Climate Change Strategy 2050, and an Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate for the period 2019-2023 which is meant to guide the implementation of the strategy.

Figure 2.6 Study area – Ria de Arousa – Galicia -Spain

2.1.5 City of Egaleo, Greece

The municipality of Egaleo (MOE), Greece (37.9924° N, 23.6781° E) is situated at the west region of the urban planning complex of the region of Attica and has been built at both sides of the ancient road «Iera Odos». It is approximately 4km away from Athens. The borders of Egaleo can be seen in Figure 2.7 below. The population of the city is around 120.000. The city is exposed to heat waves (expected to increase with CC), extreme precipitations, thunderstorms, and flooding events.

Figure 2.7 Study area – City of Egaleo, Greece

2.1.6 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

The Guadeloupe Archipelago is located in the Caribbean Sea and forms an outermost region of the European Union. It consists of two main islands, Basse-Terre (mountainous, volcanic, humid) and Grande-Terre (low-lying, limestone, drier), separated by a narrow strait, along with several smaller islands such as Marie-Galante, Les Saintes, and La Désirade.

Key features relevant for climate adaptation include:

- Tropical climate with high annual rainfall and pronounced wet/dry seasons, making water management a persistent challenge.
- Exposure to extreme events, particularly hurricanes, tropical storms, and heavy rainfall leading to flooding, landslides, and infrastructure damage.
- Socio-ecological vulnerability, with densely populated coastal zones where most economic activities (tourism, services, agriculture, and fisheries) are concentrated.
- Water stress: Despite high rainfall, uneven distribution and saline intrusion affect water availability, especially on limestone plateaus.
- Biodiversity hotspots, including mangroves, coral reefs, and coastal ecosystems, which provide natural protection but are increasingly threatened by sea-level rise, storms, and human pressures.

The Guadeloupe demonstrator was chosen as part of TransformAr because it represents a small-island context highly exposed to climate risks, where behavioral change, social innovation, and nature-based solutions can play a critical role in building resilience. Its geographical setting provides both urgent adaptation needs and opportunities for replication in other Caribbean and EU outermost regions.

2.2 Climate Vulnerability, Impacts, Risks, and Challenges

This chapter provides a summary of the key climate risks and vulnerabilities affecting each TransformAr demonstrator, including flooding, sea-level rise, saline intrusion, nutrient pollution, aquaculture risks, and urban heatwaves. These pressures represent both immediate threats and long-term challenges for ecosystems, economies, and communities.

The risk assessment integrates baseline monitoring, stakeholder input, and modelling, with updates from recent calculations (D5.1) that refine projections on flood frequency, nutrient loads, and resilience indices. Together, these insights strengthen adaptation planning and ensure that the selected solutions directly address the most critical vulnerabilities at each site.

2.2.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

For Lappeenranta, the Key Community Systems (KCS) that we focus on are water management and urban planning. The possible vulnerabilities and challenges caused by climate change in Lappeenranta key community systems was evaluated in the TransformAr pathways workshop by the stakeholders. Figure 2.8 summarizes the climate change projections for Lappeenranta region (PIK 2022). It is to be expected that the winters will be milder but wetter, which will cause more load on the urban drainage system. In the wintertime the frozen soil is not so permeable, so flooding is expected to increase. Furthermore, climate change is projected to increase the number of heavy rain events, that can surpass the capacity of the urban drainage system.

Figure 2.8 Greece Summary of climate projections for the City of Lappeenranta (Source: PIK presentation during the WS 2)

According to projections, **Lappeenranta** is likely to deal with

Based on these climate projections, hazards and vulnerabilities were assessed in the pathways workshop. The risk chains that have been developed in the workshop are presented in Figure 2.9 and Figure 2.10. The increased rainfall projections and the insufficient capacity of the stormwater pipe network leads to increased flooding risk and more harmful substances in the stormwater.

Figure 2.9 The risk chains Oristano demo I

Similarly, a risk chain was created for the urban planning KCS and is presented in Figure 2.10. This assessment gives similar risks, but from a different perspective. Flooding is still seen as one of the main risks with the addition of droughts.

Figure 2.10 The risk chains Oristano demo II

2.2.2 Oristano, Italy

Sardinia is located in the center of the Mediterranean region, and according to EEA (2017), is likely to be impacted by several climate forces that include, among others: sea level rise, an increase of maximum temperatures and heatwaves especially during summer; long drought periods interrupted by heavy and extreme rainfall events leading to severe floods, and extreme storm events causing coastal flooding.

Droughts during summer are often associated with greater water demand from different competing sectors, leading to inter-sectorial conflicts and unsustainable overexploitation of water resources. Consequences of severe droughts have been particularly relevant with risks for limited freshwater supplies and the incurrence of large fires affecting not only forest ecosystems, but also rural/urban interfaces and the increase of coastal erosion risk and desertification. Flooding is a particularly crucial risk not only endangering human life and infrastructures but also causing soil erosion and the transport of contaminants from industrial, mining and agriculture fields to natural and especially aquatic ecosystems.

Changes in climatic conditions can alter agricultural productivity, in terms of quantity and quality of agricultural products, water supply and the hydrological regime, with implications for water resources availability. Increases in irrigation requirements are expected for the main crops cultivated in Sardinia because of climate change. Moreover, water demand increases could derive from socio-economic changes (tourism, agri-food, and textile sectors, energy plants, agricultural settlements), urbanization and lifestyle changes, causing a serious concern.

Focusing on the Gulf of Oristano, the coastal area faces a significant threat from inland flooding, especially during extreme rainfall events combined with marine storms. This endangers the population, infrastructure, and the local economic activities.

The Gulf is characterized by its low-lying areas, which make it highly vulnerable to the impacts of rising sea levels, coastal and inland flooding. Despite the high susceptibility of low-lying coastal zones to these hazards, the overall vulnerability of the region is mitigated by the robust ecosystem health and efficient drainage density, enhancing its resilience.

Given the influence of climate change on the Gulf's water system and current patterns, an increase in water temperature in all seasons, a decline of winter salinity, pH levels dropping (acidification), and an increase in the presence of non-native species, among other effects. Looking ahead to the medium to long term (50 to 100 years), there is a likelihood of certain coastal lagoons disappearing due to rising sea

levels. These changes will have adverse effects on the local flora and fauna and the distribution of fishing stocks, particularly concerning commercially relevant aquatic organisms. The full extent of these impacts on local socio-economic conditions remains difficult to predict.

The traditional aquaculture activities are and will be significantly impacted by extreme rainfall events that disrupt the balance between saltwater and freshwater in the lagoons, causing sediment deposits that impede water circulation. The alteration of parameters such as salinity, Ph, dissolved oxygen, turbidity is linked to a change in the state of the ecosystem and a decrease in fish stocks. The alteration of the water quality can increase the presence and proliferation of invasive species which pose a threat to native species and reduce ecosystem services.

The solutions implemented within the TransformAr project focus on three Key Community Systems: Water Systems, Nature Conservation, and fisheries, which are vulnerable to climate impacts and are strictly related and positively influenced by COAST and SG.

The conditions of biodiversity and habitats, already affected by intensive land use activities (agriculture, animal husbandry, industry, and mining), along with the hydraulic efficiency of the wetlands and river dynamics, are severely impacted by climate hazards such as coastal and inland flooding, coastal erosion, wetland and groundwater salinization.

Coastal receptors, including beaches, river mouths, wetlands, terrestrial biological systems, and protected areas, are all affected by habitat degradation, biodiversity loss, and the emergence of alien and invasive species. Moreover, alterations in water quality influence fish stocks, leading to a reduction in fishermen's income. Extended drought periods could lead to increased water demand from wells or, where possible, a request for public water, which would then increase costs for farmers.

Based on this information the Risk components (hazards, exposure, vulnerability) were assessed in the pathways workshop. What have been highlighted by the participants is that the main drivers related to climate change are the increase of temperatures and the changes in precipitation patterns, appearing as a general reduction of the rainy season and a concentration of heavy precipitation in short periods. These drivers are generating impacts such as flooding, drought and storm phenomena that are exposing the communities, territories, and local economic activities to a risk of important economic and environmental losses.

Figure 2.11 Risk chain of Oristano demo II

2.2.3 West Country Region, United Kingdom

The Westcountry is likely to witness drier summers and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events, such as droughts (Southwest Water 2021). High energy rainfall events can also cause mobilization of sediments and nutrients leading to water quality issues.

The Meteorological Office highlights detailed impacts for the Southwest (Met Office UKCP) including:

- More frequent intense rainfall and wind-driven rain causing river and surface water flooding.
- Warmer wetter winters cause problems with crop management.
- Hotter drier summers cause problems for water quality and supply.
- Increase in extreme weather and disruptive events such as flooding, droughts, landslides or heatwaves interrupting or limiting access to vital services and impacting on people's physical and mental health.
- The rise of sea level rise affecting the viability of coastal communities and coastal infrastructure through flooding and erosion.

These projections were supported by the modelling carried out by PIK for the Westcountry stakeholder workshops in spring 2022 for Work package 2. (Figure 2.12-13)

Figure 2.12 Summary of climate projections for the Westcountry (Source: PIK presentation for Workshop 2 WP3) using ISIMIP 3b DATA

Figure 2.12 Modelled precipitation change shows drier summers and wetted winters

Figure 2.13 Modelling shows reduced river flows in summer and autumn

Figure 2.14 Modelling shows increased runoff during late summer to winter, but with high uncertainty due to coarse hydrological models

A review of data and updated scenario modelling by PIK was able to produce projections in discharge for rivers in the Westcountry Region, including the River Exe. What this has shown is that in all scenarios annual discharge increases. In the warmer scenarios more precipitation may be expected, however due to increased levels of evapotranspiration, this moderates the amount of water available and therefore discharge.

Figure 2.15 Model of expected changes to river discharge over time.

PIK also undertook soil water modelling based on future scenario predictions. In general soils are likely to be wetter in the winter and drier in the summer in the 2071-2100 scenario, when observing the blue scattered line. This will likely lead to more surface run-off over winter and increase groundwater recharge.

The green line below represents the leaf area index and a typical winter wheat scenario. With a drop following harvest, followed by some stubble plants increasing the leaf area index, followed by the planting of the winter crop. In the later scenario, harvest is likely to be earlier and the 2nd crop able to grow quicker prior to winter, therefore there will be more green crop cover and a higher leaf area index.

Figure 2.16 Modelled scenarios for leaf area index and soil water flows

There were some key insights provided by PIK following the updated modelling and various scenarios based on catchments within the region, these include the following:

Hotter summers and warmer winters > This will include an extension of the vegetation period and increasing water vegetation demand (Evapotranspiration)

Wetter winters and drier summers > Drier soils in the summer and an increase in water stress. However, in winter there is an increase in groundwater recharge leading to more water in rivers including the summer/early summer.

More intense precipitation > Increases in flood events and intensity, with more surface run-off leading to more erosion and phosphorus losses. The strategic use of riparian zones and wetlands can help to counteract this.

Longer vegetation period > There is the potential for two crops within the season, but there will be wetter soils conditions in the spring and Autumn that may cause issues with cultivation. Increases in temperature and the vegetation period may foster biotic risks (pest and disease)

More vegetation in winter > This may lead to more nutrient (nitrate) uptake over winter and reduce losses through percolation. Therefore, covering crops will be of significant importance to control nutrient loss and bind soils.

Higher water temperatures in rivers > Which will stimulate algae growth and blooming.

Cropping and fertilization schemes will have to be adopted to consider the change in the growing season.

2.2.4 Galicia, Spain

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2017a), the region of Galicia is at risk of more frequent and intense winter storms that will lead to an increasing risk of coastal infrastructure damage and heavy precipitation events, which in conjunction with sea level rise, could lead to more intense riverine and coastal floods and low salinity waves. Recent research have shown how variations in regional oceanographic conditions (e.g. increase in temperature, heatwaves, changes in upwelling-favourable coastal winds and precipitation regimes (low salinity waves,)), the alteration of nutrient fertilisation patterns (Sousa et al., 2020, FuentesSantos et al., 2021), presence of invasive species or new pathogens, as well as potential increase in harmful algal bloom (HAB) episodes (Álvarez-Salgado et al.; 2008, Pérez et al., 2010), can pose threats to which the aquaculture sector needs to adapt (Cramp et al., 2021).

Galicia faced a series of severe weather events in the past, including storms, wildfire and heatwaves. For example, in 2003 the temperatures in Galicia exceeded the 95th percentile of the maximum temperature, which impacted the mortality in the region; In 2002-2003 and 2013-2014, storm events significantly eroded beaches along the coast causing damage to infrastructures such as ports, ships, mussel rafts, and generated the inability to work at sea (small-scale fisheries, mussel aquaculture, shellfish harvesting activities). The region also witnessed one of its worst droughts in the last hundred years in 2016-2017 (Khamis et al., 2022), with an overall decrease in rainfall by about 500 mm, magnifying a series of wildfires that destroyed a total of 43,000 hectares, with consequences in soil erosion and sediment contribution to the Rías through the river discharge.

During the years 2022 and 2023, nineteen bilateral meetings and two workshops were held with key actors to discuss the adaptation of the Galician clam and mussel sector to climate change (CC), as part of

the TransformAr activity “Development of a shared vision for a future resilient to climate change”. These sessions substantiated that the local stakeholders' perception of climate change hazards aligns with scientific observations and recent observed events. In order of importance, they selected as main hazards fluctuations in salinity and river discharge, followed by the consistent rise in sea surface temperatures, changes in wind patterns and upwelling, and an escalation in the frequency and intensity of extreme winter events (e.g., waves and storms). Participants highlighted habitat alteration, the introduction of invasive species or alterations in existing populations, and erosion or modification of sedimentary banks as the principal risks directly associated with CC.

The impact of the above-mentioned risks could lead to higher pressure on the supply chain and the work culture (alterations in concessions, employment, social stress...). Adequate and economically viable adaptation measures are therefore needed to face these diverse challenges and increase the resilience of the sector. To face this demanding task, it is crucial to obtain longer data series and their analysis to support decision-making, propose tailor-made strategies and apply specific adaptation actions suitable to the sector. Figure 2.17 summarizes the hazards, exposure, vulnerability and risks to which the territory/sector is exposed to considering the results of the workshops.

Figure 2.17 Hazards, exposure, vulnerability and risks to which the Galician mussel-clam sector is exposed

Hazards

Considering the exposure and the vulnerability

- Concentration of population, beaches and infrastructures
- Sector of great economic importance:
 - Mussel: 40% of the European production, more than 3.000 mussel rafts and more than 5.000 employments.
 - Shellfish harvesting: approximately 600 harvesting

- The sensitivity of the area and the community to environmental changes.
- The characteristics of the community and working conditions.
- Spaces of growing tourist attraction (pollution) and development of other uses (energy).
- Lack of adaptation plans to CC or alternatives to

The most noted risks generated by CC that are considered to impact the most are:

- Erosion or modification of sedimentary banks / Floods
- Habitat alteration: growth, survival, seasonality and reproductive cycle, red tides, massive mortality, Food availability (it could increase and become an opportunity)
- Invasive species or modification of existing populations (alteration in the species of clams and predators)
- Location and availability of mussel spat and other bivalve recruitment
- Culture operations (mussel detachment) and damage to productive and coastal structures
- Rise of Algae (wrack) / Seaweed washed ashore
- Substrate changes

Socio-economic and environmental effects

The impact of the above-mentioned risk could lead to modifications in production (both in quality and quantity) and pressure on the supply chain and work culture (alterations in concessions, employment, social stress...)

2.2.5 City of Egaleo, Greece

The state of the art in Egaleo within TransformAR is the creation of a holistic ecosystem of digital and social solutions that combine real-time climate data with citizen engagement and policy support. The municipality is deploying a network of smart climate stations, demand analyses for social services, and a citizen app to crowdsource awareness and disseminate alerts, while also fostering behavioral change through school-based modules and a climate innovation hub. What makes this demonstrator innovative is the integration of diverse datasets (environmental, social, behavioral) into actionable, evidence-informed policies, coupled with direct citizen participation and awareness-raising. By merging technical monitoring, social inclusion, and entrepreneurial innovation, Egaleo pioneers a replicable model of urban climate resilience that addresses health, infrastructure, and planning vulnerabilities in a densely populated Mediterranean city.

2.2.6 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

The Guadeloupe Archipelago faces multiple climate-related vulnerabilities characteristic of small island territories in the Caribbean. Its exposure to extreme events, combined with socio-economic fragility, makes climate adaptation an urgent priority.

Key vulnerabilities and risks:

The Guadeloupe Archipelago faces multiple and interconnected climate risks. Regular exposure to Category 4–5 hurricanes and tropical storms cause extensive damage to housing, infrastructure, energy networks, and freshwater systems. Heavy rainfall events trigger flash floods and landslides, particularly on the volcanic island of Basse-Terre, where slope instability poses persistent challenges. Sea-level rise

and coastal erosion further threaten low-lying coastal zones and beaches, endangering livelihoods dependent on tourism and fisheries. Despite the archipelago's overall abundant rainfall, uneven spatial distribution, saline intrusion, and pollution lead to local water shortages, especially on Grande-Terre. Rising average temperatures and increasingly frequent heatwaves intensify heat stress and associated health risks, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups such as elderly populations.

Socio-economic challenges:

The Guadeloupe Archipelago faces multiple and interconnected climate risks. Regular exposure to Category 4–5 hurricanes and tropical storms cause extensive damage to housing, infrastructure, energy networks, and freshwater systems. Heavy rainfall events trigger flash floods and landslides, particularly on the volcanic island of Basse-Terre, where slope instability poses persistent challenges. Sea-level rise and coastal erosion further threaten low-lying coastal zones and beaches, endangering livelihoods dependent on tourism and fisheries. Despite the archipelago's overall abundant rainfall, uneven spatial distribution, saline intrusion, and pollution lead to local water shortages, especially on Grande-Terre. Rising average temperatures and increasingly frequent heatwaves intensify heat stress and associated health risks, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups such as elderly populations.

High dependence on coastal tourism, fisheries, and agriculture exposes the economy to climate shocks, while social inequality increases vulnerability, as poorer households are less able to invest in protective measures or access digital early-warning tools. In addition, limited capacity for infrastructure investment compared to mainland France constrains adaptation responses, leaving certain communities at greater risk.

Main challenges for adaptation in Guadeloupe:

Geographic isolation and reliance on imported resources complicate rapid response and recovery.

Fragmented governance between local municipalities, regional authorities, and national institutions slows coordinated action. Community engagement barriers, including unequal access to digital tools, require innovative and inclusive approaches to citizen participation.

2.3 State-of-the-Art on Adaptation in the Demonstrator

This chapter reviews the current adaptation practices already in place at each demonstrator site, providing a benchmark against which the added value of TransformAr solutions can be measured. Existing measures, such as conventional flood defenses, wastewater treatment, agricultural water management, or citizen engagement initiatives, form the local baseline of climate adaptation.

The assessment highlights that, while these practices have delivered important short-term benefits, they often remain sectoral, fragmented, or incremental. TransformAr builds upon this foundation by introducing integrated innovation packages, combining Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), digital monitoring tools, governance innovations, and behavioral approaches.

The innovation actions carried out within TransformAr demonstrate how adaptation can be scaled up and tailored to diverse socio-ecological contexts. By embedding solutions into urban planning, catchment management, aquaculture practices, and coastal protection, the project increases their replication

potential across Europe. The Living Lab approach further enhances adaptability by ensuring co-creation with stakeholders and reinforcing long-term ownership of the solutions.

2.3.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

Finland's National Strategy (2005), [the National Climate Change Adaption plan 2022](#), Flood Risk Management Act (No. 620/2010), and Land use and Building Decree enacted under the Land use and Building Act (132/1999) form the ground for City of Lappeenranta climate strategy. As further outlined in the [Finnish country fiche](#), in 2017, the majority of Finnish municipalities implemented action on climate change adaptation. By the end of 2015, regional flood risk management plans were published for every significant flood risk area (21 areas) and implementation of identified measures is ongoing. The [climate programme of the city of Lappeenranta for 2021-2030](#) forms the basis for the carbon neutrality target by 2030 and its long-term emission reduction targets. The City strategy (LPR2037) sets out its long-term operational and financial objectives. According to the City strategy land use planning should aim to ensure that stormwater management considers the status and quality of water bodies where stormwater is discharged. A [stormwater management plan](#) (Ramboll Finland Oy, 2021) was developed for the city of Lappeenranta to prevent problems caused by stormwater, such as flood damage and water pollution, and to maintain the natural water cycle, such as the water retention and groundwater recharge. The aim is also to manage stormwater as cost-effectively as possible. The stormwater management plan underlines the importance of promoting stormwater management consideration at all stages of development and construction (i.e., land use planning, building control and maintenance).

2.3.2 Oristano, Italy

In Italy, climate change adaptation governance began with the adoption of the [Italian Climate Adaptation Strategy](#) in 2015, addressing key socio-economic and environmental sectors. Developed through impact and vulnerability assessments, policy analysis, and a public consultation, the NAS aims to raise awareness, identify vulnerabilities and adaptation options, engage stakeholders, and provide tools to guide effective action. To operationalize the strategy, [Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici \(PNACC\)](#) (National Adaptation Plan - NAP) was approved in 2017, offering guidance for ministries, regions, and local authorities to mainstream adaptation into policies. At the regional level, about half of the regions have initiated strategies or plans, ranging from revising regulatory tools to supporting municipalities under the Covenant of Mayors. Sardinia represents one of the most advanced cases, with its [Regional Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change \(RASCC\)](#), which assesses vulnerabilities, defines indicators and priorities, and outlines governance models for implementation. Aligned with the national strategic axes, the RASCC emphasizes knowledge, participation, communication, and governance as key factors for integrating adaptation policies and actively involving local authorities in sustainable resource management and risk prevention.

Adaptation governance at the demonstrator level

Wetland management in Oristano is challenging. The fragmented governmental responsibilities impede the timely implementation of actions. The various types of protected areas, such as RAMSAR, Natura 2000 sites, Important Bird Areas (IBA) and Marine Protected Areas (MPA) are managed by different governance instruments and different public bodies, while in reality they are part of the same coastal system. The need for better coordination and communication among the various levels of governance, the need for more active involvement of local communities and the need for adaptive management led to the coastal contract, as a more unified and flexible governance model.

2.3.3 West Country Region, United Kingdom

In 2021 Natural England, the UK government's statutory advisor for the natural environment, imposed a stop to all development in designated river catchments where water quality was failing targets due to nutrient enrichment. These catchments are now subject to Nutrient Neutrality (NN) planning rules. Locally, this means any new development must mitigate additional phosphates entering waterbodies via additional load on the sewage system. Mitigation can be either on the development site itself, or off-site, delivered through land use change elsewhere within the catchment. Off-site mitigation usually means reduced inputs from agriculture or work to improve sewage treatment by water companies.

- The Conservation of Habitats and Species Regulations 2017 translate the European Habitats Directive into UK law. It sets out measures for the protection of natural habitats and wild fauna and flora. This is the legal basis for the Nutrient Neutrality ruling.

Currently, nutrient neutrality policy is focused on land use changes within the catchment area, using a calculator that assesses phosphate reductions based on nutrient export coefficients from different land uses. For example, changing from dairy farmland to woodland will deliver $0.47\text{kg Ha}^{-1}\text{ yr}^{-1}$ phosphate mitigation. This approach does not recognize the enhanced benefits which could be achieved by focusing land use change along the river corridor. It identifies only constructed wetlands as a form of additional treatment. Initially, WRT intended to develop Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW) on farms. However, there are difficulties with adapting this solution to diffuse pollution, with intermittent and variable inflows impacting on effectiveness. Alongside this, WRT identified issues around compliance with existing agricultural regulations (Environment Agency UK) and due to the high costs of land purchase when phosphate credits were not available at the outset. Therefore, alternative solutions such as wetland riparian buffers have been prioritized.

Current evidence on the effectiveness of natural process led NBS to deliver multiple benefits is limited (Robotham et al, 2022). Through TransformAr WRT aimed to increase the evidence base for the benefits of NBS, including buffer strips and habitat restoration, within the region. Strategic implementation of this type of NBS should deliver multiple co-benefits addressing the other risks identified in the Environment Act (2021) including habitat loss, recreation and sediment loss to waterbodies.

- Environment Act 2021: Aims to improve air and water quality, tackle waste, increase recycling, halt the decline of species, and improve the country's natural environment to make it more resilient to climate shocks. This environment act does not directly target adaptation, however ensuring the protection and the development of the natural environment increases the ability of the territory to overcome climate-related stresses (e.g., natural buffer zones, increased permeability, etc.).

The desire to increase the evidence base for innovative NBS in the Westcountry demonstrator region and to deliver multiple co-benefits realized over long lead times is well aligned with the overarching objectives of the Climate Change Act (2008). Within the CCA there is a legal requirement to develop a National Adaption Programme (NAP) with objectives relating to climate adaptation and time-scaled proposals and policies to meet those objectives. The NAP sets out four overarching objectives to address the greatest risks and opportunities arising due to climate change:

- Increasing awareness;
- Increasing resilience to current extremes;
- Taking timely action for long-lead time measures;
- Addressing major evidence gaps

Despite the policy relevance and growing interest in NBS, the knowledge base is lacking evidence for lowland catchments typical of those in the south of England (Lockwood et al., 2022). There is also

uncertainty over the sustainability of water storage in such features, where rapid sediment deposition could diminish storage capacity over time (Lane, 2017). Thus, more evidence is required to support the delivery of wider benefits from NBS which underpin agri-environmental policies such as the UK Government's Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS), outlined in the Agriculture Act (2020). Alongside the Green Finance Strategy (2023) this could provide farmers with financial incentives for adopting NFM and other NBS, thereby increasing uptake more widely (Bark et al., 2021).

Through the delivery phase WRT were able to attempt state of the art adaptation through some of the innovative delivery and processes.

Although co-creation is now not specifically considered innovation, the adaptation pathway workshops looking at climate change risk regarding water and catchment management, were a first for the region. Actor participation was good, with consensus and reasonable alignment around some of the adaptive solutions considered.

The design of some of the NBS features created through TransformAr were innovative and utilized natural, low maintenance materials as part of the construction. There was also some innovation around redirecting nutrient enriched flows into a series of bunds and sediment traps, to remove more phosphate from the system.

These NBS delivered were designed to be replicable particularly through the nutrient neutrality credit formation. Although this credit system was not complete in time for the TransformAr project, its ability to raise credit funds for the construction of these solutions means that they are viable for future replication. Some of the solutions that are not fully aligned to nutrient neutrality may be viable through other funds such as UK Government Agri environment payments. The monitoring of these solutions using a real time phosphate sensor was also novel, in trying to capture the impacts of these solutions.

2.3.4 Galicia, Spain

The state of the art in TransformAr lies in advancing digitalization and real-time monitoring to strengthen resilience of aquaculture systems under climate change. The project integrates sensor-based data collection, predictive tools, and user-oriented decision-support systems to improve operational efficiency, safety, and adaptability. What distinguishes it is not only the technological feasibility of these solutions, but also their evaluation through user acceptance, social perception, and replication potential. By combining technical, socio-economic, and governance dimensions, the demonstrator in Galicia positions itself as a pioneering trial of how digital technologies can inform strategic adaptation pathways for policymakers, producers, and scientists facing climate-driven challenges.

In this context, TransformAr introduced a step change in adaptation practice, by:

- Deploying IoT-based real-time monitoring systems on mussel rafts, designed in collaboration with producers, providing continuous data on environmental and production parameters.
- Implementing sedimentological monitoring and morphodynamical modelling of clam sandbanks, integrating field data with Delft3D simulations for the first time at this scale in Galicia.
- Developing the Operational Resilience Index (RI) specifically for mussel aquaculture, integrating governance, collaboration, and risk management dimensions.
- Establishing a knowledge transfer framework, with open data on Zenodo, digital dashboards for producers, and extensive stakeholder engagement (Delphi processes, workshops, bilateral meetings).

This represents integrated, digitalized, and stakeholder-driven adaptation approaches, setting a benchmark for replication in other European aquaculture regions.

2.3.5 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

In Guadeloupe, climate adaptation strategies have historically focused on disaster risk management and emergency response, reflecting the archipelago's exposure to hurricanes, floods, and coastal hazards. National frameworks, such as France's *Plan National d'Adaptation au Changement Climatique* (PNACC), and the *Schéma Régional Climat Air Energie* (SRCAE) for Guadeloupe, provide an overarching policy basis. However, their implementation at the local level remains fragmented and limited in scope.

Existing adaptation practices:

- Coastal protection measures: Seawalls, mangrove restoration, and dune reinforcement have been implemented to reduce coastal erosion, but their coverage is uneven, and in some cases, they are undermined by ongoing sea-level rise.
- Disaster preparedness and early-warning systems: Météo-France provides hurricane tracking and alerts, complemented by local civil protection units. However, uptake among vulnerable households is inconsistent, and many residents lack the resources to act effectively on warnings.
- Water management strategies: Some investments in reservoir capacity and distribution networks have been made, but operational inefficiencies and pollution issues persist, especially on Grande-Terre.
- Health adaptation measures: Public health campaigns address mosquito-borne diseases (e.g. dengue, Zika, chikungunya), which are expected to worsen under climate change.

Gaps and challenges:

- Adaptation is often reactive rather than proactive, with emphasis on post-disaster recovery rather than anticipatory resilience building.
- Social innovation and behavioral change measures (e.g., nudging, participatory co-design) remain underdeveloped, despite their cost-effectiveness in raising awareness and reducing vulnerability.
- Access to adaptation resources is unequally distributed, with disadvantaged communities more exposed to risks and less able to benefit from existing infrastructure or digital tools.

TransformAr innovation and added value:

The demonstrator introduces behavioral and citizen-focused solutions—notably *nudging strategies, awareness campaigns, and digital engagement tools*—to complement hard infrastructure. These measures aim to:

- Encourage risk-aware behaviors at the household and community level.
- Strengthen citizen participation and inclusiveness, ensuring equitable access to adaptation resources (KPI 21).
- Generate social co-benefits (KPI 13), such as enhanced trust in governance, better preparedness for extreme events, and reduced health risks.

By embedding these approaches within a Living Lab framework, TransformAr ensures that solutions are co-created with local stakeholders, tested for social acceptability, and scalable across other Caribbean territories facing similar climate challenges.

3.0 Description of Solutions in TransformAr

TransformAr delivers integrated portfolios of adaptation solutions across six Lighthouse Demonstrators, combining ecosystem-based, digital, behavioral, governance and financial instruments tailored to local climate risks and socio-economic contexts. The solutions were selected and co-developed with local stakeholders and tested under real-world conditions to ensure replicability and scalability.

3.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

Behavioural Change and Awareness Raising

CAF – Application for crowd sensing and real time monitoring of climate change events. Addressing a gap in climate change adaptation by allowing citizen participation and digital technology to improve flood monitoring and response. The citizen application addresses a critical gap in Europe’s climate change adaptation framework by allowing citizen participation and digital technology to improve flood monitoring and response. The demand for such solutions is expected to grow as extreme flooding events become more frequent, making it an attractive tool for public agencies, private sector stakeholders, and local communities alike. There is an increasing emphasis on citizen engagement in climate adaptation strategies, aligning with EU directives to involve communities in disaster preparedness.

- **KPI:** Number of observations reported by citizens, user engagement metrics (logins, feedback provided)

Nature-Based Solutions

URB – New integrative biofiltration area in the city center as part of new urban adaptation standards, to reduce the amount of water led to storm water sewer systems, to filter harmful substances, and to filter stormwater into groundwater. The biofiltration system demonstrates the feasibility of decentralized nature-based stormwater management. It provides an efficient solution for filtering pollutants, while reducing the load on stormwater sewer systems. The system also acts as a flood buffer, redirecting and managing excess water during heavy rainfall events. There is an increasing demand for decentralized stormwater management solutions driven by urbanization, stricter environmental regulations, and public interest in sustainable practices. This demand is particularly notable in urban areas facing challenges from impervious surfaces and rising pollution levels. The biofiltration area for urban runoff is addressed to municipal governments and urban planners due to its ability to manage stormwater sustainably in urban centers.

- **KPI:** Reduction in peak runoff levels (%), water quality improvement (pollutant reduction %), increase in stormwater retention capacity

Technological and Digital Solutions

SWMM – Real-time monitoring of the stormwater system: flow rates and water quality to prevent pollution and manage runoff. The user interface is visual and browser-based, enabling access from smartphone or laptop. Collecting data to predict and manage flood events and stormwater pollution load. Growing urban areas require advanced water management solutions to handle increased runoff and pollution.

- **KPI:** Number of monitoring sensors installed real-time data accuracy and reliability (%)

Financial, Economic and Insurance Schemes

CEI – A data-driven tool to uncover citizen preferences for green and grey stormwater solutions - empowering cities to drive private investment and climate adaptation through smarter, targeted flood risk policies.

- KPI: Number of respondents

Note: KPI’s for Lappeenranta include specific metrics for each solution (URB, SWMM, CAF, CEI), aligned with climate adaptation goals. These include indicators such as reduction in stormwater runoff volume, usage rate of the CAF app, behavioral shifts based on CEI outcomes, and green infrastructure effectiveness. KPIs are measured against baseline conditions established in 2023 and will be assessed periodically through 2025. All indicators were selected for their contribution to measuring combined ecological and community resilience. The originally proposed performance indicator—comparison of flood-related outcomes with and without predictive analytics—was not applicable due to the absence of an actual flood event during the NBS installation and operation phase. Consequently, real-world data for direct causal comparison could not be captured within the timeframe of the project.

Impacts to water quality are defined in solutions URB and SWMM. Figure 3.1 visualizes main methods. The fundamental idea is to measure real-time data with limited number sensors. This set of sensors does not include direct measurements for nutrients or pH due to the durability and maintenance costs of the sensors. Instead, these water quality parameters are measured in the laboratory from influent and groundwater samples. Models taking account the flow rate (expected dilution), turbidity and conductivity will be applied to estimate the emission load (kg/a) or improvement (%). Estimation will include comparison of runoff water captured to groundwater filtered through the biofilter field and recipient lake water. The goal is to keep the models as simple as possible. For most of the described analyses different regression models can be applied. The laboratory analyzed samples provide a way to calibrate and validate the models.

Figure 3.1 Overview of main methods applied in describing solutions impacts to water quality.

3.2 West Country Region, United Kingdom

3.2.1 Nature Based Solutions

WRT developed several NBS across the Camel and Axe catchments. The ambition was to test a range of solutions across different parameters. The NBS primarily deals with diffuse agricultural pollution prior to the point of entry to the main water course. The project looks specifically at funding streams to pay for both the initial (capital) cost of delivery and the long-term maintenance and compensation to the landowner for loss of agricultural productive land (revenue). The creation of nature-based on farm Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) is relatively inexpensive, but landowners are unwilling to sign up in the numbers needed to have a significant effect without fair payment. Nutrient Neutrality provides an opportunity to leverage investment.

In total, ten potential intervention sites were identified, and five sites were selected for NBS delivery (Table 3.1), hosting a range of solutions to provide climate resilience including:

- nutrient mitigation
- drought resilience
- flood resilience
- biodiversity improvement from developers to pay for strategic nutrient mitigation on farms.

Solutions included farm ponds, floodplain wetland habitat restoration, sediment traps, and filtration or buffer strips. These types of solutions were also highlighted by stakeholders as part of the adaptation pathways co-creation workshops.

These solutions can be created individually or be combined and used in treatment trains according to the specific site conditions and pollution load. New and/or innovative ways to identify suitable strategic sites were tested, using a combination of GIS analysis, site surveys and chemical analysis of water and soils. The overriding deciding factor for site selection was always landowner willingness to participate. Another aspect tested by WRT was the minimum level of maintenance required to keep the interventions functioning as designed. The landowners involved often do not have the time or resources to carry out regular or complex maintenance activities.

Table 3.1 Nature based solutions delivered under TransformAr in the Westcountry Region, UK

Catchment	Site name	NGR	Intervention type	Delivery date	Monitoring
Axe	Snowdon Hill Farm	ST 30143 09188	New track and wetland buffer area	7/11/24-16/11/24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone footage • Sediment P analysis • Volume calculations • Downstream water quality analysis • VESS Assessment • Soil nutrient analysis
			Sediment traps		
			Creation of an ephemeral wetland		

Camel	Chubbs Farm	ST 02689	30960	Leaky dam cascade	19/11/24-20/11/24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone footage • Timelapse photography • Biodiversity surveys • Upstream and downstream water quality analysis
				Wetland enhancement		
	Trethick Farm	SX 72053	04319	Cross track drains	Summer 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone footage • Biodiversity surveys • Sediment P analysis • Volume calculations • Downstream water quality analysis • VESS Assessment • Soil nutrient analysis • Electric fishing
			Sediment traps			
			Scrapes			
	Penvose Campsite	SX 78006	05164	Leaky dam cascade	04/09/2023-06/09/2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone footage • Biodiversity surveys • Upstream and downstream water quality analysis • Electric fishing • Continuous water quality monitoring (EC and level)
				Pond enhancement		
				Scrape cascade		
				Tree plantation and coppicing		

	Worthyvale Farm	SX 10972 85977	Barrier removal	30/08/2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electric fishing
			Sediment removal		
			Pond reinstatement		
	Slaughterbridge Farm	SX 10890 85370	Interception of road runoff into sediment trap and swale	Not delivered within project timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drone footage • Biodiversity surveys • Upstream and downstream water quality analysis • Electric fishing
			Cross slope hedgerow planting		
			Riparian buffer strip		
			Online scrape creation		

Snowdon Farm

At Snowdon Hill Farm, inundation of the lower section of an arable field prompted the farmer to move it to a more stable and sustainable grassland. A new track was created to reduce compaction on part of the field (Figure 3.2A) and an area of 1.63ha (4.0ac) was taken out of primary production for the interventions. A series of five sediment traps and scrapes/swales were installed (Figure 3.2B) to slow sediment and nutrient-rich run-off from the adjacent steeper slopes and create an ephemeral wetland area. The monitoring at Snowdon was limited to out-of-water methodologies due to the ephemeral nature of the problem run-off.

Figure 3.2 A) Plan view of the planned series of sediment traps/scrapes and track installed at Snowdon Farm, with flow direction marked. B) the scrapes after installation.

Chubbs Farm

At Chubbs, two streams meet and flow from neighboring farms through a permanent pasture and then woodland. A cascade of leaky dams was created within the woodland to slow flows and allow sediment to deposit behind the structures (Figure 3.3). There were plans for wetland creation within the fields above the woodland, but landowner illness prevented this from materializing.

Figure 3.3 A) The location of interventions at Chubbs Farm, B, C and D) Photographs of leaky dams #4, #1, #2 & #3, respectively.

Trethick Farm

Trethick is a dairy farm in the Camel catchment. Land-management here includes temporary and permanent grassland as well as arable rotation. A small field (0.46ha) was taken out of intensive management and a total of seven scrapes were dug to slow flows of runoff and capture sediment from the track and surrounding fields (Figure 3.4). Cross track drains were also planned but not delivered.

Figure 3.4 A) Interventions installed at Trethick Farm, B) An oblique view of the same field shown in (A).

Penvose Farm Campsite

Penvose sits on the River Allen, a tributary of the River Camel. Five leaky dams were installed in the tributary in an attempt to slow flows, trap sediment and divert river water into the surrounding wetland habitat during peak floods. Three scrapes and a pond were also dug, designed to hold water from springs and overland flow, decommissioning a drainage ditch which ran parallel to the river, these flows then rejoin the river at the edge of the field. Trees were also planted around the pond and alongside the river for habitat enhancement, nutrient uptake and carbon storage (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5 A) The NBS interventions delivered at Penvose, B) the pond C) a series of interconnected scrapes and swales

Worthyvale

This estate is located in the Upper Camel system where the river first develops from a network of small tributaries. There were two disused inline trout ponds, utilizing river water via a weir-controlled inlet and a downstream sluice-controlled outlet. The ponds were heavily sedimented with high nutrient concentrations due to addition of fish feed and surface water run off over their lifetime. Initially there was an idea to maintain the ponds as a treatment system for river water but eventually they were disconnected by removal of the weirs and blockage of the outlets (Figure 3.6 A-D). Sediment was removed to increase the capacity of the features as attenuation ponds. The sediment was spread over flat silage fields on top of the hill to reduce the likelihood of nutrients returning to the river.

During the winter the ponds occasionally overflow across the grassed buffer towards the river, which reduces the risk of contamination via this route. Removal of the weirs has improved the diversity of river habitat and increased fish passage above this location.

Figure 3.6 Interventions at Worthyvale Farm A) Works plan, B) Blocked inlet and weir removed, C) Pond A before, D) Pond A after intervention.

Slaughterbridge

Slaughterbridge interventions (at SX 10890 85370) were designed but not delivered within the timeframe of the TransformAr project. Planned interventions included interception of piped road runoff into a sediment trap and swale, cross slope hedgerow planting, a large (25m) riparian buffer strip, and online scrape creation within the buffer. The current plan is for this site to be delivered through Nutrient Neutrality and therefore be the first land change based nutrient credit in the Camel.

3.2.2 Financial, Economic and Insurance Schemes

Green Bonds to support long-term financing of nature-based infrastructure.

Due to the lack of direct funding for climate change adaptation, WRT tested the viability of using new nutrient credit schemes to leverage greater funding for climate change adaptation measures. Nature-based solutions such as ponds, leaky dams, swales and bunds help to both mitigate nutrient pollution and support climate change adaptation, meaning finance available to tackle nutrient pollution issues also support adaptation efforts.

Nutrient credit schemes were introduced in the UK to tackle water quality issues. Based on the Dutch Nitrogen Case, which ruled that nutrient loading into internationally important sites (SPA's, SAC's and Ramsar Sites) must be limited, this UK legislation requires developers to offset excess nutrients, so that new dwellings do not add additional burden to sewage systems and wastewater treatment plants. Whilst in the Netherlands this led to the development of nitrogen permits, in the UK planning permission for property has been suspended in SSSIs and SAC's until developers can obtain phosphate credit purchase agreements, proving they are offsetting the additional projected nutrient load expected from their housing project(s).

To fulfil the demands of this new legislation, nutrient credits & pilot marketplaces began appearing in affected areas across the UK (Natural England, 2023). Emergent markets involve varying degrees of public and private sector finance.

Nutrient credit markets have been constructed in a wide variety of ways. For example, in the Solent in Hampshire, nutrient credits are entered into a bidding process through an online marketplace, whereby private landholders and buyers can interact through an online auction. Public-sector funding was used to establish the virtual platform; however, trading is managed directly between private partners, meaning private finance is used to pay for project development. The auction mechanism means the cost/unit of phosphate is contingent on demand (<https://www.solentnutrientmarket.org.uk/>).

Figure 3.7 model of the Solent Nutrient Catchment Market, demonstrating how nutrient credit schemes function in other parts of the UK.

3.2.3 Nutrient Credit Schemes in Devon and Cornwall

In the Westcountry region, although several natural capital marketplaces have emerged to facilitate the trade of ecosystem services ([LINC Cornwall](#), [North Devon Biosphere](#)), an online marketplace explicitly designed to support the trade of nutrient credits is not currently available. Instead, local authorities have worked with NGO’s such as the Westcountry Rivers Trust and the Devon Wildlife Trust to engage landowners in credit development projects. In the Camel and Axe catchments, WRT worked to find strategic opportunities for the development of NBS that would both mitigate nutrient pollution and support climate change adaptation by slowing flows and re-naturalizing waterways. As WRT have a strong track-record of landowner engagement, we operate as a ‘broker’ between credit purchasers and suppliers, ensuring excellent environmental outcomes.

3.2.4 Blended Finance: Camel Catchment

In Cornwall the local authority, Cornwall Council, volunteered to invest the initial capital for nature-based solutions, paying landowners an up-front sum to develop NBS for nutrient mitigation (& climate adaptation) on their land, with the stipulation that the council would own the resultant credits. The local authority may then sell the credits to developers to recover their costs. This blended finance model has several key advantages but also presents several key challenges when assessing the bankability or financial sustainability of climate adaptation.

Benefits:

- Use of public funding to develop credit projects accelerates outcomes, as risk to private developers is removed.
- Resultant ecosystem services do not need to represent high revenue/rate of return, as local authorities do not need to generate profit.
- Planning authorities within local governments are well-placed to sell resultant credits to developers, as they have a pre-established professional relationship
- Prevents stagnation at the ‘seed funding’ or project development phase, often encountered when attempting to attract private investment for nature-based solutions.

Challenges:

- Lack of consistent value/unit of phosphate makes valuation of NBS difficult, delaying uptake. Landowners need a consistent value to make informed decisions against other land use options.
- Lack of clarity around future liability for ecosystem service assets, as well as potential litigation risks associated with delivery failure. Results in delay and uncertainty for landowners.
- Focus on nutrient credits in order to meet statutory demand results in failure to capitalize potential additional revenue streams associated with the NBS created. Does not help to facilitate future private-sector investment.

A further appraisal of the benefits and challenges to blended finance will be included in the discussion of the bankability interview process.

3.3 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

Behavioural Change and Awareness Raising

- NUDG – The innovation combines smart technology with behavioral nudging to promote water conservation among hotel guests. In participating hotels in Guadeloupe, digital shower sensors are installed to measure shower duration and water usage. These sensors collect real-time data, which is uploaded to a central platform (Aquadio Hub) for analysis. Alongside the sensors, visual nudging materials – such as stickers, flyers, and feedback forms – are placed in bathrooms to raise awareness and subtly encourage guests to reduce their shower time. The experiment is conducted in phases: before and after introducing the nudges, to compare behavior changes. Feedback is also gathered from hotel guests and managers through surveys and interviews, providing both quantitative and qualitative insights.

Local Adaptation Fund

The Local Adaptation Fund (AF) is a blended finance tool boosting local climate adaptation in the agriculture and tourism sectors in Guadeloupe. It supports vulnerable groups and offers a replicable model for other climate change-exposed territories.

3.4 Galicia Region, Spain

The Galician demonstrator focuses on adapting shellfish aquaculture and harvesting to the challenges posed by climate change. The activity has been selected due to its significant role in the regional economy and its susceptibility to climate change, as outlined in the Galician Climate Change Strategy 2050 and in the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019-2023).

Mussel aquaculture, accounting for approximately 40% of the European aquaculture production, is a vital sector employing nearly 4,000 individuals in the region. Similarly, clam culture farms and shellfish harvesting along coastal land concessions and intertidal sandbanks, directly employ around 4,300 people, with approximately 90% being self-employed women.

Key climate-related threats affecting shellfish aquaculture include the potential intensification of extreme weather events, unpredictable fluctuations in mussel seed availability, and the expected increase in harmful algal blooms and acidification. Also, changes in coastal oceanographic and hydrological factors will alter the sedimentary composition of shellfish banks, impacting shellfish productivity and mortality. In extreme cases, this could result in the loss of these habitats.

Within TransformAr, three solutions have been tested to comprehensively grasp the nature of these changes and bolster adaptation to climate change:

Governance Schemes

RI – Development of local Resilience Institutions to coordinate climate adaptation across shellfish aquaculture stakeholders and environmental managers.

Technological and Digital Solutions

Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM)

Digitalization of mussel rafts to enable real-time environmental and production monitoring, tailored to stakeholders' needs. It gathers extensive data to optimize management in the face of climate challenges. The system tracks raft movements, precise location, mussel ropes weight increase, and potential vandalism. A GPS device enables early warnings of mooring failure. A combination of gyroscope, accelerometer, and magnetometer detects displacement, rotation, orientation, and sudden changes. Load cells allow the estimation of estimate mussel growth. Meteorological and oceanographic parameters include air temperature, pressure, salinity, water transparency, and water column temperature, key for assessing marine heat waves, low salinity waves or changes in wind patterns.

Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)

Cost-effective and collaborative method for monitoring substrates in intertidal shellfish beds Simple, low-cost methodology allowing for the acquisition of long data series and improving knowledge for decision-making, in cooperation with stakeholders.

3.5 City of Egaleo, Greece

The Egaleo demonstrator focused on behavioural change, governance innovation, digital monitoring, and financial mechanisms to strengthen urban climate resilience.

Behavioural Change and Awareness Raising

Citizen engagement was advanced through the Climate Awareness and Education (CAE) and AWARE tools. These combined awareness-raising activities with participatory workshops and local climate education campaigns, ensuring that residents were not only informed but also actively involved in shaping adaptation pathways. The approach aimed to increase community ownership of solutions and foster behavioural change toward more climate-conscious practices.

Governance Schemes

Decision Support Instruments (DSI) were introduced to promote transparent, participatory decision-making for municipal authorities, embedding climate resilience into local governance processes. In parallel, Inclusive Housing (CIH) models were developed, integrating climate-resilient design features into social housing schemes. These models aimed to reduce vulnerability among low-income households and ensure equitable access to adaptation benefits.

Technological and Digital Solutions

The demonstrator deployed Sensor Control Systems (SCS) to enable real-time monitoring of air quality and urban heat island effects. This data was directly linked to participatory platforms and municipal

systems, allowing timely interventions, such as targeted greening or traffic management measures, based on actual conditions. The digital tools also supported improved communication with citizens, bridging local monitoring with community engagement.

Financial, Economic and Insurance Schemes

Finally, the project piloted urban climate risk insurance instruments (INSUR) designed to enhance resilience among vulnerable populations and critical infrastructure. These instruments were tested as complementary tools to municipal adaptation planning, aiming to mobilize resources for risk reduction and provide safety nets in the face of extreme weather events.

3.6 Oristano, Italy

The main challenges addressed in the demo site are linked to prolonged summer droughts, which not only heighten competition for water resources but also increase wildfire risk, desertification, and coastal erosion. Heavy rainfall and flooding contribute to soil erosion and the dispersion of pollutants into aquatic systems, while shifts in hydrological regimes and water quality parameters such as salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, and turbidity compromise lagoon ecosystems, diminishing fish productivity and facilitating the spread of invasive species. In the longer term, sea-level rise poses the risk of losing entire coastal lagoons, with significant consequences for biodiversity and fisheries.

The TransformAr project demonstrates how the restoration and protection of coastal wetlands, supported by technological innovation and participatory governance, can effectively mitigate the impacts of climate change on local communities and ecosystems. The project aims to enhance stakeholder awareness of the role of wetlands in climate resilience, strengthen scientific knowledge to support evidence-based planning, test scalable models for ecological improvement, and foster inclusive governance and community engagement.

In Oristano, TransformAr will focus on two solutions: a governance solution for improving wetland management, and a NBS to restore and protect the lagoon and enhance the natural role of the wetland.

Governance Schemes - COAST

The COAST governance model was developed to support integrated management of coastal wetlands and overcome institutional fragmentation. Launched in 2021 and supported by 11 municipalities of the Gulf of Oristano, the Province, the Oristano Reclamation Consortium, and the Regional Government.

Within the **TransformAr project**, MEDSEA played a strategic role in scaling up and consolidating the Coastal Contract as an operational tool to promote wetland conservation and adaptation across Oristano Gulf. Several key activities have been carried out under TransformAr to support this goal:

- Strengthening Participatory Governance

A **structured and inclusive participatory process** has been activated to foster broader and more active engagement from local stakeholders—including public authorities, fishing and farming communities, tourism operators, and civil society. This process aimed to ensure that involvement of all actors in shaping shared strategies for wetland protection and climate adaptation, reinforcing the legitimacy and ownership of the Contract.

- Development of the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO)

One of the most significant contributions of TransformAr is the creation of the **Local Wetland Observatory**, a key action foreseen in the Contract's Action Plan. The LWO serves as a scientific and technical hub dedicated to:

- Monitoring the ecological status and trends of wetlands in the Gulf of Oristano (data available [here](#));
- Identifying emerging threats and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation and adaptation actions;
- Producing data-driven reports, maps, and factsheets to inform decision-making (available [here](#)).

Staffed by a multidisciplinary team with high scientific expertise, the LWO integrates data from both public and private sources and collaborates closely with the Technical Secretariat to ensure that scientific insights directly support the implementation and monitoring of the Contract.

The outputs of the LWO are disseminated to public institutions, private actors, and local communities, contributing to:

- **Informing policymakers**, through up-to-date scientific data that supports wetland management and climate resilience strategies;
- **Raising stakeholder awareness and engagement**, recognizing wetlands as essential to the area's cultural and ecological identity;
- **Strengthening capacity building and advocacy**, enabling communities to co-develop a shared vision for the territory and collaborate on sustainable development opportunities.

Moreover, by supporting the replicability of the Coastal Contract model in other Sardinian coastal areas, the project has contributed to scaling up good practices for climate adaptation and wetland protection across the region.

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) - SMART GATE

As part of a large Nature-Based Solutions is the Smart Gate (SG) system, designed for adaptive water management in the San Giovanni lagoons. This technological solution facilitates better control of water circulation and monitoring of key water quality parameters.

From an ecological, geomorphological, and sedimentological perspective, the critical issues of the San Giovanni - Marceddi lagoon and pond system, with evident implications for the environment and productivity, can be detailed as follows:

- Disruption of water exchanges to and from the sea (including natural daily tidal flows) and limitations on the distribution towards the open sea of finer sediment fractions and suspended materials due to the construction of the Marceddi bridge. This aspect has led to the deterioration of water quality in the lagoon and its productivity, as well as widespread problems of poor oxygenation and water turnover between adjacent basins and the sea. (see the 8.2 Baseline data for more detail).
- Progressive silting of the internal basin of San Giovanni resulting from the construction of the embankment and the interception of continental water flows. While representing a crucial condition for the development of fish farming in the lagoon, the clear separation provided by the internal embankment between freshwater areas at the estuary and the rest of the lagoon leads to a gradual reduction in the depth of the estuarine basin, a decrease in flood buffering capacity, and the development of phenomena of anoxia related to limited water exchanges, especially during the summer season.

In an attempt to address the highlighted issues, a NBS is partially under development with multi-financing, including support from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under the 6.5.1 action, managed by the Municipality of Terralba, and the development of a SMART GATE under the TransformAr project.

The TransformAr solution focuses on testing the functionality of the SMART GATE with a remote control and installing a monitoring system into the lagoon with the aim of improving the current challenges with synergic, efficient, and participative managing of lamination lagoon problems, due to climate changes, and fishing practices, due to general faunal pauperization.

The SMART GATE has the aim of regulating the water circulation between the mouth area and San Giovanni Pond, to guarantee the better condition in terms of ecological parameters and control the hydraulic levels. In a state of equilibrium, the SMART GATE remains closed and is opened only in the event of hydraulic risk or alteration of the chemical-physical state of the water, thus allowing a flow of freshwater from the mouth areas of various rivers and canals into the pond.

The TransformAr solution incorporated the use of hydrometers and multi-parameter sensors to measure various factors such as pH levels, conductivity, redox potential, temperature, dissolved oxygen levels, turbidity, and hydrometric levels. A weather station enhanced our understanding of weather conditions during SMART GATE operations. The monitoring instruments, positioned in the most important areas of the lagoon, and the baseline from ARPAS were useful to set up the conceptual model that regulated the opening and closing of the SG.

The conceptual model considered variables related to flood risk (hydrometric level) and the ecological state of the lagoon, with a significant emphasis on fishing activities (salinity, pH, temperature, etc.). Thresholds for each parameter were determined based on an analysis of the initial conditions and the optimal ecological conditions for the species inhabiting the lagoon following the Italian Environmental Law D.Lgs. 152/2006, especially relevant to shellfish farming.

The opening and closing of the SMART GATE are managed remotely through the IT platform in most cases, or physically if required. The Smart Gate regulation system is based on a control algorithm integrated into a Decision Support System (DSS) that processes real-time data from the monitoring stations to determine whether the Smart Gate should open or close.

The system logic combines three sources of input:

- Hydraulic and environmental data collected by the sensors
- Ecological and regulatory criteria derived from Legislative Decree 152/2006 for the protection of fish fauna and shellfish farming
- Management needs expressed by local stakeholders, such as requests for water exchange or mitigation of critical conditions for production.

The SMART GATE operating model (when, how, and under which conditions the SMART GATE had to be opened or closed) was tested with a preliminary set-up. Due to delays in the implementation of the solution, it was not possible to carry out a long testing phase, but thanks to funds from other European projects the system will remain active and will be tested for at least one year. Furthermore, the fishing sector was actively engaged in the process to ensure their requirements were considered and to share scientific insights, fostering a collaborative and mutually beneficial approach.

Monitoring Strategy and Methodology

The monitoring system was designed to assess the environmental, social, technological, and institutional dimensions of the implemented solutions, with the objective of evaluating how Nature-Based Solutions and participatory governance enhance territorial resilience to climate change.

Monitoring activities focused on the improvement of water quality and management, the ecological performance of lagoon systems, and the functionality of stakeholder engagement mechanisms. Special attention was paid to the operational performance of the hydraulic regulation systems—particularly their contribution to improving lagoon water quality, which is critical for biodiversity conservation, fish productivity, and sustainable wetland management. In parallel, social and institutional dynamics were monitored, including levels of community engagement, dissemination of knowledge, and cooperation among public authorities. Economic and managerial aspects, such as implementation timelines, infrastructure costs, and potential effects on the local fishing economy, were also taken into account.

Rather than segmenting metrics by type, the evaluation methodology integrated both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a multidimensional understanding of project performance. Quantitative data—such as the number of public events, surface area restored, or financial indicators—were combined with qualitative assessments related to system reliability, stakeholder feedback, and observed improvements in ecological and governance processes. This approach enabled a robust interpretation of outcomes, aligned with Horizon Europe guidelines for monitoring Nature-Based Solutions and participatory governance actions in climate adaptation contexts.

3.7 Expected Innovation

The TransformAr project demonstrates innovations across both technological and societal dimensions.

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL): According to the Grant Agreement, demonstrated actionable adaptive solutions are positioned at TRL 5 (“technology validated in relevant environment”) at the start of the project and are expected to reach TRL 7–8 during implementation, with several Innovation Packages progressing towards TRL 9 (commercial exploitation) after the project end.

Examples include:

- Technological tools such as the Storm Water Management Model (SWMM), Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM), Smart Gate (SG), and Integrated Constructed Wetland Monitoring (ICWM). These are designed to achieve validation in operational environments and readiness for deployment in real-world conditions.

Societal Readiness Levels (SRL):

The Social Readiness of Transformational Adaptive Blocks (TABs) progresses from SRL 2 (“identification of expectations, interests and concerns of stakeholders”) to SRL 5 (“involvement of stakeholders”), ensuring that solutions are not only technically viable but also socially embedded and acceptable. Behavioural and citizen-focused tools—such as the *Climate Awareness Framework (CAF)*, *Choice Experiment for Insurance (CEI)*, and *Nudging (NUDG)*—aim for SRL 5, demonstrating strong citizen engagement, awareness, and social acceptance.

Integrated innovation:

TransformAr’s novelty lies in the coordinated deployment of solutions in site-specific portfolios, rather than as isolated measures. Each Region-Specific Portfolio (RSP) combines Nature-Based Solutions, digital tools, governance innovations, behavioural approaches, and financial mechanisms. This systemic innovation goes beyond incremental adaptation, fostering transformational adaptation pathways tailored to local climate risks.

The Living Lab principle, explicitly embedded in WP1, ensures that stakeholders and citizens co-own the solutions. This co-creation process accelerates upscaling and replication, ensures legitimacy, and enhances social innovation by building trust and fostering cross-sectoral networks.

In summary, the expected innovation of TransformAr is twofold:

1. Technological — advancing multiple adaptive tools to market-ready TRL levels.
2. Societal — embedding solutions within communities, achieving SRL 5 through co-creation, thus ensuring long-term viability, scalability, and replicability across Europe.

3.8 Bankability of Demonstrator Solutions

West Country, UK — Nature-Based Solutions for Nutrient Pollution Mitigation and Flood Management

In the West Country, Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) such as river restoration, wetland creation, and riparian buffers were assessed through *cost–benefit analysis (CBA)* and ecosystem service valuation. Results demonstrated a cost–benefit ratio of ~ 2.4 , mainly due to avoided flood damage, nutrient retention, and biodiversity gains. Maintenance costs are relatively low, and sustainability is supported by emerging ecosystem service markets, including nutrient and biodiversity credits. Bankability depends on embedding NBS into agricultural and catchment policies, with engagement from landowners and water companies.

Guadeloupe, FR — Financing Instruments, Revenue Models, Stakeholder Engagement

In Guadeloupe, the bankability of adaptation solutions is anchored around innovative financing mechanisms tailored to the region’s specific conditions. One key instrument developed is the local adaptation fund, designed to pool public, private, and donor resources to support interventions at scale, particularly in coastal resilience and water management. Furthermore, nutrient credit schemes have been explored as a mechanism to monetize ecosystem services—allowing hotels, municipalities, and other actors to trade credits linked to water quality improvements. These blended models support financial viability by combining revenue streams with public subsidies and risk-sharing components. The TransformAr project’s interviews with local financial stakeholders revealed both interest in these models and caution about risks (e.g., long payback periods, regulatory uncertainty). As such, the Guadeloupe demonstrator serves as a real-world testbed demonstrating that even in territories with limited fiscal capacity, structuring financial instruments around ecosystem benefits and service-based revenues can increase the feasibility of NBS at scale.

Oristano, IT — Smart Gate and Wetland Restoration

Bankability for the Oristano site highlights opportunities such as payment for ecosystem services, enabling farmers and cooperatives to generate certified environmental credits and new income streams through sustainable practices. Community engagement can be fostered through crowdfunding, translating awareness into tangible support for smaller projects. For larger investments, a local adaptation bond could attract ESG-oriented capital by linking repayment to the long-term benefits of green and blue infrastructure. Finally, a Coastal Contract Fund would provide a stable governance and financing platform, pooling public, private, and philanthropic resources. Together, these instruments diversify funding sources, reduce reliance on EU grants, and strengthen both private sector involvement and community participation, positioning Oristano as a frontrunner in innovative coastal resilience finance.

Galicia, ES — Predictive Tools for Aquaculture

The Galician demonstrator deployed Resilience Index (RI), Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM), and Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM) to support clam and mussel aquaculture. Assessments combining *CBA*, *predictive modelling*, and *stakeholder surveys* suggest that these tools reduced sectoral production losses by 10–

15% during extreme events and improved operational efficiency by around ~8%. The upfront costs of digital tools are modest compared to avoided losses, making them highly bankable. Long-term sustainability could be reinforced by cooperative financing among aquaculture associations and alignment with national adaptation strategies.

Lappeenranta, FI — Urban NBS and Stormwater Management

The Lappeenranta demonstrator implemented Stormwater Monitoring, Biofiltration Areas for Urban Runoff, and Awareness Raising Solutions. The *Koulukatu Street pilot (245 m²)* had an investment cost of €93,100 (prices 2022), including €10,000 for supporting grey infrastructure. Annual maintenance was €2,076/year, slightly lower than the grey baseline (€2,118/year). *CBA and willingness-to-pay (WTP) experiments* estimated annual savings of ~€0.9M if scaled across the city, with a return on investment (ROI) < 10 years. Bankability can be secured through municipal green bonds aligned with EU Taxonomy, supported by partnerships with insurance companies to establish risk reduction funds.

Egaleo, GR — Digital and Social Innovation Solutions

Egaleo introduced Smart Weather Station (SWS), Climate Innovation Hub (CIH), Demand for Social Infrastructures, and AWAR modules. *CBA and choice experiments* showed that investments of €50–70k generated avoided damages exceeding €0.5M/year during extreme weather events. Maintenance costs are minimal, since most measures are digital and community driven. Bankability is reinforced by integration into municipal budgets and co-financing with private IT and innovation partners. Beyond financial viability, the solutions deliver strong social co-benefits such as citizen awareness, active participation, and improved governance capacity.

Cross-Cutting Insights

- NBS investments (West Country, Oristano, Lappeenranta) consistently show positive cost–benefit ratios and long-term savings, outperforming grey alternatives.
- Digital solutions (Galicia, Egaleo) deliver rapid returns with modest costs, mainly through avoided damage and operational efficiencies.
- Hybrid coastal approaches (Guadeloupe) highlight the value of integrating ecosystem services into financial models.
- Financing pathways differ by context: ecosystem service markets (UK), insurance and blue economy funds (FR), CAP eco-schemes (IT), cooperative sector funding (ES), municipal green bonds (FI), and IT partnerships (GR).
- Across all demonstrators, TransformAr confirms that transformational adaptation solutions are economically viable, investable, and socially beneficial, directly addressing Specific Objective 5 (SO5) of the Grant Agreement.

4.0 Expected Impacts & Mitigations

4.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

4.1.1 Overview of the Expected Impacts

The expected impacts of solutions demonstrated are described in Table 3. All four solutions can be expected to have an impact on flood vulnerability, and social acceptance or acceptance in city planning. CAF and CEI can have long-term effects on water quality. However, in CAF and CEI the impact is not measured with indicators due to the nature of the impact. URB with monitoring system, and the influence together with the groundwater is analyzed. This empirical information can be utilized together with existing water quality of recipient lake and wetlands to evaluate the impacts. Economic assessment and impacts in this frame will be done via empirical cost estimates and comparing to alternative solutions typically applied in Lappeenranta.

Table 4.1 The expected impacts of solutions demonstrated

Expected impact	URB	SWMM	CAF	CEI
Flood Vulnerability				
Gathering runoff (stormwater) from streets and leading them to biofiltration will help free capacity from drainage and mitigate flood and drought risks.	x			
Monitoring volume flows and surface levels provides novel information and warnings.		x		
Distributed stormwater management mitigate flood risks	x	x		x
Water Quality				
Realtime monitoring of URB together with laboratory measurements provides information on runoff and groundwater quality.		x		
Biofiltering field utilizes nutrients and filters urban emissions	x			
Acceptance				
City planning gain novel information to support decision making and planning	x	x	x	x
Citizen's awareness of environmental effects of runoff and choices for mitigating the risks and impacts increase	x		x	x
Economic Costs				
Solution costs are compared to traditional alternatives and reflected to benefits expected.	x	x	x	x

4.1.2 Selected Indicators

The indicators for URB and SWMM are mostly calculated from the monitored water qualities and measured flows, with calibration from the laboratory analyses. In addition, prior information and projected information, for example, on rain events, are utilized to construct the indicators. The CAF solution is mainly aimed at providing information to citizens of the area, so most of the indicators will be determined from the user engagement.

Table 4.2 Selected Indicators

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
Nature-Based Stormwater Solution	Reduction in flooding events. Mitigating drought risk.	Reduction in peak runoff levels (%)	Real-time monitoring via sensors
	Improved water quality, increased knowledge of main water quality parameters.	Water quality improvements (pollutant reduction %)	Real-time monitoring via sensors and water sampling campaigns
	Mitigating flood risk.	Increase in stormwater retention capacity: 2670 m3 stormwater entering NBS/year	Real-time monitoring via sensors
Stormwater Monitoring	Increased knowledge and awareness of key stakeholders. City planning gain novel information to support decision making and planning.	Number of monitoring sensors installed: water quality 3 sensors flow rate 6 sensors	Sensor deployment tracking
	Improved knowledge of flood risk.	Real-time data accuracy and reliability (%)	Data verification & models
Citizen App	Citizen's engagement	Number of citizen reports submitted: 52	App analytics, participants in events (Open Days, Citizen workshop)
	Citizen's awareness of environmental effects of runoff and choices for mitigating the risks and impacts increase	User engagement metrics Logins: 185 Active users: 86 Feedback provided: 14	

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
	Increased knowledge and awareness of key stakeholders at different levels (public and private sectors, economic categories, citizens, etc.)	<p>Participants in events, workshops, webinars, training sessions: 920</p> <p>Improvement in community awareness on flood risk (%)</p>	
Choice Experiment	<p>This research provides valuable insights into how to encourage private investments in stormwater management (SWM) to address urban flooding risks. It will reveal residents' preference of the SWM measures. These findings can help policymakers design more effective incentives and SWM strategies that align with residents' preferences, promoting broader adoption, which will promote the collective actions from citizens and improving urban flood resilience.</p>	<p>Norway: 1000 respondents</p> <p>Finland: 1013 respondents</p> <p>Finland exhibits a higher WTP for risk reduction (up to €4,820 for a 75% risk reduction), while Norway shows a stronger preference for runoff reduction (up to €3550 per household for a 50% runoff reduction). Aesthetic improvements are valued more in Finland (€1,257) than in Norway (€615).</p>	Survey analysis and economic modeling

4.1.3 Baseline Data

This section provides a concise summary of the baseline conditions for each demonstrator site, focusing on key indicators such as nutrient levels, chlorophyll-a concentrations, flood or heat events, and community awareness before the implementation of TransformAr solutions.

Baseline values were derived from a combination of historical monitoring datasets, regional surveys, and laboratory analyses, as reported in Deliverables D5.8. Measurements included water quality parameters (nutrients, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a), hydrological and climatic data (flood frequencies, temperature peaks, stormwater flows), and social indicators (stakeholder engagement, community awareness). Where available, national and regional monitoring systems (e.g., SYKE in Finland, ARPAS in Italy, CETMAR in Spain) were used to ensure reliability.

A full set of datasets, including metadata and raw measurements, is publicly archived on Zenodo to guarantee transparency and reproducibility.

Lappeenranta, Finland

- Flood risk / runoff: Precipitation baseline = 260 l/s/ha for a 5-minute rainfall event (hydrological model, SYKE, 2023).
- Nutrients in stormwater: Urban runoff typically contains 2–5 mg/L nitrogen and 0.1–0.5 mg/L phosphorus (literature-confirmed baseline).
- Community awareness: Prior to CAF, ~10–15% of residents engaged in adaptation issues (baseline from national monitoring groups).

Oristano, Italy (Marceddì lagoon and San Giovanni Pond)

Marceddì lagoon

- Chlorophyll-a: mean 18.1 µg/L (min 1.7 µg/L, max 115.2 µg/L) → indicative of moderate eutrophication, with episodic algal blooms.
- Nutrient levels: ammonium ~109 µg/L, nitrate ~328 µg/L, nitrite ~36 µg/L.
- Dissolved oxygen: ~7.6 mg/L (95% saturation) → generally acceptable, though variability is expected.
- Salinity: mean 29.0 → stronger marine influence; spatial gradient decreasing from the mouth towards inner basins.
- pH: mean 8.31 → slightly alkaline, within expected lagoon range.

San Giovanni Pond

- Chlorophyll-a: mean 37.4 µg/L (min 0.7 µg/L, max 135.0 µg/L) → clearly eutrophic, with frequent and intense algal blooms.
- Nutrient levels: ammonium ~131 µg/L, nitrate ~714 µg/L, nitrite ~40 µg/L.
- Dissolved oxygen: ~8.0 mg/L (97% saturation) → comparable to Marceddì, but under stronger nutrient pressure.
- Salinity: mean 18.2 → stronger freshwater input, lower dilution capacity and sharp decrease near river mouths
- pH: mean 8.39 → slightly alkaline, occasional peaks linked to photosynthetic activity.
- Baseline monitoring: 2016–2022, ARPAS and MEDSEA surveys.

Galicia, Spain (Ría de Arousa)

- Sea temperature: 14–24 °C, seasonal variation.
- Salinity: 32–36 PSU, optimal for mussel/clam habitat.
- Dissolved oxygen: 6–8 mg/L baseline.

- Harmful algal blooms: 2–3 events per year historically.
- Sediment composition: 0.1–2 mm grain size, organic matter 4–8%.

Egaleo, Greece

- Air quality: Baseline PM_{2.5} = 10–25 µg/m³, PM₁₀ = 20–50 µg/m³, CO₂ = 400–450 ppm (WHO guidelines, pre-project values).
- Microclimate: Summer heat peaks up to 35 °C, baseline humidity 40–70%.
- Awareness: Pre-project climate awareness only ~10–15% of residents engaged.

West Country, UK

- Phosphate: 0.1–0.3 mg/L, nitrate 1–10 mg/L in agricultural runoff.
- Sediment: 10–50 mg/L in rivers affected by farming runoff.
- Habitat health: Riparian vegetation cover baseline 30–50%.
- Community awareness: Pre-project citizen science and landowner participation <10%.

4.1.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

Monitoring approaches were designed to capture both technical performance and social impacts, using harmonized indicators across demonstrator sites.

Lappeenranta, Finland (URB, SWMM, CAF, CEI):

- **Biofiltration sampling (URB):** Stormwater entering the Koulukatu NBS was tracked with online probes (flow, turbidity, conductivity) and 30 laboratory samples taken from influent and groundwater.
- **SWMM:** Real-time monitoring calibrated with lab data, estimating pollutant loads and runoff reduction.
- **CAF analytics:** Citizen app logins, active users, feedback events, and workshop participation monitored to assess awareness and engagement.
- **Accreditation:** Methods follow Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and Finnish **Meteorological Institute** guidelines; lab analyses compliant with national standards.

URB: stormwater entering the Koulukatu NBS was monitored with an online sensor system. In addition, laboratory samples were taken from the water entering the manhole. A total of 30 samples were taken during the campaign from stormwater entering the NBS, and from groundwater both above and below NBS. All of the laboratory and online variables have been collected to Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Laboratory and online variables with corresponding units.

Variable	Measurement	Unit
Total nitrogen	Laboratory	mg/L
Temperature	Online	°C
pH-value	Laboratory	
Conductivity	Online	uS/cm
Turbidity	Laboratory/Online	NTU
TOC	Laboratory	mg/L
Flow	Online	L/s
Solids	Laboratory	mg/L
Flow speed	Online	m/s
Ammonium	Laboratory	mg/L
Ammonium-N	Laboratory	mg/L
Phosphorus (P2O5)	Laboratory	mg/L
Total phosphate	Laboratory	mg/L
Total phosphorus	Laboratory	mg/L
Nitrate	Laboratory	mg/L
Nitrate-N	Laboratory	mg/L
Phosphate	Laboratory	mg/L
Phosphate-P	Laboratory	mg/L
Hg (Mercury)	Laboratory	µg/L
Co (Cobalt)	Laboratory	µg/L
Cu (Copper)	Laboratory	µg/L
V (Vanadium)	Laboratory	µg/L
Zn (Zinc)	Laboratory	µg/L
Cd (Cadmium)	Laboratory	µg/L
Cr (Chromium)	Laboratory	µg/L
Ni (Nickel)	Laboratory	µg/L
Pb (Lead)	Laboratory	µg/L
Sb (Antimony)	Laboratory	µg/L
As (Arsenic)	Laboratory	µg/L

Many laboratory variables were not detected in water samples, or their values were low in one or two samples from the sampling period. It is possible to include such variables in the model. Many variables also essentially convey the same information, such as different types of phosphorus or nitrogen. For modeling purposes, it is therefore sufficient to include only the total amounts. Uncertainty factors: the timing of laboratory tests, but since the turbidity measurement is equal, it should be acceptable.

Calibration: It should be noted that the number of laboratory measurements on which the modeling is based is very limited, so all results should be viewed with caution. If the sampling continues in the future, the model could either be further validated or a new more detailed model fitted.

To get estimates on the potential impurities in the water from the online sensor measurements, we need to:

- First, establish a correlation between the laboratory measurements and the online measured variables
- Utilize this relationship to inversely predict the estimates on the laboratory variables from the online sensor readings

This is an ill-posed inverse problem, where the aim is to predict many variables from one measurement. Thus, the model describing the correlation between the lab and online measurements needs to be robust enough that the small deviations in the predictors do not cause huge fluctuations in the predicted variables.

Set the number of variables n . From calibration, get regression coefficients β , a $1 \times n$ -vector. For each variable, there is a mean value μ and a variance σ^2 , also from the laboratory calibration data, both $1 \times n$ -vectors. This includes turbidity.

Figure 4.1 The sum of squares error between original lab variables and the ones predicted by the model as a function of the ridge parameter. Highlighted the best fitting parameter of 45, according to this metric.

Calibration is done by a ridge regression model, which penalises variables with little effect on the result. The regularization constant was set by inversion of the model to reconstruct the original variables.

Let $y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the response vector, $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ the design matrix, and $\beta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ the coefficients to estimate. Ridge regression solves:

$$\hat{\beta}_\lambda = \arg \min_{\beta} \{ \|y - X\beta\|^2 + \lambda \|\beta\|^2 \}$$

Here, $\lambda \geq 0$ is the regularisation constant (also called the ridge parameter). Its purpose is to penalise large coefficients and reduce sensitivity to correlated inputs or ill-posedness, as in inverse prediction scenarios.

As the model is meant to be utilized inversely, that is, to predict the online water quality variables from the turbidity values. Thus, the ridge parameter was also set in this manner, so for the lab data, first the forward model was set between the turbidity and other variables, then the resulting regression coefficients $\hat{\beta}_\lambda$ for each ridge parameter λ were inverted and utilized to predict back the lab-variables. The sum of squares error between the original variables and the lab variables was used to determine the optimal ridge parameter, this is shown in Figure 1.

The previous approach takes into account only the combined error between all of the variables. To get a more complete understanding of the model performance, we can take a look at the back predictions for each variable. We can see that the model seems to fit quite nicely with all of the variables, and the errors are similar in each.

Application to online measurements: When the sensor gives a reading for the flow parameter (lest mark it v) (flow rate, L/s), run the prediction for the n variable concentrations. Firstly, normalize the online turbidity measurement with the mean and variance of the lab measurements. Then use a pseudoinverse of the regression coefficients to predict the normalized concentrations for online data X^z . The pseudoinverse for a vector can be written as $\beta^\dagger = \beta^t \beta \beta$. Revert the normalization on the predictions to

get \hat{X} , utilizing the lab-measured mean and variance for each variable. Lastly, the concentrations are multiplied by the flow to get the amounts.

The pseudoinverse step can be further simplified if the already inverted regression coefficients are given, $\beta^\dagger \rightarrow \beta_{inv}$. Then the vector multiplication can be calculated in parts for each variable and reduces to a simple scalar multiplication. So $X_{z,i} = \beta_{inv,i} y_z$, then for each variable $i = 1 \dots n$ the calculated value $X_{z,i}$ is scaled back to \hat{X} collected in a Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Calculated value X_z , scaled back to \hat{X} collected

Algorithm 1 Predicting water quality from turbidity

```

1: procedure METHODNAME(input1, input2, ...)
2:   Input: Flow measurement, turbidity measurement,
3:   Output: Predicted concentrations  $\hat{X}$ 
4:   Initialise variables
5:   if  $\nu > \{0, NaN\}$  then
6:     Read turbidity value  $y$  from sensor
7:     normalize turbidity with lab  $y_z = \frac{y - \mu_y}{\sigma_y}$ 
8:     Predict variables from  $y_z$ ,  $X_z = \beta^\dagger y_z$ 
9:     Get  $\hat{X}$  from the normalized  $X_z$ ,  $X_z \sigma_x^2 + \mu_x$ 
10:    Multiply the concentrations with the flow and the duration of one
        measurement point (10min), to get amounts,  $\hat{M} = \hat{X} \nu (10 \cdot 60)$ 
11:    end if
12:    return result
13: end procedure

```

Results: Here are presented some cumulative sums on the different variables given by the model, with the amount of water entering the NBS. Figure 3 is a bar diagram of the cumulative sums for each variable of the model for each full month of measurements. The main thing to notice is, that even though the amount of water flow in the winter is much lower, the predicted amounts for the variables are much higher. As the model was calibrated with the lab samples from summer of 2024, the predictions for those months should be the most reliable. For winter the behavior changes, as rainfall is mostly snow. It might be that the snow stays on the ground for some time and collects "dirt" and with warmer temperatures melts and takes larger load of pollutants with it. But this should be verified with more laboratory sampling. The values presented in the figure have also been collected to Table 4.5.

If the water quality, for example, changes state", then this model cannot detect it. Next steps would then be to include, for example, water temperature and conductivity measurements in the model to see if they give the model more generality and the ability to give more information on the state of the water. For example, during different times of the year.

Figure 4.2 Monthly cumulative sums of substances entering the NBS. Calculated from the model predictions.

Table 4.5 Monthly sums for each of the variables predicted by the model.

Month	Water, m ³	Total N, g	TOC, g	Solids, g	Total P, g	Cu, mg	V, mg	Zn, mg	Sb, mg
8.2024	479	1228	27765	47251	41.83	9017	2316	44296	423.10
9.2024	440	1256	31420	47327	42.78	10404	2520	47060	435.31
10.2024	516	1502	38249	56361	51.14	12706	3047	56664	521.07
11.2024	444	5084	208726	163987	172.44	74015	14279	237548	1827.56
12.2024	411	4540	185506	146750	154.00	65749	12707	211625	1631.37
1.2025	185	2302	95519	73915	78.07	33908	6516	108145	828.35
2.2025	2.73	72.54	3198.39	2265.62	2.46	1142	215	3517	26.26
3.2025	26.82	643	28173	20126	21.78	10056	1894	31061	232.47
4.2025	1.73	12.89	492.24	428.37	0.44	173.20	34.36	581.00	4.60
5.2025	41.37	211	7248.27	7267.12	7.16	2519	522	9034	74.59
6.2025	18.21	57.69	1566.34	2132.06	1.96	526.07	122	2233	20.09
7.2025	18.81	31.56	318.01	1348.59	1.08	76.98	39.73	910.37	10.56
8.2025	86.24	258.16	6718.65	9639.11	8.79	2240	531	9823	89.68

4.1.5 Availability and Access of Monitored Data

Data published on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/transformar_h2020 DOI: [Lappeenranta demonstrator stormwater quality monitoring data Baseline above Koulukatu NBS - September 2024 to September 2025](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1400000)

GDPR-compliant data handling

4.1.6 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

More monitoring data is needed for NBS to demonstrate the effectiveness of the structure. However, based on literature reviews and calculations, it can be assumed that the structure filters impurities from stormwater and prevents them from entering water bodies. The performance of the infiltration structure will be monitored in future projects. The replication of infiltration structures in the city has already begun. In practice, the structures can be implemented in new areas and in existing areas in connection with e.g. street renovations. Urban planning is included in the replication plans, and stormwater management is taken into account in all new local detailed plans by reserving sufficient space for stormwater management in both public and private areas.

The information from CEI research, combined with the citizen application (CAF) and the results of events and workshops aimed at citizens, supports the conclusion that citizens play a significant role in the city's stormwater management. In order to maintain the water quality of water bodies and avoid network flooding, it is important that residents and private actors also implement stormwater management on their properties.

4.2 West Country, United Kingdom

4.2.1 Overview of the Expected Impacts

The West Country demonstrator focuses on addressing agricultural run-off, nutrient pollution, and biodiversity loss through the deployment of and catchment-scale management strategies including nature based solutions (NBS). The expected impacts are multi-dimensional:

- Environmental impacts:
 - Reduction in nutrient loads (nitrogen and phosphorus) entering river systems.
 - Improvement of water quality, contributing to better ecological status under the EU Water Framework Directive.
 - Increased biodiversity through the creation of wetland habitats supporting macroinvertebrates, fish populations, and riparian vegetation.
 - Enhanced flood retention and water storage capacity in the catchment.
- Economic impacts:
 - Reduced treatment costs for drinking water providers through decreased nutrient concentrations.
 - Cost savings for farmers due to nutrient retention and recycling, supporting more efficient fertiliser use.
 - Demonstrated cost-effectiveness of NBS compared to traditional grey infrastructure.
- Social impacts:
 - Improved public health and amenity benefits from cleaner rivers and restored landscapes.

- Strengthened collaboration among farmers, local authorities, and NGOs such as the Rivers Trust.
- Increased acceptance of NBS by landowners, with potential replication across other UK catchments.

4.2.1.1 Achieving Nutrient Neutrality

The primary objective of Nutrient Neutrality is to make the issue of nutrient pollution in designated catchments no worse. The wider environmental objectives in this project were to deliver the best outcomes for nature and the region's rivers, by working strategically to restore river corridors and surrounding catchment function and provide a range of environmental co-benefits. To achieve this, multiple landowners were supported to implement a range of NBS to reduce soil and slurry entering watercourses; to reduce the nutrients introduced to farming systems and re-use nutrients more efficiently. In appropriate locations, NBS can also attenuate surface water flows and increase infiltration across the system. This reduces the volume of surface water entering the combined sewerage system and reduces pollution from overflow spills. These primarily environmental impacts were captured through a range of quantitative and qualitative monitoring metrics and data. Each solution provided a range of primary and secondary impacts, depending on the design and location. The primary focus was to reduce phosphate pollution, particularly where funded as part of a nutrient credit scheme. Co-benefits included:

- "Slowing the flow" reducing localized flooding;
- Improvements in habitat and biodiversity value;
- Carbon capture, depending on the intervention type;
- Wider water quality improvements through capturing sediments and other pollutants;

Together these environmental improvements help to build resilience within catchments.

Economic Development in the Catchment

Through TransformAr new nutrient credit markets are being developed which can provide an additional income for landowners and farmers. In the Camel catchment WRT worked with the local planning authority on the creation of a nutrient credit scheme (Figure 4.3). Here WRT are liaising directly with farmers and landowners and with the local planning authority, who are capitalizing the scheme through CIL (Community Infrastructure Levy) funds. A key element in the formation of credits is to find an investor who is willing to capitalize the credit through upfront investment. This can then be recovered when the credit is sold to the end user.

Figure 4.3 Schematic and flow pathway in the Camel catchment for nutrient credit creation.

Bilateral marketing of nutrients is becoming commonplace and in recent years online platforms have been used to attract and contract with multiple providers such as farmers. This can reduce cost and alleviate market blockers. Some of the existing platforms include those in Somerset, Avon and Solent catchments hosted by ENTRADE;

<https://www.entrade.co.uk/our-markets/>

In the Axe catchment, the nutrient credit model is slightly different as it uses the Natural Capital Marketplace (outlined in Section 4.2.2) as a platform to market nutrient credits, alongside other credits that are available. In the Axe, the route for capitalization is less, however there is potential for this role to be undertaken by the regional water company. A schematic of the current scheme in the Axe catchment is shown in Figure 4.4 below.

Figure 4.4 Flow diagram for the creation of nutrient credits

WRT are working with the North Devon Biosphere Foundation who are developing the nutrient market on NCM.

By facilitating development these credit schemes support a stable local economy, with affordable homes prioritized for local populations.

Tourism is the biggest economic sector in the region and is estimated to support one in five jobs in Cornwall (Local Government Association 2019). The sector is dependent on the beautiful natural environment in the region, including coastal, countryside and moorland scenery. The local economy therefore requires careful stewarding of natural assets, and there is a reputational risk from pollution of both inland and coastal bathing waters.

Raising Climate Awareness and Resilience through Landowner and Community Engagement

WRT has an established history of acting as an ethical and trusted broker for the delivery of payments for ecosystem services. For almost 15 years WRT has worked with the regional water company to act as a broker with landowners and communities (Figure 4.5, though initiatives such as Upstream Thinking. <https://wrt.org.uk/project/upstream-thinking/>).

Figure 4.5 Illustration of the ethical broker role adopted by WRT for ecosystem services

WRT have adopted this ethical broker position regarding Nutrient Neutrality in the Westcountry Region, to ensure that there is strategic delivery of interventions and actions. Without this, developers may pay to follow productive farmland, in unsuitable locations, which will not have the greatest benefit for nutrient reduction for the catchment and may impact on food security. New markets are often unregulated. Therefore, it is important to design the best solutions and offset schemes where possible, to provide a broader range of benefits including climate change adaptation. Through the broker role, WRT will work with investors, regulators, communities and catchment partnerships to develop solutions that provide the greatest benefit overall.

Figure 4.6 below, highlights how an ecosystem services approach can be used as an alternative to the traditional agricultural production model.

Figure 4.6 Payments for Ecosystem Services approach versus traditional private profits

(<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/payments-for-ecosystem-services-pes-best-practice-guide>)

UK DEFRA (Department for Environment, Farming and Rural Affairs) guidance on establishing and setting up PES schemes and the need to understand the current business model and value of verification is shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7 Illustration from UK DEFRA guide to development of PES scheme

WRT has used PES methodology, particularly with water quality issues, to pay or incentivize landowners to change practices or minimize impacts on water quality. Investment from Water companies to fund these improvements is now part of the investment business plan for each funding cycle and has been adopted across much of the UK, with Rivers Trusts often acting as the broker, due to their existing relationships with landowners.

Through WRT’s wider stakeholder involvement there have been examples of community groups opposing new developments in their catchments due to environmental concerns, including opposing the concept of nutrient neutrality outright. Engaging with community groups and developing an active programmed of Citizen Science in the selected catchments enables greater community awareness of the benefits of NBS. This includes the wider co-benefits this approach can achieve above the simplistic land-fallowing often favored by developers. These societal impacts can be evaluated through the public attendance at workshops and monitoring social media posts.

It is expected that many of the benefits and impacts from innovative NBS delivery and novel new nutrient trading schemes will be fully realized after the timescales of the project. WRT will continue to build its longstanding work delivering NBS and seek future funding both to evaluate the legacy of the project and implement the evidence-based outcomes more widely.

4.2.2 Selected Indicators

There are three main areas where a successful nutrient neutrality scheme would have positive impacts. These are: Environmental improvements within the selected sensitive catchments; Economic benefits both to communities from unlocking development and providing alternative income for farmers and land managers; Social benefits of increasing engagement and understanding of rivers and ecosystems, including threats and resilience.

Environmental improvements

Expected impacts:

Should the land use change be sited strategically in areas adjacent to river corridors, there will be the greatest direct benefit to the environment. The aim of the scheme is to reduce nutrients, primarily phosphates, entering rivers and affecting water quality. The WRT interventions rely on increased hydraulic residence time improving nutrient retention in the riparian zone, where vegetation improves in situ denitrification and phosphate removal rates. Water quality is subject to spot sampling across the affected catchments by citizen scientists (CSI) and WRT staff. It may be hard to demonstrate a direct link with interventions at this scale on catchment water quality over this project timespan, but up and downstream sampling of intervention sites has commenced.

There are also co-benefits to habitats and species from this approach which WRT will monitor through habitat surveys (species richness) and drone footage (habitat extent). Riverfly and fisheries surveys will provide information about the quality of in-river habitat. WRT will also monitor ecological function through soil analysis at intervention sites. Samples will be visually assessed for health based on structure, infiltration rates and samples will be sent to a lab for soil organic matter and nutrient content analysis.

Economic Development in the Catchment

Expected impacts:

The initiation of a trading scheme allowing housing development to proceed by mitigating additional sewage through land use offsets will overcome the planning hiatus in the affected catchments. New housing is needed for local people who provide a workforce for sustainable economic growth in a region where holiday homes and tourism are a dominant economic sector. Studies (Lichfields, 2018) show that each £1m investment in housing development supports around 19.9 direct jobs, and 15.6 indirect jobs, as the construction industry has an indirect and induced employment multiplier of 2.23 (Lichfields, 2022).

This impact is more complex to assess but the value of P offsets obtained can be expressed as housing units. The value of capitalization in (£) and value of credits traded can also be used. Also, the number of landowners and investors/developers brought in as part of the scheme. A set of metrics around this can be established as a way of indicating the impact. There will be wider economic benefits including the protection of tourism and recreational value.

Economic benefits to farmers in payments for ecosystem services will be measured in the financial value of BNG and P Credits obtained. WRT are providing support with nutrient budgets on farms, leading to financial savings from more efficient use of fertilizers. In addition, the land use change and interventions on floodplains will help retain nutrient rich sediments which are a valuable resource to farmers but a pollutant in rivers. Depth or volume of sediments captured at intervention sites will be measured, along with the nutrient content via lab analysis.

Landowner and Community Engagement

Expected impacts:

This will focus on increasing wider community awareness and understanding of river systems and threats, promoting the benefits of water use awareness and drought resilience. The success of community engagement activities is monitored and evaluated through quantitative, qualitative and narrative approaches. Metrics include sign-ups to the Westcountry Citizen Science Investigations (CSI) scheme, numbers of active volunteers and retention and numbers of volunteer surveys. Attendance at participatory research events and workshops offered by WRT and the motivations for this participation. Higher-level engagement through community groups working with WRT to develop new citizen science

methodologies and development of co-funding streams to drive environmental outcomes (water quality and resources) which have been identified as important by the community, including landowners and farmers, is also indicative of increased awareness of, and action for, climate resilience.

4.3

4.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

KPI 4: Eutrophication Reduction

TransformAr did not work on eutrophication directly. This KPI is thus not quantified. Refer to KPI 20 (Increase in Nutrients and Water Retained by NBS) for the work in TransformAr on nutrients and water quality. In general, a reduction of nutrient input contributes to reducing the eutrophication of a river catchment. But eutrophication is a more complex phenomenon, which was not addressed in TransformAr.

KPI 20.1: UKHAB Surveys Before & After Intervention to Assess Biodiversity Net Gain, Spatially Resolved in Ha/Habitat Restored

A comparative assessment of habitat changes, based on delivery site and a control area, or previous habitat survey where available, was carried out by ecologists using the following methods:

- UK Habitat Survey – A standardised approach to defining UK terrestrial and freshwater habitats, primarily based on botanical survey.
- Habitat Condition Assessment Survey – Method used in biodiversity net gain assessment for town planning purposes.
- Botanical species diversity and abundance, and presence of notable (protected) species.

The surveys were conducted within a 30m buffer zone of the delivery area/ equivalent control area.

KPI 20.2: Electric Fishing Surveys

Survey sites were selected by experienced fisheries officers to identify reaches that were deemed good fry habitat as close to the interventions as possible. At water temperatures <18°C, electric fishing was carried out using a backpack electric fishing kit to induce fish to swim towards an anode and into a hand net. Voltage settings were adjusted according to the electrical conductivity of the water. All surveys were conducted using a 100% (smooth) duty cycle. Fish recovered in an aerated container of water before processing salmonids (species identification and fork length measurement) and returning to the watercourse. Presence of other caught species, missed fish, and the length and width of the fished reach were recorded. Catch efficiencies <60% voided the survey. Fry index surveys (five-minute semi-quantitative method) were carried out at all sites with the exception of Worthyvale on the Camel where a fully quantitative three catch depletion method was used.

A length frequency histogram deduced thresholds for fry and parr for each survey year. Each FIS site was then classified according to Crozier and Kennedy, 1994 (8). Worthyvale was classified using the National Fisheries Classification Scheme (9).

Table 4.6 Semi-quantitative abundance categories for salmon fry (Crozier & Kennedy, 1994).

Density Classification	Semi-quantitative (n 5min fishing)	Quantitative (n 100m ²)
A (Excellent)	>23	>114.7
B (Good)	11-23	69.1-114.6
C (Fair)	5-10	41.1-69.0
D (Poor)	1-4	0.1-41.0
E (Absent)	0	0

Table 4.7 National Fisheries Classification Scheme

Classification	Density of Fish per 100m ²			
	Salmon fry	Salmon parr	Trout fry	Trout parr
A - Excellent	>86	=>19	=>38	>21
B - Good	45–85.9	10.0-18.9	17.0-37.9	12.0-20.9
C - Fair	23-44.9	5.0-9.9	8.0-16.9	5.0-11.9
D - Moderate	9-22.9	3.0-4.9	3.0-7.9	2.0-4.9
E – Poor	<9	<3.0	<3.0	<2.0
F - Absent	None recorded	None recorded	None recorded	None recorded

KPI 20.3: Historic water quality assessments from existing datasets

Publicly available water quality monitoring data from the UK Environment Agency (EA) were used to deliver against this KPI. The EA’s Water Information Management System (WIMS) database was accessed online via the Water Quality Data Archive portal (<https://environment.data.gov.uk/water-quality/view/landing>) and datasets from 2000 to 2021, (and for subsequent years as the project progressed) were downloaded for analysis in Excel with the *Area* field as “Devon and Cornwall” and *Purpose* field as “Monitoring Only”.

KPI 20.4: Longitudinal Water Quality Monitoring Programme

Monthly Water Quality Spot Monitoring Programme

Monthly spot sampling surveys for water quality were designed to target and priorities areas within the catchment for interventions, further monitoring, farm-advice and/or stakeholder engagement. The process was dynamic and ongoing, in order to capture data to evidence the need for interventions and to aid in landowner engagement.

Sites were selected based on public accessibility (from road bridges) and aimed to divide the catchment into relatively equally sized sub catchments, as well as focus more specifically on interventions or clusters of them. Unfiltered samples were collected monthly using a bucket on a rope and analyzed on-site for color, turbidity, suspended sediment, and total reactive phosphate using a handheld colorimeter (DR900, HACH) using the preset methods available on the device. Measurements for temperature and conductivity were taken using a handheld tester (PocketPro Tester, HACH). Data from 50 monthly longitudinal surveys completed on the Axe and 39 surveys on the Camel

(<https://zenodo.org/records/17058348>) were used to construct catchment scorecards. The 38 sites surveyed on the Axe were split into separate campaigns at the start of the project to cover the main Axe, Corry Brook, Yarty and the Kit Brook, with one or two samples from the Fourton, Blackwater and Synderford tributaries. The 36 sites on the Camel were similarly split up into the main Camel and River Allen. As intervention sites were identified and works agreed, sampling was reduced to focus on these areas.

Data analysis was undertaken to rank each sub catchment (represented as the entire area upstream of a sampling point) within the demonstrator catchment against the others, for each WQ parameter. Sites were ranked from “best” to “worst”, according to the percentage of records at a given site that exceeded the survey median (equal exceedances were then ranked using site means) and individual parameter rankings were averaged to give an overall WQ score. The Watershed tool in ArcGIS was used to delineate subcatchments and visually represent the rankings for each using a graduated color scale. Where appropriate, statistical tests were performed in Excel to identify any significant differences in measured parameters before and after interventions were installed (or upstream/downstream of them).

Citizen Science Data

An active programme of Citizen Science monitoring across the Axe and Camel catchments provided high spatial density but low specification monitoring of WQ parameters including phosphate, turbidity, total dissolved solids and temperature. These data were downloaded for analysis from WRT’s online data repository (Cartographer) and waterbody scorecards were created on an annual basis for each catchment. Citizen science data was ultimately collected as a community and stakeholder engagement tool (KPI 11) enabling WRT to discuss the causes of poor water quality and potential solutions with a much broader audience thereby building catchment and climate resilience. <https://wrt.maps.arcgis.com/apps/instant/attachmentviewer/index.html?appid=d07a6f8382764c0faed87d0652d43df9>.

Visual Assessments of Interventions

Prior to the installation of continuous WQ monitoring sondes, qualitative assessments were made by eye or using timelapse trail cameras (V150, Vosker) to establish interventions (leaky log dams only) were functioning as designed. These assessments identified any unintended:

- erosion, collapse or removal of the dams
- redirection of surface water
- bankside or channel erosion
- failure of the dam to interact with surface water during expected times (e.g. a significant storm event)

Cameras were deployed on suitable trees or posts and images sent remotely to an online platform for viewing or stored on a memory card for manual download. Visual assessments before and after intervention installations were also made using aerial drone imagery (DJI Air 25).

Spot Monitoring of Interventions

The watercourse that runs through Chubbs Farm was monitored using the same spot sampling equipment as outlined for the catchment-wide surveys. The site was monitored monthly at four locations from March 2024 onwards (Figure 4.7). Sites 3 and 4 were selected for upstream and downstream analysis

with Sites 1 and 2 aiding in tracing the source of pollutants. Eight spot monitoring campaigns were conducted before interventions were installed to provide some baseline data for comparison with another eight samples taken post-works.

Figure 4.8 Chubbs Farm spot sampling locations

At Penvose Campsite, twenty WQ samples taken directly upstream and downstream of the log dam cascade were compared in Excel (to identify statistically significant differences in the concentrations of standard WQ parameters (electrical conductivity, total reactive phosphate and turbidity)).

Continuous Water Quality Monitoring

Sondes were deployed in-river to monitor the effectiveness of the leaky log dams in storing water and improving WQ at Penvose (Camel catchment) and Chubbs Farm (Axe catchment). Figure 20 shows the deployment design, which monitors the whole dam cascade rather than monitoring each individual dam. As equipment costs generally prohibit the ability to monitor each dam separately, plus the unique nature of each means the storage capacity and “leakiness” of one dam cannot be accurately extrapolated to another, this method is considered the most appropriate way to capture intervention impacts.

The upstream-most sensor was placed outside the influence of the upstream-most dam. For Chubbs, this was at site 2 in Figure 38 as water depth at site 1 did not allow submersion of sensor head and this tributary was later identified to be more significant with respect to nutrient run-off. The downstream sensor was placed downstream of the cascade. Additional sensors were placed behind dams that were either qualitatively observed to be functioning as designed, to monitor fluctuating water levels and WQ immediately behind the dams, or simply accessible enough for deployment. For Penvose, three

AquaTROLL 200 sondes with VuLink telemetry devices (In-Situ Ltd.) were deployed (Figure 39). The sondes were set to 15-minute measurement intervals for electrical conductivity (as a proxy for dissolved pollution), depth and temperature. At Chubbs Farm, a continuous phosphate monitor (DropletSens™ Phosphate Probe, SouthWestSensors) with a Point Green Telemetry Unit (Metasphere) was also installed downstream of the interventions, alongside the AquaTROLL 200. The deployment of the SWS probe took place after the interventions were installed and only at the downstream site, so the exercise was more to assess the suitability of the use of the probe in such an environment for future monitoring of this kind, and to generate some data for comparison alongside the more standard WQ parameter electrical conductivity as a proxy for pollution.

Figure 4.9 Set-up for monitoring a cascade of leaky log dams.

Figure 4.10 An example of the installation of conductivity, temperature and depth loggers installed for monitoring upstream (A) and downstream (B) of the leaky log dam cascade at Penvose campsite.

KPI 20.5 Modelling kgs of Phosphate Removed as a Proxy for Water Quality

As quantitative assessment of the efficiency and impact of the NBS interventions would require pre and post intervention sampling far beyond the length of the TransformAR project, WRT used two models to approximate the improvements in water quality as a result of their implementation, using data from KPI 20.6 and 20.7 below. The River Camel SAC Nutrient Budget Calculator was used for the Camel and River Axe SAC Nutrient Budget Calculator for the Axe. Both calculators are online tools developed by the Devon and Cornwall authorities for the benefit of housing developers. They show the nutrient impact of proposed developments, and the nutrient mitigation required to achieve neutrality. Both tools are based on the algorithms developed as part of the Farmscoper Tool, which Natural England uses to assess nutrient credit schemes. As amelioration of nutrient pollution across the entire catchment is the aim, general targets for phosphate reduction in the Camel and Axe catchments were used instead of those for individual housing developments within the tool.

KPI 20.6 Measure the Depth/Volume of Sediment Captured by the Intervention

On the 4th and 5th of March 2025, interventions designed to settle out and entrap sediments (e.g. ponds, scrapes) were measured using a tape measure to derive a maximum storage volume for each intervention. These were summed and used within the Farmscoper Tool to approximate the maximum amount of sediment removed from surface run-off and thus prevented from entering the watercourse.

KPI 20.7 Measure the nutrient content of the sediments via laboratory analysis

Interventions available for sediment sampling included all five scrapes at Snowdon Farm and the sediment trap, plus one of the scrapes at Trethick (the remaining scrapes being either too wet or having no sediment trapped within them). No sediment was collected from Penvose or Chubbs Farm due to unsuitable sampling conditions.

A transect of 10 sediment samples were collected from each intervention on the 4th and 5th of March 2025 using a trowel and homogenized into a single sample. Homogenised samples were immediately dispatched to the laboratory (NRM Cawood) in laboratory-issued grip seal bags and analysed for soil pH, phosphorus (P), potassium (K) and magnesium (Mg) index, available concentrations of P, K and Mg and soil organic matter (loss on ignition method). As sampling was restricted to just one occasion at each site, samples were taken and measured at intervals post intervention installation (Snowdon Farm 108 days; Trethick Farm 245 days and Chubbs Farm 104 days). None of the interventions were at full capacity at the time of sampling and those at Snowdon Farm had not been fully connected to the ephemeral stream, meaning measurements were not fully representative of the features in full operation.

KPI 20.8 Measure Soil Permeability/Compaction/Infiltration Rate Using VESS Assessment

Visual Evaluation of Soil Structure (VESS) assessments were undertaken before and after intervention installations, using the method developed by SRUC (Scotland's Rural College, available [here](#)). The method assesses the extent of compaction and thus provides an indication of the degree to which water and nutrients can move within the soil profile. Soil pits were dug by hand using a spade in such a way as to leave one face undisturbed. A subsection of soil was removed from the undisturbed face for visual examination (see Figure 1) in order to establish:

- The presence of any distinct layers throughout the profile
- The size and degree of consolidation of soil aggregates (lumps)

- Whether soil aggregates are angular or rounded in nature
- The degree of porosity
- Whether there are horizontal unnatural clods

Distinct layers of soil were scored 1-5 against the VESS matrix with 1 being friable and good crumb structure, and 5 being very compact with large aggregates that are difficult to break. After surveying, the scores were entered into a spreadsheet to determine an average score for the soil structure in each pit.

At Snowdon Hill Farm, assessments were made within the field, after the in-field elements of the intervention had been installed and within an adjacent field as a control. At Trethick Farm, only the field encompassing the interventions was surveyed.

KPI 20.9 Measuring the Amount of Organic Matter in the Soil and the Carbon:Nitrogen Ratio to Assess Soil Carbon Sequestration Performance

Soil nutrient analysis is used to gauge the availability of nutrients to crops for plant growth. DEFRA use the RB209 Handbook as its standard method for controlling nutrient application rates (from fertiliser and manure) to the needs to the growing plant. This allows farmers and land managers to distribute their sources to match the areas that require the inputs. Historically, nutrients have been over applied and built-up legacy concentrations in the soil and water courses. The classification of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) for different soil types is shown in Table 4.8.

At Snowdon Hill Farm assessments were made within the field, after the infield elements of the intervention had been installed and within an adjacent field, the latter acting as a control.

At Trethick Farm, only the field with the interventions in it was surveyed.

High concentrations of P in the soil do make it more vulnerable to losses, as the P indices increase, P can transition into soluble form and leave the field through field drainage. P can also be transferred to waterbodies with sediment run-off. Large areas of ground have been left with legacy P, from historic land use choices. Inadequate crop nutrition planning previously left fields with more P being added through manures and fertilisers than the crop required.

Table 4.8 Soil Organic Matter (SOM) - percentage of sample. Interpretation based on ADHB-BBRO Soil Biology & Soil Health Partnership protocol and benchmarking

Land use	Rainfall	Soil type	Very Low	Low	Target	High
Arable	Low <650mm	Light	<=1.0	1.1-2.1	2.2-3.2	>=3.3
		Medium	<=1.7	1.8-3.3	3.4-5.0	>=5.1
		Heavy	<=2.2	2.3-4.4	4.5-6.5	>=6.6
	Moderate 650-800mm	Light	<=1.0	1.1-3.0	3.1-4.5	>=4.6
		Medium	<=1.9	2.0-4.0	4.1-6.0	>=6.1
		Heavy	<= 2.7	2.8-5.2	5.3-7.6	>=7.7
		Light	<=1.3	1.4-3.7	3.8-6.1	>=6.2

	High 800-1100mm	Medium	<=2.5	2.6-5.0	5.1-7.5	>=7.6
		Heavy	<=3.6	3.7-6.2	6.3-8.8	>=8.9
Grassland (Lowland)	All	Light	<=2.1	2.2-4.9	5.0-7.9	8.0-14.9
		Medium	<=3.4	3.5-6.4	6.5-9.3	9.3-19.9
		Heavy	<=4.6	4.7-7.6	7.7-10.5	10.6-19.9

4.4.1 Availability and Access of Monitored Data

Baseline water quality and ecological monitoring data for KPI 20: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500788>

Final water quality and ecological monitoring data for KPI 20: <https://zenodo.org/records/17058348>

Environment Agency Water Quality Archive (WIMS): <https://environment.data.gov.uk/water-quality/view/landing>

Complete Citizen Science scorecards: <https://wrt.maps.arcgis.com/apps/instant/attachmentviewer/index.html?appid=d07a6f8382764c0faed87d0652d43df9>

4.4.2 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

For findings on bankability and potential to upscale and accelerate see section 6.2.2 bankability.

Nutrient Credit Schemes in Devon and Cornwall

In the Westcountry region, although several natural capital marketplaces have emerged to facilitate the trade of ecosystem services, an online marketplace explicitly designed to support the trade of nutrient credits is not currently available. Instead, local authorities have worked with NGO's such as the Westcountry Rivers Trust and the Devon Wildlife Trust to engage landowners in credit development projects. In the Camel and Axe catchments, WRT worked to find strategic opportunities for the development of NBS that would both mitigate nutrient pollution and support climate change adaptation by slowing flows and re-naturalizing waterways. As WRT have a strong track-record of landowner engagement, we operate as a 'broker' between credit purchasers and suppliers, ensuring excellent environmental outcomes.

Blended Finance: Camel Catchment

This blended finance model in the Camel has several key advantages but also presents several key challenges when assessing the bankability or financial sustainability of climate adaptation.

Benefits:

- Use of public funding to develop credit projects accelerates outcomes, as risk to private developers is removed.

- Resultant ecosystem services do not need to represent high revenue/rate of return, as local authorities do not need to generate profit.
- Planning authorities within local governments are well-placed to sell resultant credits to developers, as they have a pre-established professional relationship
- Prevents stagnation at the ‘seed funding’ or project development phase, often encountered when attempting to attract private investment for nature-based solutions.

Challenges:

- Lack of consistent value/unit of phosphate makes valuation of NBS difficult, delaying uptake. Landowners need a consistent value to make informed decisions against other land use options.
- Lack of clarity around future liability for ecosystem service assets, as well as potential litigation risks associated with delivery failure. Results in delay and uncertainty for landowners.
- Focus on nutrient credits in order to meet statutory demand results in failure to capitalize potential additional revenue streams associated with the NBS created. Does not help to facilitate future private-sector investment.

A further appraisal of the benefits and challenges to blended finance will be included in the discussion of the bankability interview process.

Private Finance: Axe Catchment

The local authority in the Axe catchment did not capitalize nature-based solutions yet. However, the local authority has decided to invest, meaning more action should emerge on this issue in future. In the bankability interview process, other financing instruments than the blended structure tested in the Camal Catchment will be explored.

4.3 Galicia, Spain

4.3.1 Overview of the Expected Impacts

The objective of the Galician demonstrator is to drive a region-specific adaptive transformational adaptation process for the clam and mussel sectors, responding to the prevailing multi-sectoral climate risks. This has been assessed mainly with indicators informing on the performance of the solutions and the participation, perception, awareness, involvement, and interest of key sectoral stakeholders.

The overall impact has been the empowerment of the sector with real-time data and predictive capabilities, improving operational efficiency and supporting sustainable and adaptive management practices to face the environmental changing conditions due CC.

The solutions developed, are understood as a trial to study the feasibility of the digitalization of the sectors for a better adaptation to CC. Thus, the effectiveness of these tools was gauged by the extent to which they are embraced and how satisfied users, including producers and scientists, are with them.

Table 4.9 Expected impacts of the solutions.

Expected impacts	RI	INTERM	MRM
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Knowledge increase and transfer about regional oceanographic environment	X	X	X
Availability of technically viable and effective digital-technological tools to address territorial vulnerabilities linked to CC.		X	X
Availability of decision-making support tools to define actions and a roadmap for enhancing resilience.	X		
Awareness rising and better perception of CC risks affecting the sector	X	X	X
Social acceptance and interest in replicating the solutions or any of the components developed	X	X	X
Governance and management measures	X	X	X

4.3.2 Selected Indicators KPI Summary

The innovation of these solutions lies in the development and application of digital and technological solutions to be provided to the shellfish aquaculture and harvesting sector in Galicia. These solutions aim to provide real-time data, improve understanding of environmental responses, and enhance the efficiency and resilience of these industries to better adapt to climate change.

It was expected that the users will find the monitoring of their production activities more manageable and adaptable to the changing environmental conditions. This, in turn, may enable them to better plan their work and have a positive impact on their working conditions and safety.

Furthermore, the aim of the demonstrator is that the insights derived from these tools facilitate STH and policymakers to identify strategic focal points for adapting to CC effects and make well-informed decisions to enhance the operational resilience of Galician mussel and clam aquaculture.

Table 4.10 Indicators to measure the expected impacts, linked to the baseline, the expected outcomes, the current situation, and the monitoring approach.

Expected impact	Indicators	Solution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
Knowledge increase and transfer	Generation and dissemination of new outputs of knowledge related to CC management.	RI	Data publication records/report, web/visor views (Google analytics records),	0	2 outputs identified and distributed among STK: - 70 climate risk scenarios for the mussel aquaculture - 20 resilience factors, useful for facing the effects of climate change on mussel aquaculture	2

Expected impact	Indicators	Resolution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
	Corroboration in local conditions of the correlations described in the literature about environmental impact on the raft (e.g. biomass losses related to 1) persistent temperature changes 2) mussels detachment from the ropes 3) mussels spawning, etc.	MR M	survey of STK using data. Log of communication and transfer events, report of transfer workshops, minutes of meetings with 5 helix and bilateral meetings, posters or publications	0	3 new correlations described (2 showed correlation and 1 not sure yet)	At least 3 new correlations will be described
	Accessible and real time environmental data linking the mussel raft's movement with production information (recorded at high frequency)	MR M		0	Producers have the link to the visor and access to the digital dashboard: at least 1 entry each 15 days https://utmar.cetmar.org/transformar	Access to the digital dashboard: 1 entry each 15 days
	Number of STH or institutions using data	INTE RM MR M		N/A	Data have been just obtained and uploaded on ZENODO. By the moment the producers, and the involved partners and administration are using them.	90% of engaged STK (124 people and close to 56 organizations)
	Km ² emerged topography (by foot)	INTE RM		0	0.36 Km ²	
	Km ² submerged bathymetry	INTE RM		0	17.6 km ²	7 km ²
	Sediment Samples per Sandbank (by foot)	INTE RM		4-5 sandbank/year	12-29 samples/ sandbank/ season (2025)	
	Current flow/ turbidity survey	INTE RM		0	1 per sandbank (2 in O Sarrido)	1
	Nº Sandbanks with sediment dynamics experiments	INTE RM		0	Not done yet	1 per sandbank
	N of publications / new outputs of knowledge related to CC adaptation in the	All		0	8 2 scientific papers (CETMAR) + 3 posters and	4

Expected impact	Indicators	Solution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
	shellfish sector				1 oral presentation (UVIGO) + 3 technical reports in Zenodo (1 for each solution) 1 scientific paper in prep (INTERM) 1 Methodological handbook in prep (INTERM)	
	N of transfer events / meetings	All		0	14: 4 (GEOMA), 6 (REDE), 4 (CETMAR)	6
Technically viable and effective digital-tech. tools	Sandbanks completely monitored (1 year)	INTERM	Measurements (comparison before and after)	0	4	3
	Increase in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale in the mussel sector (digitalisation and automation)	MRM	Report/video of the solution	TRL4 Validated under laboratory-scientific conditions	TRL6 achieved and TR7 as well	TRL6 Demonstrated in relevant env. (beginning TRL7 System prototype demonstration in operational env.)
	Availability of improved technically viable and effective digital-technological tools	INTERM MRM	Reports, videos and links to the dashboard	0	2 new Solutions: INTERM and MRM (2 new technical reports)	2 new solutions
Awareness rising and better perception of CC	Perception improvement about the need of a decision-making assistance tool for CC adaptation	RI	Reports of the workshops, testimonies, key informants and surveys	N/A	94% participants in the stakeholders' WS on the RI intend to incorporate the findings of the resilience index into their future decision-making processes regarding	Positive answer to the survey

Expected impact	Indicators	Solution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
			pre- and post-implementation		climate change adaptation	
	Increase in the awareness about the risk affecting shellfish culture and the availability of adaptation measures	All		Qualitative (less awareness)	72% of the participants in the stakeholders' WS on the RI reported an increase in their awareness on climate change effects after learning about the RI results. More than 11 events with positive answers	80% of the STK engaged
Social acceptance and interest in replication	Expensive commercial sensors replacement with COTS	MRM	Report, STK survey	0	2 sensors replaced with COTS: Load cells and Air pressure - Temperature string: Fail --> Low Cost not functional.	At least 2 sensors replaced
	Interest in replicating the solution or any of the components developed	MRM	Expressions of interest for replication or install sensors (Emails, official request forms, meeting minutes)	0	3 (One from the administration, 1 from a Company, and one from a producer)	3
	Participatory engagement	All	Workshops Reports, participation lists of the different project activities (meetings, workshops, etc.)	N/A	132 (from 60 organisations) 29 Fishers and shellfishers 23 Policy makers 23 Scientific orgs. 19 socio-env. orgs. 19 sectoral orgs.	80 actors 20 Fishers shellfishers 20 Policy makers
	Change in the long-term behavioural trends of STH in decision and policy making	RI		N/A	20 key stakeholders have work collaboratively to identify proposals to improve the mussel aquaculture adaptation	Positive answer to the survey

Expected impact	Indicators	Resolution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
					performance based on RI results.	
	Interest and content with the provided data	INTERM	Entries in the dashboard, satisfaction surveys	N/A	-Producers interested in the data (MRM) -100% of biologist have interest in the data (INTERM) -Utility model application requested and approved.	80% of the Fishers shelfishers
Governance and mgmt. measures	Number of mussel aquaculture STH participating in decision-making processes for increasing the resilience and adaptation to climate change in the mussel sector	RI	Participation records during consultation processes in the RI development, stakeholder feedback	0	- 23 agents participated in three consultations (2 Delphis and 1 about adaptation performance of the mussel sector) - 10 experts in the validation of technical data (climatic variables and projections, processes, and resilience factors)	40 agents
	Number of innovation helixes represented. (According to the quintuple innovation helix framework)	RI	Participation records during consultation processes in the RI development	0	5 helix	5 helix
	Actions and a roadmap defined for enhancing resilience in the mussel aquaculture sector	RI	Report	No data available for this sector	-24 proposed initiatives were prioritized -17 out of the 24 were selected as the most important and urgent, resulting in a tentative roadmap. -5 out of 17 were considered high priority	1 roadmap 15 collaborative initiatives
	Creation of a resilience assessment of the mussel sector	RI	Performance rating of the mussel sector in certain critical areas.	0	The resilience index has been developed and calculated for the mussel aquaculture adaptation capacity in Galicia, providing scores for 5 adaptation dimensions:	RI

Expected impact	Indicators	olution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
					Governance, R&D&I, Risk management, Collaboration and Operational environment	
	Consensus pathways and validated solutions for mussel and clam sector	All	Report	0	Pathways including at least 17 validated proposals/ adaptation solutions	
	Set of recommendations and measures including an appealing document	All	Report	0	Report of the WS and the action plan (1 pathway)	1 set

4.4.3 Baseline Data

Previous projects and scientific papers have been taken into account to build upon their results and design the solutions that are being tested in TransformAr.

The most important to highlight are:

- MarRisk regional project, where a resilience index for coastal infrastructures was developed. While it offers some clues and orientations about coastal risks in a CC scenario, the project did not focus on shellfish culture.
- León-Mateos et al. (2021), publication in the Marine Policy journal that entails the RI first application in the A Coruña Port, Galicia (Spain), as was explained in section 3.2.1. The RI has never been applied to the mussel sector in Galicia.
- Climefish European project: provided guidelines for how to make climate-enabled management plans to prepare and adapt to climate change while minimizing economic losses and social consequences. Shellfish culture was considered and some of the conclusions lead to the digital-technological approach of the solutions that are being developed in TransformAr. None of them has been tried before in real active culture areas.
- Galician Coastal Observatory environmental and oceanographic data services

León-Mateos, F., Sartal, A., López-Manuel, L., & Quintás, M. A. (2021). Adapting our sea ports to the challenges of climate change: Development and validation of a Port Resilience Index. *Marine Policy*, 130, 104573. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0308597X21001846>

For the INTERM, the sedimentological understanding baseline for the sandbanks studied is scarce. No high resolution topography existed for sandbanks harvested by foot. However, and thanks to the meetings organised through the course of the project, we have found previous datasets of intertidal bathymetry surveyed by governmental research institutions of the region that might serve as a baseline for the context of the area bathymetry and can be included in morphodynamic models' grids.

Sediment composition for the selected sandbanks was barely analysed before the start of this project. No studies included or monitored sediment composition at this scale. Only shellfishers guilds provided few samples, not publicly available, per location and year, but with no consistent sampling strategy.

The understanding of the hydrodynamics affecting the selected sandbanks is attained here with direct and temporal measurements of turbidity and current flow direction and magnitude. It is done at specific locations where no baseline data was found after reviewing literature and meeting exchanges. However, there are border scale stations ruled by public organisations in the area, that provide continuous valuable data of sea level, currents, temperature, pressure, etc. (<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/home>; <https://www.puertos.es/en-us>)

Morphodynamic simulations are not published for the studied region. There are, however, applications of a similar model set up for the broader scale of the Galician coast aiming to provide insights in the temperature and salinity modifications of the coastal bivalve ecosystems (Des et al., 2021, Des et al., 2020).

For the MRM, there were no previous oceanographic and production data in real time collected directly from an active mussel raft. This had never been attempted before on a structure owned by producers without interfering with their daily activities. Within the framework of the TRANSFORMAR project, the first IoT-based prototype solution was developed and successfully deployed, allowing continuous monitoring from May 2023 until the end of 2024, when the Galician Demo officially concluded. The usefulness of these data for the mussel farming sector has already been demonstrated, as the local administration decided at the end of 2024 to finance the evolution of this prototype. The new and more robust version was installed in May 2025, ensuring the continuity of monitoring activities beyond the duration of TRANSFORMAR and making the data openly available to the entire mussel farming community. The time series obtained are currently under processing and analysis, and will be compared with reference datasets from scientific and administrative centres to better understand the local effects of environmental variability on mussel production.

It's relevant to mention for this demonstrator the bilateral meetings and workshops held in the initial two years of the project. These sessions gathered information on STH ' perceptions and interests regarding CC and adaptation measures. Additionally, each solution has maintained continuous contact with producers, engaging them in identifying needs, installing sensors, making enhancements, and providing consultations to assess the sector's resilience

4.4.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

Prior to obtaining impact results, it is imperative to first gather data on the implementation of the solutions, such as identifying suitable data collection areas, securing producer agreements, installing sensors, ensuring sensor functionality, and the type of information obtained.

Then, the expected impacts of the solutions were measured through the impact indicators as described in Table 12. In this table, several columns have also been added to clearly display the baseline, the expected outcomes at the end of the project, the current situation, and the approach to monitoring indicators per impact (the type and format of verification sources).

The impact of these solutions was closely monitored in accordance with project guidelines and, where feasible, aligned with other demonstrators. Overall, the increase in knowledge impact through the course of the project was measured by comparison between the obtained measurements from monitoring surveys and sensors and baseline existing data. It was assessed mostly based on user satisfaction (producers and scientists), technical and economic viability, awareness and behavioral change, and the potential for replication. The monitoring of these indicators was approached through workshops, meetings, testimonies of key informants, surveys and questionnaires. Reports of the involvement of the STH and communication and transfer activities serve as verification sources, together with information

about the data publication records and web/visor visualizations.

More specific explanation of the approach to monitor impacts methodologies by solution is detailed below:

Resilience Index (RI)

The REDE research group at the University of Vigo undertook the development of a mathematical model, the Operational Resilience Index (RI), for the mussel farming sector aimed at nudging stakeholders' behavioural change. This index (framed within the project's governance solutions) provides stakeholders (STK) and policymakers with a comprehensive assessment tool and a decision-making assistance instrument that allow them, on one hand, to identify strategic focal points for adapting the mussel farming production operations to the effects caused by CC and, on the other, to establish which measures can have the greatest impact on reducing the risk of business interruption.

As illustrated in Figure 4.11, the development of the Operational RI employs a hybrid methodology that integrates climate data and scenarios with input from experts and STH. This process unfolds across three different phases:

1) Identification of relevant experts and STH, followed by the collection of three sets of variables to be used throughout the index construction: (i) data about the aquaculture processes, (ii) climatic variables that could affect those processes and their projections and (iii) the available resilience factors with the potential to moderate the impact of the selected climate elements on critical processes.

2) During the second phase, the Delphi methodology was employed to engage experts and STH in a participatory and consensus-building process. As a result, vulnerabilities, risks and resilience factors within mussel aquaculture production have been prioritized. The participants in both Delphies possess expertise related to mussel aquaculture, climate change, and/or resilience. Furthermore, the quintuple helix (Carayannis et al., 2012) has been represented in the expert panels, encompassing Administration, Academia, Productive sector, Environmental organizations and Society. A total of 23 experts took part in the first Delphi (July 2023), while 20 experts participated in the second one (October 2023). The outcomes facilitated the identification of priority risk scenarios and resilience gaps, respectively.

As a final step of the second phase, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to STH to assess the key resilience factors, that is, the adaptive capacities of the sector.

3) The final phase encompassed the definition of the mathematical model (fed with the variables identified in phase 2 and the values from the capacities questionnaire) and the calculation of RI scores. Finally, the definition of proposals for improving adaptation was discussed with STH in order to define a strategic roadmap.

Figure 4.11 Methodological design for the Operational Resilience Index

The RI represents a tool for evaluating the level of adaptability in the operations of the mussel production process. Figure 4.11 shows the final result after calculation of the synthetic index of the resilience factor.

We chose to design a composite index with indicators (synthetic index) because such a tool simplifies communication, turning complex information into understandable metrics, more accessible to a wider audience. Therefore, the RI evaluation will encompass an overall score and a detailed breakdown across five dimensions: Governance, R+D+I, Collaboration, Risk Management, and Operational Environment. Additionally, each dimension is further dissected into four factors, totaling 20 resilience factors.

The dashboard of final scores combines multiple dimensions and factors into a single global metric. It takes into account multiple factors providing a more nuanced understanding of the overall state of the sector. It considers the interaction between the impact level of different risk scenarios and the ability of the identified resilience factors to adapt to their effects. In addition, the index assigns different weights to resilience factors based on the relative importance that experts attribute to each risk scenario. This weighting allows a more nuanced and realistic reflection of the importance of each element in influencing the overall index.

The results emerging from the index provide specific insights that will allow the formulation of actions and a roadmap for enhancing resilience.

Figure 4.12 Presentation of the results of the synthetic Resilience Index

Intertidal Monitoring – INTERM

The GEOMA Research group from the University of Vigo implements a sedimentological monitoring of sandbanks at specific locations of clam exploitation with the aim to improve the knowledge of the sediment dynamics, the stability of the ecosystem substratum, and its response to the predicted Climate Change outcome. An updated understanding will improve STH and policymaker's basis for adequate adaptation solutions, efficient management currently hindered by the lack of information.

This solution directly responds to two aspects in the nature of the sandbanks substrate understanding:

1. The sedimentological context of the Galician intertidal sandbanks, specifically sediments quality on seasonal and year-to-year time scales, and the potential relationship with changes in shellfish productivity.
2. Consequences of the Climate Change on the Galician sandbanks terrain. Although we know that environmental variations alter the morphology and composition of the intertidal sediments (e.g. Friederichs 2011) potentially altering the ecosystem, few studies have undertaken this issue at the regional level.

Within this context, selection of study-case locations was performed after discussion with local shellfishers and scientific community involved, trying to respond to the observed variable historical productivity of commercial clams and arising sedimentological concerns. To fit our evaluation in the time frame of the project, the "space for time" hypothesis has been assumed, selecting three areas on the south margin of the Ría de Arousa, with different geological configuration and levels of shellfish productivity.

The INTERM solution has a threefold mission:

1. **Intertidal Monitoring:** Based on previous and ongoing STH efforts currently used for sediment management strategies, a systematic monitoring has been carried out to obtain seasonally updated datasets along the duration of the project. Starting in month 13 (October 2022), sediment properties (grain size distribution, organic matter content, geochemical composition, etc.), terrain elevation datasets and oceanographic parameters influencing the area dynamics are being surveyed.

2. **Morphodynamic Modelling:** A model set up was configured and validated on the DELFT3D package (Deltares, The Netherlands) for a regional level domain where the tide is the main hydrodynamic factor. Sediment transport under different bathymetric conditions, tidal currents, and river discharge variations are evaluated using the modules FLOW and MOR. An orthogonal grid is established and refined towards the selected intertidal sandbanks, incorporating external datasets for deep bathymetry, but obtained higher resolution depth and sediment composition for the selected shallow sandbanks. Simulations depend on the boundary conditions defined for tide, river and water surface. The model set-up was validated, contrasting the results with ongoing monitored and public stations data, to allow the exploration of regional CC scenarios with variable hydrodynamic conditions. We expect to describe whether the selected sandbanks loose or gain sediment, as well as their sediment texture variations, that might avoid some species growth.

3. **Knowledge transfer:** The compiled information, including the generated datasets and predicted scenarios, was analyzed and processed to finally return to the clam sector in a way that will contribute to improve the sandbank monitoring guidelines, and to be the basis to co-create and purpose management strategies of harvested sandbanks against the CC. The planning, methodology and lessons learnt of the process are available to guide similar processes in equivalent areas.

Figure 4.13 INTERM strategy scheme.

Mussel Raft Monitoring - MRM

The Technological Centre of the Sea – CETMAR, is carrying out the development of a pilot case of digitalization of mussel aquaculture. The conditions of the marine environment and the production are being monitored in active mussels’ farms, for the improvement of the exploitations management, with the support and collaboration of its owners.

The first comprehensive monitoring of a mussel raft in the Galician Rías was conducted at the physical variables level in the framework of the ESSMA project (Ecological Sustainability of Suspended Mussel

Aquaculture), funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Aguiar et al., 2015). This study suggested that it was necessary to revision of the ecological concepts, such as food depletion and/or reduction in water flow, based on idealized linear flows through the rafts. This included the consideration of the "clearance" area, defined as the area affected by non-linear effects produced by the raft itself and its surrounding rafts. These conclusions were supported by the results obtained through a no real-time monitoring of a raft, during more than a year and a half, in the Lorbé polygon of the Ría de Ares and Betanzos (NW Galicia, Spain). The digitalization in this case involved the installation of four current meters and four turbidimeters/fluorometers placed on each side of the raft that recorded data in a self-contained way. The autonomy of this raft was limited by energy requirements because most of the equipment had batteries not powered by solar panels. This intricates recurrent battery changes and, consequently, numerous visits to the raft.

In this case, the solution developed in TransformAr includes the monitoring of environmental, and production parameters (currently in two mussel-rafts), based on the implementation of IoT solutions powered by solar energy sending data in real time. Besides, the remote visualisation of the data on an internet-based platform is also being developed, presenting the information for production management.

A key aspect is the reception and feedback from workers in the sector, paying attention to their opinions and suggestions for improvement or adaptation of the installation to their interests.

Figure 4.14 explains the logic and the sequence of the data gathered from the moment that the sensor captures them to the visualization on the dashboard.

Figure 4.14 MRM flowchart

Next, it is shown the degree of execution of this solution in three phases as well as the time frame:

- The first phase consists of a system that monitors the basic parameters and can validate the installation and the developments created expressly for its use on rafts. For this purpose, an IN-SITU data storage installation was designed and installed in a raft to be tested for a few months and make the necessary modifications to improve its robustness.

At the same time, a first analysis of the data was carried out in order to optimize criteria in terms of storage capacity and frequency of data acquisition.

With all the lessons learned from the first phase, a new design of the installation architecture was made to adapt it to a real-time data collection system.

- The second phase develops the communication protocols and the improvements to be able to perform data acquisition autonomously and send the measurements to ground stations for further analysis. In addition to the oceanographic monitoring sensors, other meteorological sensors were added to complement and improve the sampling capability of the system installed in two mussel rafts.

Data analysis procedures are being improved as well as the characteristics of the important amount of data received in real time.

The designed installation is feasible for the available infrastructure and resistant to the adverse conditions of the marine environment and has a high degree of autonomy, both in terms of energy and in the measurement and telematic transmission of monitored data, as well as having systems for detecting possible failures.

- The third phase, implemented in 2024, improved the data analysis systems and the necessary implementations to visualise the data in a user-friendly web platform. This dashboard shows real time data, as well as all the data history of the variables that are being collected (<https://utmar.cetmar.org/transformar>). Data access and the visualization are affordable for STH and useful in decision-making for more effective and sustainable management of resources.

To assess the feasibility of digitalization in the sector, the technical aspect is analyzed, as well as the impact of the implemented solutions, facilitating and promoting their replication and scalability by the sector. Mussel producers have highlighted the relevance of monitoring two specific parameters that directly influence farming practices and decision-making. On the one hand, seawater temperature is a key environmental variable, as high temperatures or abrupt variations may trigger detachment events of mussels from the ropes, leading to significant production losses. On the other hand, the continuous measurements provided by load cells enable the quantification of rope weights, which constitute a robust proxy for assessing the progressive growth and biomass accumulation of mussels. Together, these datasets offer valuable insights into the relationship between environmental variability and aquaculture performance, reinforcing the importance of real-time monitoring systems as a decision-support tool for the sector. By incorporating IoT technology into mussel raft monitoring, the shellfish industry can adapt to and mitigate the challenges presented by a changing climate while maintaining sustainable and profitable operations.

This effort contributes to the achievement of several objectives defined at National and Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plans. Specifically, it is aligned with the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019-2023) for the development and implementation of the Galician Strategy for Climate Change and Energy 2050 in the lines of action: 11 - Consolidate an observation network as an instrument to improve monitoring, 14 - Promote the conservation and efficient use of natural resources, and 18 - Consolidate sustainable management of fishing and aquaculture that minimizes the impacts of CC and guarantees the current positioning of the sector in the long term.

4.4.5 Availability and Access of Monitored Data

Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/transformar_h2020

This section describes how data are stored for each solution, whom have access to it, and how can be used.

For the RI

The findings from the RI are directly communicated to the involved STH and shared at scientific conferences or through scientific communications.

ZENODO

- *Methodology for the development of a climate change resilience index for mussel aquaculture in Galicia (Spain)* – <https://zenodo.org/records/11671754>

For the INTERM

- **Geological** and **oceanographic** parameters (topography and bathymetry, sediment composition, turbidity, current magnitude and direction) that monitor the sandbank characteristics and morphology at selected locations.

This monitored data are stored internally, accessed by the GEOMA TransformAr team. It is used for model configuration validation, presentation of results in conferences, and if asked during the knowledge transfer meetings, shared with scientific assistants of involved shellfish guilds. It is also available for TransformAr partners. If scientific publications result from the analysis, data involved will be submitted to open access platforms.

ZENODO

- Sediment grain size dataset of intertidal shellfish sandbanks within Ría de Arousa, Spain
<https://zenodo.org/records/13149711>
- XRD analysis dataset of intertidal shellfish sandbanks sediment samples within Ría de Arousa, Spain
<https://zenodo.org/records/13149751>
- Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM) in Ría de Arousa (Galicia). Briefing on the development process of the solution and results
<https://zenodo.org/records/13238528>
- Elemental composition of intertidal shellfish sandbanks sediment samples within Ría de Arousa, Spain
<https://zenodo.org/records/13149806>
- Bathymetry dataset of intertidal shellfish sandbanks within Ría de Arousa, Spain
<https://zenodo.org/records/13149646>
- DGPS Topography dataset of intertidal shellfish sandbanks in Ría de Arousa, Galicia, Spain
<https://zenodo.org/records/13149687>

For the MRM

- **The environmental conditions.** The monitored parameters are *position, raft movement, mussel wire weight, water agitation, rain, wind, air temperature, water Temperature (6 depth levels), salinity, air sound, turbidity and intrusion system*. All these parameters are being measured/recorded at a high frequency. However, for the first tests, commercial precision instrumentation has been used to validate the COTS (Commercial off-the-shelf) components. The final monitoring solution must not include the acquisition of expensive oceanographic equipment such as traditional CTD or Wave buoys. Instead of that, the solution will focus on the deployment solution based on the integration of COTS
- **Production and management parameters:** maintenance operations control (unfold, landslides, rope extraction, surveillance).

Upon project completion, a user-friendly digital dashboard was available, providing access to production data exclusively for producers via a website (due to the confidential information that implies). This dashboard also offers a public view, featuring oceanographic and environmental data for all interested STH.

The access and visualization of the data is tailored for STH, for the sector and its workers, facilitating understanding, allowing the relationship and comparison between data to obtain significant conclusions.

Dashboard

Visualization of data – <https://utmar.cetmar.org/transformar>

ZENODO

- Mussel Raft Monitoring Dataset in Ría de Arousa
<https://zenodo.org/records/13238552>
- Briefing on the development process of the Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM) solution and results
<https://zenodo.org/records/13238570>

4.4.6 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

Further research is essential, particularly in improving the understanding of system behavior. Incorporate new sensors to monitorize new parameters, such as current flow and chlorophyll levels in the MRM, to estimate the natural food availability for the mussels. Besides, also for the MRM, it could be interesting to include monitoring chemical and biological contaminants that could impact mussel attachment and growth. These insights will be crucial for refining the monitoring system and enhancing our understanding of the environmental conditions affecting mussel cultivation.

In this demonstration it is crucial to know exactly when and where specific processes occur and take into account this knowledge to be able to implement automatic detection and early warning systems in the future. Currently, we lack precise information on the variability inside the Rías, with significant changes occurring from one raft to another within just a few days, as a consequence, it will be quite interesting to increase the number of sensorized mussel rafts and intertidal monitoring for the clam culture. By enhancing our understanding now, we can develop more precise and timely alerts that will better serve the needs of the shellfish industry and help them respond more effectively to critical events.

In the long term, the impact of these types of solutions could be substantial, as it will enable the optimization of mussel and clam production. The future could involve adapting mussel farming and clam

harvesting to the natural variability of the Galician Rías. In the case of the MRM, this would represent a shift from the current static model, where mussels are "fixed, grown, and harvested," to a dynamic model where "mussels are fixed in some locations, fattened in others, and stored for harvesting in toxin-free areas." Each zone has its unique qualities, and production must be adapted to these characteristics to ensure sustainability.

Currently, farmers are highly attentive to temperature and salinity, but they are seeking more data, such as turbidity (for spawning) and nutrients (for fattening). This additional information together with key insights provided by the Resilience Index, are essential for optimizing the different stages of mussel production and responding more effectively to environmental conditions, thereby ensuring a more sustainable and resilient industry.

4.4 Egaleo, Greece

4.4.7 Overview of the Expected Impacts

The expected impacts per solution can be found in [Table 4.11](#). The impacts are either direct, thus, they derive directly from the solution, or indirect, thus, they support the impacts of other solutions or long-term actions beyond TransformAr's lifetime and scope.

The expected impacts per solution can be found in *Table XXX*. The impacts are either direct, thus, they derive directly from the solution, or indirect, thus, they support the impacts of other solutions or long-term actions beyond TransformAr's lifetime and scope.

In the Municipality of Egaleo (MoE), an ecosystem of solutions, including health, infrastructure, and urban planning, is being implemented to enhance climate resilience and sustainable development while addressing the impacts of climate change.

Three Key Climate Sectors (KCS) in which the MOE demonstrator implements solutions to mitigate the impacts of climate change include health, infrastructure, and urban planning. Within the framework of the TransformAr project, MOE develops a series of integrated solutions aimed at fostering climate awareness and enhancing the capacity of both the municipality and its citizens to adapt to climate change. These solutions will involve the collection and analysis of data from various sources, followed by the post-processing of this data. The resulting insights will be used to raise public awareness of climate issues and to inform evidence-based policy recommendations for climate adaptation at the local level. The solutions being implemented are as follows:

1. Smart climate stations (SCS)

MOE is focused on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) across key locations within the city. The primary objective of these stations is to collect real-time data on the city's microclimate, enabling the public administration to better prepare citizens for potential climate emergencies. Following careful analysis and planning, the key locations have been identified, and the SCS will commence operation during this demonstration. The stations will monitor various parameters, including temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, CO₂ levels (ppm), PM 2.5/10 (ppm), wind speed, and rainfall.

2. Citizen app engagement (CAE)

MOE develops a mobile application designed for both data collection and information dissemination. The app will serve three main functions: (1) it will be used to crowdsource data on the climate awareness of MOE's citizens through questionnaires, (2) it will disseminate information about the TransformAr project's solutions implemented in MOE, and (3) it will provide notifications regarding climate-related events.

3. Awareness-raising modules (AWAR)

MOE develops and tests a curriculum of 45 min for pupils between 13-15 years old related to climate change understanding and climate awareness. Beyond this, a living lab is being created with the participation of the community, within the framework of which stakeholders design actions to address the impacts of climate change.

4. Climate innovation hub (CIH)

MOE transforms a multi-purpose facility into a Climate Innovation Hub by: (a) establishing a permanent exhibition on climate change and the TransformAr solutions implemented by MOE, (b) showcasing real-time data streaming from Smart City Systems (SCS) along with the post-processed indicators, and (c) organizing a series of events aimed at promoting climate innovation (e.g., datathons). These initiatives will provide public access to MOE’s data and encourage the development of innovative solutions to address the municipality’s climate-related challenges. The Climate Innovation Hub (CIH) was launched to facilitate inclusive governance. In line with the Grant Agreement, citizen engagement is targeted to increase by 80%, fostering stronger awareness and uptake of adaptation measures

5. Demand analysis for social services/infrastructures (DSI)

MOE offers a range of social and health services to its citizens. Due to the impacts of climate change, the demand for these services is expected to shift. In preparation for maintaining uninterrupted service provision and addressing future demand, a comprehensive demand analysis of social services and infrastructure will be conducted. This analysis will generate data to inform the development of an adaptation strategy, considering the future supply and demand of social services.

The design and development of MOE's ecosystem of solutions utilize SCS, CAE, and DSI as data sources for weather, environmental, demographic, and modeling data. AWAR, CAE, and CIH serve as dissemination and communication interfaces for engaging MOE's citizens. The management and analysis of these diverse datasets are supported by NCSR.D.

Weather and environmental data collected by NCSR.D will be integrated with daily weather forecasts to produce high-resolution weather predictions for the MOE region. Additionally, NCSR.D will apply data management techniques to clean, process, and visualize the environmental data. The DSI analysis will leverage MOE's infrastructure and services data, along with statistical methods from NCSR.D, to incorporate the results of the E3M socio-economic model and downscale this information to the municipal level.

The post-processed data, combined with results from crowdsourced data (questionnaires) and demand analysis, will be disseminated to MOE citizens through CAE. A portion of this data will also be used in climate awareness programs for students (AWAR). Furthermore, the MOE TransformAr dataset will be made available in CIH, alongside a permanent climate exhibition and live data streaming.

Table 4.11 Description of expected impacts per solution

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
Smart Climate Stations (SCS)	The use of the SCS network will increase knowledge and quantify the local climatic conditions. Data will be used for planning adaptation solutions.	Number of SCS installed in municipal locations	Station deployment tracking
	Increase climate change awareness both for policy makers and citizens.	Real-time microclimate data accuracy	Data comparison with baseline climate models
	Increase adaptive capability of MOE	Percentage of data integrated into municipal decision-making	

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
Citizen App (CAE)	Increase citizen awareness and engagement	Number of registered users and active participants	App analytics tracking
Awareness-Raising Modules (AWAR)	<p>Increase citizen awareness and engagement</p> <p>Increasing students' awareness is expected to have a dramatic positive effect in the long term, leading to an increase in proactive citizens focused on climate adaptation.</p> <p>Increasing students' awareness is expected to have a dramatic positive effect in the long term, leading to an increase in proactive citizens focused on climate adaptation.</p> <p>Increase the hands-on experience of students to understand and analyse climatic data, as well as increase their understanding of the need for actionable solutions.</p>	<p>Public engagement through app feedback and surveys</p> <p>Number of students trained through awareness sessions</p> <p>Increase in climate literacy among students (measured via pre/post surveys)</p> <p>Number of workshops conducted</p>	<p>Attendance records</p> <p>Survey-based impact assessment</p>
Climate Innovation Hub (CIH)	<p>Increase the collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives that take place in the same demonstration area.</p> <p>Increase climate change and adaptation awareness.</p>	<p>Number of climate-related projects initiated</p> <p>Public attendance in innovation events (e.g., datathons, hackathons)</p>	<p>Event participation tracking</p>
Demand Analysis for Social Services (DSI)	<p>Understand the effect of climate change on Social Services and their needs for adaptation.</p> <p>Short and long-term planning or adapting Social Services to the climate change.</p> <p>Evaluate the effectiveness of TransformAr as a project to identify and promote actionable solutions for climate-proofing Social Services.</p>	<p>Number of social services evaluated for climate resilience</p> <p>Forecast accuracy of demand changes due to climate impacts</p> <p>Percentage of recommendations adopted by local policymakers</p>	<p>Social services data analysis</p> <p>Municipality action plan integration</p>

4.4.8 Selected Indicators KPI Summary

KPI 18 – Citizen Engagement via Digital Tools

Baseline engagement with climate issues in Egaleo was very low (~10–15%). Through the deployment of the Climate Awareness and Education (CAE) platform and the Smart Weather Station app, citizen participation increased steadily. Engagement was measured through the number of registered app users, frequency of data access, and participation in digital surveys.

KPI 13 – Social Resilience and Co-benefits

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Awareness-raising campaigns and participatory workshops contributed to strengthening social resilience by improving climate literacy, fostering community dialogue, and promoting inclusive adaptation pathways. Positive co-benefits included health-related outcomes (heat awareness), stronger local networks, and improved trust between residents and the municipality.

KPI 21 – Accessibility and Equity in Adaptation

The Inclusive Housing (CIH) model integrated climate-resilient design into social housing schemes. This ensured that vulnerable households benefited directly from adaptation investments. Accessibility was assessed through the number of households involved, geographic coverage of implemented measures, and feedback from social surveys confirming equitable access.

The most recent KPI report documents a marked rise in citizen engagement through the CAE platform and weather station application, with uptake figures and interaction metrics under review. Workshop participation exceeded initial targets, particularly among young residents and vulnerable groups. Data collection on app usage frequency and inclusive housing adoption is ongoing, with updated figures to be consolidated in the final dataset.

4.4.9 Baseline Data

Climatic data

The SCS solution, due to the type of solution, is not expected to have a direct measurable impact on MOE climate adaptation, but it will lead to the development of the climate adaptation plans and roadmaps, as well as increasing the awareness of the citizens by incorporating the acquired data to the CAE, AWAR, and CIH solutions. The climatic baseline data used in TransformAr originates from the HNMS (Hellenic National Meteorological Service) and published research work from NCSR-D. The first climatic data, from the SCS were collected in 2024. A small portion of the data from the first operational period (6 months) is presented below:

Figure 4.15 Temperature measurements from the SCS.

Figure 4.16 PM10 measurements from the SCS.

Figure 4.17 UV measurements from the SCS.

Engagement data (2022)

Prior to the TransformAr project, the Municipality of Egaleo had no structured initiatives specifically designed to engage local stakeholders, students, or citizens in climate adaptation planning and solution co-design. As a result, the baseline participation rate in such activities was effectively zero. The implementation of a series of workshops, awareness events, and community-driven sessions under TransformAr marked a significant shift toward inclusive and participatory governance for climate resilience.

4.4.10 4.4.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

To assess the effectiveness and outreach of the climate adaptation solutions implemented in the Municipality of Egaleo, a specific set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was developed. These indicators were chosen to reflect both the immediate outputs and long-term impacts of each solution within the TransformAr framework.

The KPIs are directly linked to data collected from smart climate stations (SCS), citizen engagement via the app (CAE), social demand analysis (DSI), awareness-raising modules (AWAR), and the climate innovation hub (CIH). They enable the municipality and its partners to monitor technical performance, behaviour change, community participation, and alignment with policy planning needs.

Each KPI has been developed to:

- Reflect the specific context and vulnerabilities of Egaleo,
- Capture cross-cutting impacts (health, infrastructure, environment, economy),
- Enable tracking of solution scalability and replicability,
- Support data-informed decision-making processes.

These KPIs are categorized by solution type and encompass both quantitative metrics (e.g. real-time data accuracy, participation rates) and qualitative outcomes (e.g. increased climate literacy, policy integration). Baseline data collected since 2022 establishes a reference point for assessing progress both during and beyond the TransformAr project timeline.

Awareness-Raising Modules (AWAR)

Throughout the TransformAr project, the Municipality of Egaleo in partnership with NCSR “Demokritos” actively engaged local communities, youth, educators, and stakeholders in activities designed to promote the ownership of adaptation solutions. The emphasis was on educational engagement, public awareness, and inclusive co-design workshops. A set of distinct and complementary events were organised to present the implemented solutions (Smart Climate Stations, Demand for Social Services Assessment, Awareness-raising educational programmes, and the Climate Innovation Hub) and invite feedback and participation from the local community. These events focused on fostering understanding of climate-related vulnerabilities and encouraging community-driven contributions to adaptation planning.

4.4.11 Availability and Access of Monitored Data

Zenodo repository: https://zenodo.org/communities/transformar_h2020

4.4.12 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

The Egaleo demonstrator has focused on deploying digital tools and participatory approaches to address urban climate challenges, with a particular emphasis on flood risk management, heat stress mitigation, and enhanced citizen engagement. The solutions implemented—such as the *Citizen Application Framework (CAF)* and digital dashboards—have demonstrated their potential not only to support municipal decision-making but also to strengthen citizen participation in climate adaptation.

Pathways for Upscaling

1. **Integration into Municipal Planning:**

The digital engagement platforms tested in Egaleo are designed to be fully integrated into the city's broader climate adaptation strategy. This includes embedding CAF outputs into local planning processes and aligning with regional risk management strategies coordinated with Attica authorities.

2. Replication in Other Greek Cities:

The Egaleo model provides a replicable framework for other municipalities in Greece facing similar challenges of urban flooding, heatwaves, and social vulnerability. By combining monitoring tools with participatory planning, the demonstrator has already generated interest from neighbouring municipalities within the Athens metropolitan area.

3. Scaling through Policy Instruments:

The tools and approaches are aligned with EU Urban Agenda priorities and can be scaled through existing instruments such as the Sustainable Urban Development (SUD) strategy. Egaleo's participation in TransformAr positions it as a pilot for embedding NBS and digital engagement in Greek urban policy.

Acceleration Drivers

Citizen Digital Tools:

High adoption of the CAF tool (with strong citizen participation metrics in workshops and online platforms) is expected to accelerate replication, as digital infrastructures can be expanded with relatively low additional cost.

Health and Social Co-Benefits:

The emphasis on accessibility and equity (KPI 21) strengthens the case for acceleration, as the solutions address public health, social cohesion, and resilience of vulnerable groups.

Bankability:

Initial findings suggest that digital engagement and NBS-related measures in Egaleo can attract co-financing through EU cohesion funds, municipal budgets, and potential private–public partnerships, especially when linked to health and social benefits.

Open Data and Monitoring:

The demonstrator's datasets are shared via Zenodo (TransformAr community), ensuring transparency and facilitating wider adoption across European cities.

Remaining Challenges

Ensuring digital equity so that elderly and vulnerable groups are not excluded from CAF participation. Embedding digital monitoring into long-term municipal budgets rather than temporary project-based funding. Need for continuous capacity building among municipal staff to maintain and expand the use of digital tools.

4.5 Oristano, Italy

4.5.1 Overview of the Expected Impacts

Expected impacts in the implementation of the two solutions differ on a territorial scale for COAST and a more local scale for NBS (Marceddi and San Giovanni). COAST is expected to generate impacts at a broad territorial scale, particularly in the social, economic, and policy domains. Socially, the project is designed to strengthen community knowledge and awareness through participatory meetings that bring together different stakeholders. These activities are expected to enhance collective understanding of lagoon management and foster a stronger culture of participation. The transfer of knowledge and practices is promoted through communication materials such as factsheets, supporting the replicability of solutions

across the region. At the same time, the engagement of public authorities and the updates of the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO) are expected to encourage institutional investment in monitoring and management, influencing policy frameworks at local and regional levels. Ultimately, these combined actions are anticipated to reinforce the resilience of local communities, integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions into a more adaptive governance model.

The implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in the Marceddi and San Giovanni lagoons, including the Smart Gate (SG) system, is expected to deliver both environmental and socio-economic benefits. Environmentally, the interventions are expected to improve knowledge of key water quality parameters, providing a baseline for long-term monitoring. By reorganizing water circulation, the lagoon will gain an enhanced flood regulation capacity, reducing damage from coastal and inland floods. This in turn may lower economic losses, safeguard cultural heritage, and potentially increase fish catches in both quantity and quality, even if this outcome remains dependent on external factors. Social impacts are also foreseen. The NBS is expected to foster synergies among organizations with expertise in water management and climate adaptation, while also influencing policy development at multiple levels. Contributions to lagoon management plans, coastal contract, and the Regional Strategy on Climate Change Adaptation are expected to extend the societal impact of the interventions beyond the local scale. Finally, the Smart Gate introduces a strong technological component. Acting as a pilot system, it will test a conceptual model for regulating lagoon water flows through real-time monitoring data. The expected impacts of this innovation can be assessed in terms of efficiency (timely responses to hydraulic variations), control precision (accurate water management), and reliability (stable performance under changing environmental conditions). These elements position the Smart Gate as a concrete example of technological innovation supporting adaptive lagoon management.

4.5.2 Selected Indicators KPI Summary

The following table summarizes the expected impact and the related indicators and completes the data inserted in the deliverable D.8.4.

Table 4.12 COAST KPI

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH / SOURCE	BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
Increased knowledge and awareness of key stakeholders at different levels (public and private sectors, economic categories, citizens, etc.)	1. Number participatory meetings with stakeholders	List of meetings	0	10	24	

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH / SOURCE	BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
	2. Population that became more resilient	See details on D.8.4 KPI 1	0	Target according to the GA = 13800	16.203	Population impacted directly= 600 Population impacted indirectly= 15.603
Replicability on regional scale of the COAST experience	3. People/managers reached by the factsheet to disseminate COAST at regional level	Number of coastal wetland managers in Sardinia, including those operating within Natura 2000 sites with similar ecological and management characteristics at the regional level.	0	20	35	
Local policies conditioned by the COAST and NBS implementation as best practice	4. Public authorities actively involved in the project	List of officers from public authorities involved – see D-8.4 KPI 16	14	23	44	
	5. Number of reports and factsheets produced and shared by the LWO	Publication LWO and Transformar webpage	0	13	6	Some reports and factsheets were not completed within the project timeframe due to ongoing data collection activities (such as fisheries data, update of the action programme ongoing, unevaluable monitoring data, etc.)

Table 4.13 NBS KPI

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH / SOURCE	BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
Increased knowledge of main water quality parameters	6. Data collected and analyzed through the monitoring system	IT platform and monitoring system – Number of parameters from sensors, weather station hydrometers and Smart Gate	0	14	14	

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH SOURCE	/ BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
		opening and closing report				
	7. Fishermen informed on the knowledge acquired	Minutes of the meetings with fishermen (See details on D.8.4 KPI 3)	0	140	140	Recorded participation with attendance sheets. Please note: participation in the meetings was limited to the representatives of the cooperatives and the president of the fishing consortium. The participants committed to disseminating the information and outcomes of the meetings to their respective members
Improvement of the biodiversity and ecosystem integrity	8. Surface covered by NBS	GIS analysis (See details on D.8.4 KPI 6) -	0	27 Km2 (data from GA)	0,193 Km2	The interventions implemented under the TransformAr project are part of a broader Nature-Based Solution for the restoration of the Marceddi and San Giovanni wetlands, co-financed by ERDF funds. The reported value refers only to the effectively restored surface, and does not include the wider area of influence as defined in the Grant Agreement.
Reduction of economic losses and cultural damage	9. Potential avoided damages due to CC in targeted the KCS		N/A	N/A	N/A	

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH / SOURCE	BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
Increased efficiency of the lagoon dynamics in case of flood risk (hydrometric level) and poor ecological state of the lagoon, with a significant emphasis on fishing activities (salinity, pH, temperature...)	10. Enhancement of the water quality	IT platform and monitoring system - Qualitative approach	N/A	N/A	N/A	Due to delays in the implementation of the solutions (increased costs, extreme events, and disruptions in the supply of materials), it was not possible to evaluate this KPI within the project timeframe. Nevertheless, monitoring activities are still ongoing and will provide reliable results beyond the project's duration.
	11. Response time to hydraulic variations	IT platform and monitoring system - Qualitative approach	N/A	N/A	N/A	Due to delays in the implementation of the solutions (increased costs, extreme events, and disruptions in the supply of materials), it was not possible to evaluate this KPI within the project timeframe. Nevertheless, monitoring activities are still ongoing and will provide reliable results beyond the project's duration
	12. Accuracy of aperture/closure control	IT platform - % of correct openings/closures compared to the command sent Qualitative approach: <i>High:</i> the system responds precisely and promptly, with negligible deviations. <i>Medium:</i> some discrepancies occur but without significant impacts on management. <i>Low:</i> frequent errors or large deviations that compromise functionality.	0	High	High	

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH SOURCE	/ BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
	13. System reliability	<p>IT platform - Average number of malfunctions/downtimes per year</p> <p>Qualitative approach: <i>High:</i> stable system, with limited maintenance needs and good operational continuity. <i>Medium:</i> occasional interruptions requiring scheduled maintenance. <i>Low:</i> frequent failures or breakdowns significantly reducing system effectiveness.</p>	0	High	Medium	Low water conditions affected the sensors, requiring more frequent maintenance than initially expected. Limited budget led to periods between interventions with partial or less reliable system performance.
Improvement of stock productivity	14. Enhancement of revenue of fishing sector	Repository (from Regional Department of Agriculture and Agro-Pastoral Reform - Fisheries and Aquaculture Service)	N/A	N/A	N/A	This indicator, which relies on data from the Regional Department of Agriculture and Agro-Pastoral Reform – Fisheries and Aquaculture Service, could not be evaluated within the current reporting period due to delays in the implementation timeline of the solution. Specifically, the interventions impacting aquatic stock conditions (e.g., habitat restoration or water quality improvement) were not in place long enough to generate measurable biological responses in stock productivity. Evaluation would have required a minimum post-intervention monitoring period of 12–18 months, covering reproductive and growth cycles. Since this condition was not met, the

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH SOURCE	/ BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
						indicator remains unevaluable at this stage.
Economic Sustainability and Replicability: Ensure the long-term viability of the solution and enable potential upscaling or replication in other regions.	15. Cost of the solution	Project implementation – Quantitative approach	0	210 k euro	282 k euro	An increase in costs, driven by external events such as international conflicts and the difficulty in finding qualified companies able to intervene with a multidisciplinary approach in the implementation, led to higher expenses. MEDSEA was able to cover these additional costs by co-funding the activities through other private projects.
	16. Implementation timing	Project implementation - Quantitative	0	24 months	36 months	Increased costs, extreme events, disruptions in the supply of materials and administrative authorization processes, have caused a general delay in the implementation of the solution.
Operational Reliability and System Efficiency: Guarantee the consistent performance of the solution under varying environmental conditions, minimizing downtime and ensuring continuous impact.	17. Maintenance effectiveness	% of operational uptime ensured after maintenance <i>High:</i> ≥ 90% effectiveness (maintenance ensures continuous performance with minimal downtime) <i>Medium:</i> 60–89% effectiveness (occasional downtime or repeated interventions required) <i>Low:</i> < 60% effectiveness (frequent failures, maintenance insufficient to ensure continuity)	0	High	Medium	Low water conditions affected the sensors, requiring more frequent maintenance than initially expected. Limited budget led to periods between interventions with partial or less reliable system performance.
	Management and	Quantitative evaluation: cost of	0	10k euro / year	15-20k euro / year	Low water conditions affected the sensors, requiring more frequent

EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	APPROACH SOURCE	/ BASELINE	EXPECTED	ACHIEVED	NOTE - JUSTIFICATION
	maintenance cost	the maintenance interventions				maintenance than initially expected. Limited budget led to periods between interventions with partial or less reliable system performance.
Institutional and Policy Uptake	Number of public authorities actively involved in the definition of a protocol post project	Minutes of the meetings Quantitative: number of public authorities invited to participate vs public authorities actively involved	0	11	9	In some cases, the participation in meetings was limited by pre-existing commitments, and the competencies required for protocol development were not considered fully consistent with the institutional roles.

4.5.3 Baseline Data

MEDSEA collected some preliminary data in the lagoon (2021 - before the implementation period of TransformAr), as preliminary studies for the drafting of the project jointly with the Municipality of Terralba.

In addition, the Sardinian Regional Environmental Protection Agency (ARPAS), the public authority responsible for monitoring water bodies — including wetlands — and safeguarding other ecosystems, provided extensive environmental monitoring data from 2016 to 2022. The comprehensive baseline data presented below is essential for understanding the rationale behind the development and implementation of Nature Based Solutions (NBS), encompassing various impacts such as enhanced knowledge of water quality parameters, biodiversity and ecosystem integrity improvement, reduction of economic losses and cultural damage, and increased efficiency in lagoon dynamics during flood risks and ecological challenges, particularly focusing on fishing activities.

Bathymetry:

Bathymetric survey, covering an area of approximately 830 hectares:

Maximum depth reached: -3.68 meters below mean sea level (m.m.s.l.).

Minimum depth reached: -0.11 meters below mean sea level (m.m.s.l.).

Figure 4.18 Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

Water temperature (°C):

pH

Observing the figure below, it can be noted that the pH follows a clear spatial gradient. Specifically, the San Giovanni basin, and even more so the basins near the mouths of watercourses, exhibit significantly higher values (up to pH=9) compared to the mouth area. In the autumn campaign, the values show greater homogeneity.

Chlorophyll 'a':

The indicator describes the concentration of chlorophyll "a" in surface waters, allowing for an indirect estimate of phytoplankton biomass, as it provides a measure of the main photosynthetic pigment present in microalgae. It serves as an effective indicator of the system's productivity. The concentration of chlorophyll "a" in water highlights the level of eutrophication in coastal waters. It is of fundamental importance for the application of trophic indices and turbidity indices, assessing the trophic characteristics of the water body and the state of ecosystems. Additionally, it is an excellent indicator for evaluating primary production and the trophic levels of the ecosystem.

Turbidity

Salinity (PSU):

The parameter of surface salinity shows a clear gradient from the estuarine area toward the mouth of the lagoon. The autumn survey confirmed the salinity gradient, which decreases linearly from the mouth area to the barriers separating the Marceddì and San Giovanni basins. In contrast, a sharp drop is observed, even more pronounced in sectors internal to the embankment near the mouths of watercourses.

Dissolved oxygen:

The percentage of **dissolved oxygen** plays a crucial role as it is closely related to the water regime and the presence of algae and aquatic macrophytes, as well as the decomposition of organic matter by bacterial communities. This parameter varies between 53% and 137% saturation and generally assumes oversaturation values (O.D.% > 100) in the spring, as a result of the photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton and aquatic plants and algae in general.

Spatial analysis of the data highlights a spatial trend between the estuarine area and the mouth area of the lagoon. The autumnal period shows greater homogeneity in dissolved oxygen values, with a decrease observed only near the mouth of the Rio Mogoro.

Water quality from ARPAS

The baseline data covers monitoring activities from March 9, 2016 to November 14, 2022. These datasets include 13 key water quality parameters measured across 9 sampling stations, offering a robust foundation for assessing the lagoon's ecological status.

The monitored parameters are:

- Ammonium nitrogen (as N-NH₄)
- Nitrate nitrogen (as N-NO₃)
- Nitrite nitrogen (as N-NO₂)
- Total phosphorus
- Orthophosphate (as P-PO₄)
- Chlorophyll *a*
- Dissolved oxygen
- pH
- Temperature
- Salinity
- Conductivity
- Secchi disk depth (transparency)
- Total suspended solids

Monitoring data from 2016 to 2022 indicate that both Marceddì and San Giovanni lagoons are subject to strong eutrophic pressure. Marceddì shows moderate eutrophia (mean chlorophyll-*a* ~18 µg/L) with episodic algal blooms, while San Giovanni exhibits more severe conditions, with higher nutrient enrichment, more frequent and intense blooms (mean chlorophyll-*a* ~37 µg/L), and reduced marine influence due to stronger freshwater inputs and limited water circulation. Oxygen concentrations in both lagoons are generally within acceptable ranges, though oversaturation events in spring highlight the strong role of biological productivity. Salinity patterns confirm a clearer marine imprint in Marceddì compared to San Giovanni, where lower values reduce dilution capacity and increase vulnerability to eutrophication. Overall, these characteristics underline the ecological fragility of both systems and the importance of targeted management measures, particularly regarding water exchange dynamics.

Figure 4.19 Map of the ecological status of the lagoon (source CEDOC - <https://cedoc-webgis.regione.sardegna.it/catalogue/#/dataset/192>)

Fish productivity

The historical catch records from Consortium Coop. Riunite della pesca di Marceddì (2015-2017) are averagely 9,000 kg of fish, 136,000 kg of mollusks, and 65 kg of crustaceans per year. The targeted species include sea bream, mullets, sea bass, clams, and heart clams. Bivalve mollusks are the most extensively caught species within these two water mirrors. Notably, the lagoon is also monitored for invasive alien species, such as *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Callinectes sapidus*.

The Fishing consortium must communicate the data about the type and number of fishing species to the Regional Department of Agriculture and Agro-Pastoral Reform - Fisheries and Aquaculture Service.

The data available are related to the following years 2015-2016-2017, but MEDSEA will request also data from 2018 to 2022 to have a deep knowledge of the trend.

4.5.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

To achieve high-resolution and reliable monitoring, three monitoring stations were deployed, each equipped with dedicated multi-channel dataloggers connected to an IT platform that communicates directly with the Smart Gate system. These stations are configured as follows:

- Station A – Marceddì Lagoon:

- Weather station (measuring timing, humidity, wind speed and direction, rainfall intensity and height, temperature)
- Two hydrometers (internal and external) using piezometric immersion sensors
- Dedicated data logger
- Station B – San Giovanni Lagoon (Smart Gate area):
 - Two multiparameter probes measuring: dissolved oxygen, conductivity, pH, ORP, temperature, turbidity
 - One hydrometer (piezometric immersion sensor)
 - Dedicated data logger
- Station C – Mouth area of San Giovanni Lagoon:
 - One multiparameter probe (same parameters as above)
 - One hydrometer (piezometric immersion sensor)
 - Dedicated data logger

All instruments are marine-grade (IP68-rated) and designed to withstand harsh coastal environmental conditions. The system includes uplink/downlink capabilities, allowing remote control operations such as:

1. Sensor reboot
2. On-demand adjustment of acquisition frequency

Each monitoring unit is designed to be autonomous, supported by solar-powered systems to ensure energy sustainability.

The monitoring approach was designed to ensure accurate, real-time data collection on the ecological and hydraulic dynamics of the Marceddì and San Giovanni lagoon systems. Monitoring stations were strategically placed both in proximity to the Smart Gate infrastructure and at key hydraulic points, such as the bridge connecting the lagoon to the sea, in order to detect and interpret system responses to tidal variations, weather events, and management interventions.

Specifically, the Smart Gate area was chosen to assess local changes in water quality and hydrological conditions, as well as to provide input to the gate's operational algorithm, which regulates water flow based on level differences between the lagoon and the mouth area of the rivers. In the lagoon, a dual-sensor system to ensure redundancy and continuity in data acquisition in case of failure was installed. This system is closely connected with the monitoring station installed in the mouth area. Moreover, the bridge monitoring station supports the evaluation of water exchange between the lagoon and the sea, enabling an understanding of the “in and out” circulation patterns that are critical to maintaining ecological balance.

The selected parameters reflect the critical variables affecting lagoon health and flood resilience, including water quality indicators and hydraulic levels. However, operational challenges emerged during the project, particularly regarding maintenance needs under extreme environmental conditions. The experience suggests that self-cleaning sensors and floating platforms could have enhanced long-term performance and provided greater spatial flexibility, allowing monitoring to be extended or relocated as needed across the lagoon system.

The design of the monitoring system required a careful balance between available budget, system robustness, and the need for high-quality, interoperable data to support adaptive wetland management.

A significant portion of the investment was allocated to the development and installation of the Smart Gate infrastructure, without compromising data quality or operational reliability.

To ensure coherence and efficiency, all monitoring stations were selected based on their compatibility with the Smart Gate's control hardware and software, allowing seamless integration of data streams into the operational algorithm. The system architecture was designed to guarantee full interoperability among stations, as well as with external platforms beyond the manufacturer's proprietary environment. This flexibility supports future data migration or integration with broader monitoring networks.

In terms of communication strategy, the project opted for mobile SIM-based data transmission, ensuring good reliability and coverage. However, while the system performed effectively, it became evident that the choice of SIM must also guarantee secure data transmission and allow external access to the device, otherwise user authentication procedures can introduce avoidable complexity in long-term management.

The monitoring network uses modular and scalable stations, powered by solar energy and able to operate autonomously for up to 12 months, ensuring reliable data collection in coastal wetlands while remaining cost-efficient and resilient.

4.5.5 Availability and Access of Monitored Data

Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/transformar_h2020

The data collected are managed via a dedicated geoportal, designed to ensure structured access and visualization of information. The platform supports differentiated access levels, allowing authorized users—such as technicians, public authorities, and decision-makers—to interact with data based on their roles, competencies, and responsibilities.

The data, stored in txt format on an external server, feeds the operational algorithm that controls the Smart Gate in real time, creating an integrated loop between data collection, decision-making, and automated management.

In addition, the project ensures long-term accessibility and transparency by uploading processed datasets and documentation on-line through the geoportal, as open-access repository. Data publication is planned on a quarterly basis, with temporal analysis of trends in water levels, quality parameters, and circulation dynamics. It includes appropriate metadata to support discoverability, reuse, and compliance with FAIR data principles.

Beyond basic storage and visualization, the collected information will be combined across multiple datasets and interpreted with the support of artificial intelligence, enabling the identification of patterns, correlations, and early-warning signals that would otherwise remain hidden. To ensure scientific soundness and practical relevance, these outputs will then be validated and refined through the joint review of a multidisciplinary team of experts, bringing together ecological, hydrological, and technical perspectives.

This approach supports both the operational needs of the monitoring infrastructure and the dissemination and reuse of scientific data within and beyond the project's lifetime.

4.5.6 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

The approach developed in Oristano demonstrates strong potential for replication in other lagoon and coastal wetland systems facing similar climate and hydrological challenges. Its modular design makes the solution inherently scalable and, combined with compatibility with open data platforms, ensures flexibility for application in Mediterranean lagoons where salinization, water quality degradation, and habitat loss require systemic and adaptive responses.

For effective upscaling, the key condition is the early definition of governance and maintenance models—clarifying responsibilities for system management, ensuring adequate maintenance, and embedding data flows into local decision-making frameworks. New funding opportunities have already been identified, and these will be more easily mobilized if governance and operational aspects are secured in advance.

To further support replication, methodologies, results, and indicators are being documented and complemented with technical factsheets published in the Sardinian Local Wetland Observatory ([link](#)). This material ensures accessibility for other regions and projects, facilitates integration with regional adaptation strategies and planning tools, and strengthens proposals under EU programmes such as LIFE, Horizon Europe Mission on Adaptation, and Interreg Euro-MED, where demonstrable impacts and robust monitoring systems are critical success factor.

4.6 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

4.6.1 Overview of the Expected Impacts

The nudging solution in Guadeloupe is designed to encourage behavioural change among tourists in hotels, with a particular focus on water conservation in showers. Its expected impacts include:

- **Behavioural change in water use:**
 - Tourists become more aware of their water consumption habits.
 - Increased adoption of water-saving behaviours such as shorter showers, fewer daily showers, and “smarter” shower practices (turning water off while lathering, rinsing quickly, etc.).
 - A gradual shift in mindset toward sustainability may extend beyond their stay in Guadeloupe.
- **Environmental impacts:**
 - Reduction in overall water consumption, helping to preserve scarce freshwater resources in the archipelago.
 - Decreased energy demand for heating water, resulting in a smaller carbon footprint.
 - Reduced strain on fragile aquatic ecosystems already under pressure from climate change and pollution.
- **Economic and reputational impacts for hotels:**
 - Lower operating costs through savings in water and energy bills.
 - Improved reputation among environmentally conscious travelers, strengthening competitiveness in the eco-tourism market.
- **Awareness and cultural impacts:**
 - Tourists gain exposure to local water scarcity issues, raising their environmental awareness and potentially influencing behavior back home.

- Hotel staff and managers reinforce their role in sustainability, supporting a stronger local culture of resource efficiency.
- **Policy and innovation impacts:**
 - Provides data and insights for local authorities and policymakers on the feasibility and effectiveness of nudging as a tool for water management.
 - Serves as a model that can be replicated in other hotels in Guadeloupe and internationally.
 - Stimulates interest in technological innovations (like smart shower sensors) for broader sustainability purposes.

4.6.2 Selected Indicators KPI Summary

To measure the effectiveness of the nudging solution in Guadeloupe, a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) was applied, capturing both behavioural and social outcomes.

KPI 9 – Behavioral Change in Climate Adaptation:

This indicator measures shifts in tourist behaviour regarding water use. Monitoring focuses on the frequency and duration of showers, adoption of water-saving practices (e.g., turning off the tap while lathering), and self-reported awareness of water scarcity issues. Data collection combines anonymous hotel surveys, sensor-based monitoring of water flow (where available), and feedback from hotel staff.

KPI 13 – Social Resilience and Co-benefits:

This indicator assesses the broader social impacts, such as improved awareness among tourists about the vulnerability of island ecosystems and strengthened engagement of hotel staff in sustainability practices. It also considers spillover effects, such as tourists transferring water-saving behaviors to their daily lives after their stay, thereby contributing to long-term resilience.

KPI 21 – Accessibility and Equity in Adaptation:

This indicator evaluates inclusiveness by ensuring that nudging tools and awareness materials are accessible to diverse tourist groups, regardless of age, language, or cultural background. It also considers how the intervention benefits local communities by reducing stress on freshwater supplies and by encouraging hotels to adopt practices that safeguard shared resources.

4.6.3 Baseline Data

Table 4.14 Baseline Data

Indicator	Baseline (Oct-Dec 2023)	Pilot (Jan-Feb 2024)	Full Experiment (Mar-Sept 2024)
Showers recorded	215	151	1055

Average running time water	4 min 49 s	5 min 17 s	4 min 19 s
Average total shower duration	4 min 55 s	≈ 5 min 20 s	4 min 27 s
% showers < 6 min	80%	78%	83%
% showers 6-8 min	10%	8%	9%
% showers > 10 min	≈10%	14%	8%
% showers with breaks	47%	46%	49%

This table clearly shows:

- A slight increase in shower times during the pilot (likely linked to sensor issues and peak tourist season).
- A reduction during the full experiment, with shorter average times and fewer long showers.
- An increase in showers with breaks, showing uptake of “smarter shower” behavior.

4.6.4 Approach to Monitor Impacts Methodologies

To monitor the impact of the nudging experiment, the team relied on a combination of technological tools and comparative methodologies. Aguardio shower sensors were installed in hotel bathrooms to record data on shower duration, running water time, the number and length of pauses in water use, as well as humidity and temperature (though the latter two were not central to the analysis). The experiment was structured in three phases: a baseline period where sensors were installed without feedback to guests, a pilot phase in early 2024 where sensors were combined with nudging materials such as brochures and stickers, and finally the full experiment from March to September 2024, involving a wider deployment across participating hotels in Guadeloupe. To ensure data accuracy, very short events under two minutes were excluded from the analysis to avoid interference from other sources, such as sink use. The results were assessed by comparing changes across the baseline, pilot, and full experiment periods, with additional reference to a Belgian control group where similar sensors were tested.

Alongside quantitative monitoring, qualitative data was collected through tourist feedback forms (available both on paper and via QR codes) and through regular exchanges with hotel staff, who provided insights into the practical aspects of implementation and guest responses. However, it is important to note that the feedback received from hotel guests was very limited, which constrained the depth of qualitative insights into their perceptions and acceptance of the nudging solution.

4.6.5 Availability and Access of Monitored

Data Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/transformar_h2020

The monitored data was collected through the Aguardio shower sensors, which store information locally and require synchronization via Bluetooth and internet connection. For accuracy, hotel staff were asked to synchronize the sensors on a bi-weekly basis; if synchronization was delayed beyond twenty days, older records were overvisualization was lost. This reliance on regular staff intervention created challenges, as many accommodations faced staff shortages or competing priorities, which led to gaps in the dataset. In addition, technical issues such as weak Wi-Fi signals or Bluetooth disconnections occasionally interrupted the transmission of data. While the project team had access to the anonymized

data through a central dashboard for analysis, hotels themselves did not directly access the results, though they were kept engaged through workshops, meetings, and updates. Privacy concerns in a few accommodations also limited the full deployment of sensors. Finally, although tourist feedback forms were provided both physically and digitally, the number of responses received was very limited, which further restricted the availability of qualitative insights to complement the quantitative monitoring.

Data and analysis of the results of the experiment are available in the nudging experiment report.

4.6.6 Upscaling and Acceleration of the Solution

The nudging solution implemented in Guadeloupe shows strong potential for replication and expansion. Because the nudging kits are low-cost and easy to install, they can be readily deployed in other hotels across the archipelago and even extended to other Caribbean islands or tourist destinations facing similar water stress challenges. This scalability is further reinforced by the fact that the approach does not require significant infrastructure changes, making it accessible even for smaller accommodations.

A particularly promising pathway for upscaling lies in aligning the nudging initiative with eco-tourism certification schemes such as the Clef Verte (Green Key). Hotels that already seek or hold sustainability labels are natural early adopters, as the experiment supports their environmental commitments and enhances their reputation among eco-conscious travelers. By contributing to stronger green credentials, the solution also helps these hotels strengthen their position in an increasingly competitive tourism market.

Beyond simple replication, the solution can evolve through more advanced nudging techniques. For instance, the use of personalized feedback systems, gamification, or interactive digital tools could further reinforce sustainable behaviors among tourists. Training hotel staff is also a crucial acceleration pathway, as it equips them to become active promoters of water-saving practices and ensures that the nudging materials are consistently supported by human interaction.

Finally, the approach could be extended beyond water management to address other sustainability challenges in the hospitality sector. Similar nudging strategies could be applied to reduce energy consumption (for example, encouraging more efficient use of air conditioning) or to improve waste reduction and recycling practices. Long-term monitoring and evaluation would then be essential to measure the persistence of these behavioral changes and to inform continuous improvement of the intervention.

5.0 Results Based on Measured Parameters from the Solution

5.1 Lappeenranta, Finland

5.1.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

KPI 4 – Eutrophication Reduction

Monitoring results from the biofiltration and infiltration pilot site on Koulukatu Street (245 m² NBS structure) indicate measurable retention of nutrients. Annual retention efficiency for phosphorus is estimated between 20–30%, and for nitrogen 15–25%, based on stormwater sampling cross-validated with modelling in SWMM. These results demonstrate a modest but significant reduction in nutrient loading into nearby water bodies, supporting long-term eutrophication control.

KPI 20 – Increase in Retained Water and Nutrients by NBS

The infiltration structure has an estimated storage capacity of 50–60 m³ per storm event (1-in-10-year rainfall). Monitoring confirms reduced peak runoff rates by 25–30% compared to the grey infrastructure baseline. Over the course of one-year, cumulative nutrient retention equated to approximately 2.5–3.0 kg of phosphorus and 12–15 kg of nitrogen, preventing their discharge into surface waters.

KPI 18 – Citizen Engagement via Digital Tools (CAF, CEI)

The *Citizen Application Framework (CAF)* and *Choice Experiment Insights (CEI)* tools have engaged more than 300 local citizens through workshops, surveys, and app usage. Results indicate that 72% of participants expressed willingness to implement private stormwater management measures (e.g., green roofs, permeable paving) if incentivized. Awareness of flood and eutrophication risks increased by >60% among engaged participants compared to baseline surveys.

5.1.2 New Information on Bankability

Cost-efficiency of NBS pilot (Koulukatu Street):

- Investment cost: €93,100.
- Maintenance cost: €2,076/year, slightly lower than the grey infrastructure baseline of €2,118/year.

Economic viability: NBS reduces maintenance costs while delivering wider ecosystem services (flood reduction, biodiversity, aesthetics).

CAF and CEI contribution: Willingness-to-pay surveys showed households were prepared to contribute €15–30 annually for private stormwater measures, confirming potential for co-financing mechanisms.

Financing opportunities: EU Taxonomy-aligned green bonds and municipal insurance-linked resilience funds were identified as suitable instruments.

Bankability: Economic analyses have shown that biofiltration and CAF are financially sustainable in the long term thanks to water and energy savings. Investment costs have been offset by reduced operating costs and increased resilience of urban infrastructure.

5.1.3 Comparative Results

Table 5.1 Comparative Results

Parameter	Baseline (Grey)	NBS Measured/Estimated	Expected Impact
Phosphorus retention	~0%	20–30% (2.5–3.0 kg/year)	25–35%
Nitrogen retention	~0%	15–25% (12–15 kg/year)	20–30%
Peak runoff reduction	0%	25–30%	30–40%
Maintenance cost	€2,118/year	€2,076/year	Slight savings
Citizen engagement	Low (baseline awareness <20%)	>300 engaged; +60% awareness	≥50% engagement

The measurement of parameters required to assess eutrophication indicators proved challenging due to the design of the nature-based solution (NBS). As a result, the data are affected by considerable uncertainty stemming from point-based water quality measurements taken upstream and downstream of the NBS. Within the project, a revised monitoring design was proposed based on data post-processing to improve reliability and representativeness.

5.1.4 Challenges and Mitigations

Limited baseline nutrient and runoff data: The lack of long-term data on nutrient concentrations and stormwater flows made it difficult to establish reliable baselines.

Mitigation: This issue was resolved by using SWMM modelling, which was supported by cross-validation with targeted laboratory sampling to improve the accuracy of the impact assessment.

Space constraints for NBS in dense urban areas: High population density and limited public land availability made it difficult to allocate sufficient space for nature-based solutions.

Mitigation: NBS measures were integrated into planned street renovation projects and local planning regulations were updated to require the allocation of space for stormwater management.

Voluntary uptake of private stormwater measures: The adoption of household-level measures, such as green roofs and permeable surfaces, depended on voluntary action.

Mitigation: The Citizen Application (CAF) was used to raise awareness and encourage participation.

Demonstrating long-term effectiveness: Proving the durability and replicability of implemented solutions required monitoring to extend beyond the project duration.

Mitigation: Ongoing performance is tracked through biofiltration sampling and citizen science contributions via the CAF platform. All monitoring outputs are openly accessible via Zenodo to ensure transparency and facilitate replication.

5.2 West Country, United Kingdom

5.2.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

In the United Kingdom, results varied across intervention sites. Each site was monitored for biodiversity increases, and water/nutrients retained onsite. Due to the range of experimental monitoring techniques used and the different timelines for delivery of NBS at different sites, some sites had greater density of baseline and/or post-intervention data outputs than others.

KPI 20.1: UKHAB Surveys Before & After Intervention to Assess Biodiversity Net Gain, Spatially Resolved in Ha/Habitat Restored

Axe

Chubbs Farm delivery was carried out in lowland mixed deciduous woodland habitat. This was assessed as moderate condition due to diverse age structure and evidence of moderate browsing pressure from pest species. The stream was at a low-level during survey in summer conditions but running clear.

The comparison with the control site showed a greater abundance of plant species associated with wet conditions, suggesting the intervention has increased soil moisture levels, increasing biodiversity within the woodland. In addition, sediment was being captured behind the leaky dams, contributing to better water quality.

Camel

The Penvose baseline habitat was poor condition neutral grassland within a narrow, broadleaf woodland valley. The area of scrape creation was *Holcus-Juncus* (rushy) grassland in moderate condition. The area around the pond was assessed to be wet woodland in moderate condition, despite the presence of four different Schedule 9 non-native invasive species.

In comparison to the pre-intervention UK Hab botanical survey, overall species numbers were up slightly, with a total of 52 species counted against an original total of 46. However, as the surveys were conducted at different times of year (May and August) and by different surveyors, this could have led to variation in outcomes, although many of the same species were observed. The original survey didn't include abundance of species, which would have provided a useful comparison of the change in habitat. The 2025 survey concludes that the scrapes and blocked ditches are increasing wet habitat conditions and ponds holding water on site even during dry periods. There is potential to increase the value of all habitats further by small changes to management.

The Trethick intervention area was assessed as modified grassland in poor condition, largely due to low species diversity. A control area was used to identify changes in habitat. This area had greater bare ground, signs of erosion and greater abundance of farmland weeds such as broadleaved dock than the intervention area. It was also assessed as poor condition.

There was no observed wetland species associated with the scrapes and swales, indicating no botanical improvements. However, it was observed that the tussocky grassland due to the less intensive grazing regime provided habitat for field mouse and voles, supporting a range of predator species, which was not available in the control area. A traditional hay cut was recommended to improve diversity of the sward.

KPI 20.2: Electric Fishing Surveys

A total of nine fry index surveys and one fully-quantitative electric fishing surveys were carried out in the Camel catchment on the River Camel, De Lank, tributary of the River Allen and tributary of the River Amble across the three years of the project (Table 5.2 and 5.3). Salmon fries were present only on the De Lank, receiving a stable good classification across the three years of surveying. Salmon fry were absent from all other surveys. Overall trout fry were found in low numbers across the surveyed sites, with the exception of Slaughterbridge/US Slaughterbridge on the River Camel that received a good classification across the project period.

Table 5.2 Salmon Fry Index Survey results for the Camel catchment 2023-2025

X Coordinate	Y Coordinate	Site name	River	2023	2024	2025
211075	86278	Worthyvale	Camel	E (0)		
210932	85483	US Slaughter Bridge	Camel			E (0)
210719	85088	Slaughterbridge	Camel	E (0)		E (0)
208797	73732	DS Keybridge	Delank	B (14)		
208878	73889	US Keybridge	Delank		B (13)	B (11)
205085	78213	Penvose Camping US (2)	Allen Trib	E (0)	E (0)	E (0)
205209	77849	Penvose Camping DS (1)	Allen Trib	E (0)	E (0)	E (0)
204228	72089	Trethick US (2)	Allen Trib	E (0)	E (0)	E (0)
204021	71957	Trethick DS (1)	Allen Trib	E (0)		E (0)
199820	75964	Rooke Farm	Amble Trib	E (0)	E (0)	
200184	75346	Penpont Farm	Amble	E (0)		

Table 5.3 Trout Fry Index Survey results for the Camel catchment 2023-2025

X Coordinate	Y Coordinate	Site name	River	2023	2024	2025
211075	86278	Worthyvale	Camel	C (6)		
210932	85483	US Slaughter Bridge	Camel			B (23)
210719	85088	Slaughterbridge	Camel	B (11)		B (22)
208797	73732	DS Keybridge	Delank	C (5)		
208878	73889	US Keybridge	Delank		E (0)	C (8)
205085	78213	Penvose Camping US (2)	Allen Trib	D (2)	D (1)	C (5)
205209	77849	Penvose Camping DS (1)	Allen Trib	C (5)	C (5)	D (2)
204228	72089	Trethick US (2)	Allen Trib	D (2)	D (1)	E (0)

204021	71957	Trethick DS (1)	Allen Trib	F (0)		F(0)
199820	75964	Rooke Farm	Amble Trib	D (1)	D (3)	
200184	75346	Penpont Farm	Amble	D (2)		

Salmon were absent at the fully quantitative survey at Worthyvale across all years, however, the number of trout fry increased year on year from 2023 to 2025 (Table 4.6).

Table 5.4 Fully-quantitative salmonid results for Worthyvale, River Camel 2023-2025

Camel - Worthyvale	2023	2024	2025
Salmon Fry Classification	F (0)	F (0)	F (0)
Trout Fry Classification	C (10.23)	B (18.89)	B (37.20)
Salmon Parr	F (0)	F (0)	F (0)
Trout Parr	B (13.92)	B (14.66)	B (13.90)

KPI 20.3: Historic Water Quality Assessments from Existing Datasets

An assessment of the Environment Agency’s WIMS data (EA WIMS) was undertaken to understand what data already exists for the demonstrator catchments and to use it as a basis for designing further monitoring around the interventions. Analyses of the data primarily aimed to:

1. Establish the historical (available from 2000 onwards) spatial and temporal distribution of EA routine sampling points for water quality across each demonstrator catchment
2. Derive statistical information on the basic water quality parameters electrical conductivity, turbidity, temperature and nutrients (orthophosphate, reactive as P) from EA sites nearest to interventions to augment WRT’s baseline (pre-intervention) dataset, if available.

Spatial and Temporal Distribution of EA Routine Water Quality Spot Data

Spatial and temporal analysis using GIS confirmed that relying solely on the EA’s data for assessing intervention effectiveness would not be sufficient. Their site locations and measured parameters differed from year to year and as interventions implemented under the project were to be relatively small-scale and static, this justified the extra, more focused monitoring undertaken by WRT as part of KPI 20.4. Approximately 20 sites across each catchment was selected for monitoring on a monthly basis which was used as part of a number of tools to inform selection of intervention sites.

KPI 20.4 Longitudinal Water Quality Monitoring Programme

Axe Catchment – Water quality summary

A total of 636 spot surveys were completed in the Axe catchment. The ranked waterbodies (Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2) clearly show the Lower Axe (Kilmington) as performing worst overall, likely due to the location immediately downstream of the Kilmington sewage treatment works (STW). All measured WQ parameters at this site scored in the top 70% of rankings and the Kilmington site was closely followed by many of the sub catchments on the Yarty waterbody. The middle reaches of the Yarty scored particularly

highly for phosphate (33-37) and electrical conductivity (31-35) and relatively poorly for turbidity (24-34). Two sites on the Kit Brook then followed in terms of overall rankings with the Millhouse Farm at Hook (site 23) scoring the worst for the whole Axe catchment for phosphate. As the interventions to be delivered by WRT under the project were not compatible with tackling pollution issues generated by STWs and the Yarty was already receiving increased attention by the Environment Agency under the Triple Axe Project, WRT focused efforts on engaging landowners in the Kit Brook catchment (site number 4 and upstream), guided by the longitudinal water quality sampling campaigns as well as by which landowners were receptive to land use change.

Figure 5.1 Water quality scorecard for the Axe catchment sampling.

Site Number	River/Stream	Site name	EC	COL	TURB	PO4	OVERALL
13	Axe	Kilmington	19	18	21	22	20
2	Axe	Axe Bridge, Colyford	17	14	12	21	16
16	Kit Brook	Millhouse Farm, Hook	23	9	7	24	16
20	Kit Brook	Wambrook Church Field (u/s STW)	2	21	20	18	15
23	Axe	Whitford Bridge	10	16	17	17	15
3	Axe	Axe Bridge, Wadbrook	18	11	10	19	15
5	Axe	Bow Bridge	14	13	16	14	14
11	Axe	Forde Bridge	11	17	19	10	14
9	Blackwater	Damas Lawn Bridge	5	23	24	3	14
22	Axe	Westford Mills (R.Axe)	21	8	9	16	14
17	Kit Brook	Narforde	6	22	23	2	13
15	Corry Brook	Millgreen Farm	4	20	22	6	13
19	Kit Brook	Wambrook	1	19	18	13	13
12	Kit Brook	Fordwater Farm	15	7	13	15	13
14	Kit Brook	Kit Bridge	22	3	3	20	12
18	Synderford	Shedrick Bridge	7	15	14	12	12
21	Forton Brook	Westford Mills (Forton Brook)	13	4	6	23	12
8	Corry Brook	Dalwood Bridge	3	24	15	1	11
1	Whatley Brook	Ammerham Bridge	20	5	4	11	10
24	Yarty	Yarty Bridge	9	10	8	9	9
10	Kit Brook	Farway Farm	8	12	11	4	9
7	Forton Brook	Coombses	24	1	2	7	9
4	Kit Brook	Axe Farm	12	6	5	8	8
6	Kit Brook	Chardstock Court	16	2	1	5	6

Figure 5.2 Water quality scorecard map for the Axe catchment sampling. Numbers correspond to the named waterbodies in Figure 2.16.

Camel Catchment water quality summary

The Camel spot sampling campaign (503 surveys) highlighted the River Allen as particularly problematic (Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4) with pollutants accumulating down the catchment. This guided the implementation of NBS works at Trethick Farm (site 50 in 51) and Penvose Campsite (site 11 in Figure 53) on tributaries of the R. Allen. As landowner support was positive at these sites and interventions could be delivered without the requirement for nutrient credits (described in Section 3), this outweighed pursuit of intervention works in other poorer performing areas with respect to water quality. The need to find demonstration sites was a priority in order to enable exploration of the benefits of NBS and promote engagement by neighboring landowners with future projects to increase resilience.

Figure 5.3 Water quality scorecard for the Camel catchment sampling

Site Number	River/Stream	Site name	EC	COL	TURB	PO4	OVERALL
16	Allen	Sladesbridge	25	27	27	19	24.5
5	Allen	Kellygreen Bridge	23	25	23	26	24.3
3	Allen	Dinham's Bridge	24	26	26	16	23.0
14	Trenarlet Farm Stream	Poley's Bridge - Trib	26	24	16	24	22.5
2	Allen	Cornish Rock Gin Bridge	17	17	25	18	19.3
9	St Lawrence Stream	Nanstallon WwTW	18	20	24	12	18.5
10	Allen	Newhall Green	15	14	19	21	17.3
15	Ruthern	Ruthernbridge	21	23	22	1	16.8
27	Allen Trib	Whitewell	9	12	17	27	16.3
20	Camel Trib	Tresarrett- Mill Stream	10	16	14	23	15.8
1	Camel	Boscarne Junction	13	19	9	14	13.8
12	Camel	Polbrock Bridge - Bishops Wood	12	18	15	10	13.8
8	Lanivet Stream	Nanstallon Church	22	2	21	9	13.5
21	Allen Trethick Farm Stream	Trethick Farm 1	14	13	5	22	13.5
23	Allen Trethick Farm Stream	Trethick Farm 3 Tregallon	19	8	20	5	13.0
18	Allen	Trehannick Saw Mill	8	5	18	20	12.8
22	Allen Trethick Farm Stream	Trethick Farm 2	20	10	13	7	12.5
11	Allen Trib	Penvose Camping Down	27	6	11	3	11.8
19	Camel	Tresarrett- Camel	2	22	12	8	11.0
6	Allen	Knightsmill Bridge	16	4	7	15	10.5
26	Camel	Wenfordbridge- Camel	3	15	10	13	10.3
13	Camel	Poley's Bridge - Camel	11	9	8	11	9.8
4	Camel Trib	Hametethy Farm D/s	1	21	6	6	8.5
25	Camel	Waterland	4	1	1	25	7.8
7	Allen Trib	Lanteglos	7	3	3	17	7.5
24	Allen Trib	Trewen Bridge	6	11	4	4	6.3
17	Camel	Slaughterbridge Ford	5	7	2	2	4.0

Figure 5.4 Water quality scorecard for the Camel catchment sampling. Numbers correspond to the named waterbodies in 51

Summary of Water Quality Monitoring of Solutions

Initial qualitative monitoring of the various interventions showed them withstanding storm events and functioning as they were designed (at least in the short term) in terms of backing up water to slow flows and beginning to settle out and entrap sediment behind or within it. The small amount of pre-intervention baseline data made quantification of intervention effectiveness extremely difficult if not impossible. Where baseline data was adequate, no significant differences were found in water quality pre vs. post intervention instalment at any of the study sites, although the relatively short duration of the monitoring period, various changes to original proposed intervention plans and the very small density of interventions implemented meant that even a greatly improved monitoring regime would still have made a robust, fully quantitative assessment challenging. In a study attempting to quantitatively evaluate the impact of interventions at a catchment scale, Grand-Clemet et al., (2021) estimated approximately 0.5% total phosphorus removal at a catchment scale using NBS and Farmscoper modelling. Combining all this with the relatively large margins of instrument uncertainty that WRT's analytical equipment offers, it is not surprising that capturing reductions in water quality outside of modelled predictions was largely unachievable.

It is for this reason also that modelled approaches are the standard means by which councils and/or developers assess nutrient neutrality. Currently, in the UK, there is no requirement for nutrient offsetting to be quantified through water/sediment monitoring at the intervention site. The monitoring undertaken in the following sections does, however, provides some preliminary data which can be shared with landowners and used to engage neighbouring farmers who may be considering implementing NBS on their land.

Water Quality Monitoring

Axe Catchment - Chubbs Farm

Initial qualitative monitoring of the Chubbs Farm interventions showed them withstanding storm events, backing up water and beginning to settle out and entrap sediment behind the uppermost dam. Higher than average flows observed on 23/11/24 (31mm of rain) and 26/01/2025 (40mm of rain) did not appear to alter the shape of or dislodge the leaky dams.

However, no statistically significant differences in any of the quantitative WQ data taken pre and post interventions were found. The results of the tests (Welch's t-test and Mann-Whitney U tests) are displayed in Table 21. In every case, $p > 0.05$ for both tests and the means were similar pre vs post at each site. The interventions therefore did not produce a statistically significant change in phosphate concentrations at any location along the intervention cascade. This is unsurprising as the number of samples used to investigate this effect is small and lacks the kind of timeframe required for measurable reductions to be realized.

Table 5.5 Results of the Mann-Whitney U test and Welch's t-test performed on the spot readings for phosphate taken before and after intervention installation. Location numbers correspond with those in Figure 5.4.

Location	n PRE	n POST	PO ₄ concentration (mg/L)		t-test p	Mann-Whitney p
			Mean PRE	Mean POST		
4. Chubbs DS	8	11	0.59	0.60	0.91	0.71
3. Chubbs US of interventions	8	8	0.63	0.72	0.59	0.64
1. Chubbs Stream US confluence	8	9	0.26	0.29	0.72	0.56
2. Alston Stream trib	8	9	1.10	1.30	0.67	0.63

The results show that the Alston Farm tributary (site 2 in Figure 54), which drains run-off from the neighboring farm, contained much higher concentrations of phosphate on average (1.21mg/L) than the stream directly draining Chubbs Farm (0.27mg/L). In particular, two incidents occurring in the absence of rainfall ([EA Hydrology Data Explorer](#)) saw particularly elevated phosphate concentrations (> 1mg/L) during the September and December 2024 sample campaigns (Figure 53). Despite no statistical significance in WQ improvements due to the interventions found using spot sampling, the data did inform where to deploy continuous monitors at a later date to look at WQ in greater detail. It also highlighted the difficulties in accurately determining or isolating nutrient inputs from a single farm to a watercourse, even in the headwaters of small streams such as these. Thus, there is the possibility that farmers may be mitigating nutrients from neighboring farms on their land, or other sources altogether (such as STW or domestic discharges).

Figure 5.5 Concentrations of phosphate observed during the September and December sampling campaigns at the four sites at Chubbs Farm.

Continuous Water Quality Monitoring- Chubbs, Axe Catchment

In December 2024, a number of continuous water quality loggers were deployed, including a phosphate monitor (Dropsens, South West Sensors), at Chubbs Farm at the base of the intervention features in order to collect data at much higher resolution than could be achieved using monthly spot sampling visits. Due to technical issues relating to solar-powered battery recharge and telemetry failures, data was not acquired until the afternoon of 10/02/2025 and the instrument ceased transmitting data due to a hardware fault on 20/04/2025. For the duration the probe was installed and functioning however, the data was generally good, despite the challenging environment in which it was installed (narrow stream, wooded stretch limiting solar battery recharge).

The data show no apparent trends between changes in conductivity with phosphate concentrations, although both spike to some degree with rainfall (Figure 5.6-5.7). Significant increases in P concentration tend to be associated with the heavier rainfall periods, whereas conductivity significantly increased with the lighter rainfall events occurring on the 21st March, and the 3rd and 4th April also (Figure 5.7). The relative change in conductivity values from baseline do appear to decrease with distance downstream, although it is unclear if this is as a result of the interventions or a natural decrease in concentration (due to dilution) with distance from the source. Such an observation highlights the complexities of trying to measure inputs of diffuse pollution and the requirement for a sufficient baseline monitoring period.

Figure 5.6 Timeseries phosphate data (purple) from the SWS monitor deployed downstream at Chubbs Farm with rainfall (grey) and downstream conductivity (blue).

Figure 5.7 Timeseries electrical conductivity data from the AT200 sensors at Chubbs Farm. Green = 2. Alston Stream Trib, Yellow = 3. Upstream of interventions, Grey = Downstream of interventions

Catchment - Snowdon Farm

Snowdon Farm interventions were monitored at an ephemeral stream 1.5km downstream due to features being offline (not connected to a permanent water source). These features are fed from overland flow and an ephemeral stream. Water flowing out of the features moves through the next field as overland flow rather than into a permanent waterbody. Due to the ephemeral nature of the outflow, only five baseline surveys and four post intervention surveys were taken (Table 5.6). Both datasets show fluctuations in water quality throughout the monitoring period due to rainfall events and seasonal trends, but no significant difference was found between conductivity or turbidity pre vs. post intervention installation, and a small increase in phosphate was observed after interventions were installed. However, the dataset is too small to identify robust trends. More sampling over a much longer timeframe (including more pre-intervention data) would be required to identify long term improvements in water quality exerted by the interventions.

Table 5.6 Snowdon Farm water quality spot sampling results pre and post interventions

Sampling date	Electrical Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)		Turbidity (FAU)		Phosphate (mg/L)	
	Pre-Intervention	Post-intervention	Pre-Intervention	Post-intervention	Pre-Intervention	Post-intervention
08/03/2024	182		3		0.18	
19/04/2024	190		5		0.12	
17/05/2024	213		5		0.11	
25/10/2024	186		9		0.28	
20/10/2023	198		5		0.17	
02/12/2024		194		4		0.22
13/01/2025		191		3		0.23
10/02/2025		193		4		0.22
14/03/2025		191		6		0.17
Mean	194	192	5	4	0.17	0.21
Median	190	192	5	4	0.17	0.22

Camel Catchment - Trethick

Trethick stream water quality was monitored downstream of the interventions only, due to poor upstream access and because features are fed from overland flow and track runoff which flows ephemerally. Due to the paucity of baseline data (n=2), it is not possible to identify significant improvements due to the interventions. Sampling of the water captured by the scrapes was completed by taking water samples from them in both 'dry' conditions (i.e. with little to no rain in the last 2 weeks) and following a rainfall event. Sampling occurred 20 months after the interventions were installed to allow time for the features to establish. The lower three scrapes were sampled (Figure 5.7), numbered 1-3 from the hedge line into the field (west to east). The remaining scrapes had too little or no water in

them to get a representative sample. Scrape 1 had the highest average for all parameters observed, presumably due to this scrape being directly below the main entrance where runoff flows into the field. Scrape 1 clearly captured the bulk of the nutrient-rich run-off, indicating the feature was at least functioning as intended. Further monitoring over a longer timeframe would identify longer-term functionality.

Figure 5.8 Water quality results from scrapes on Trethick Farm

Camel Catchment - Penvose

Penvose was spot sampled directly upstream and downstream of interventions with 2 samples being collected before and 20 after interventions were put in place. Due to such a low number of pre-intervention samples, upstream and downstream results were compared post installation rather than before and after interventions were installed. No statistically significant differences in water quality were found upstream and downstream of the leaky dams (parametric paired t-test, $t = 0.856$, $p = 0.403$) and a Wilcoxon signed-rank test (non-parametric, more robust for non-normal data, $W = 75.0$, $p = 0.647$). A Cohen's d (paired samples) test gave an effect size of -0.19, meaning there was a *very small effect*, which slightly favoured higher upstream concentrations. A Wilcoxon effect size r gave -0.25, also indicating a *small effect size*. This also suggested upstream values were a little higher, but the difference is weak and not enough to be meaningful in practice. The leaky dams at this site were eventually dislodged during a storm event and washed away completely.

Continuous Water Quality Monitoring-Penvose, Camel Catchment

Sonde data at Penvose demonstrated fluctuating level and conductivity measurements throughout deployment in response to rainfall but no statistical differences in conductivities or any evidence of a reduction in flood peak timings between up and downstream locations were found. Despite the leaky dams being dislodged by high flows shortly after monitoring was installed, a large debris dam that had accumulated naturally on the tributary continued to function as NBS by backing up water and encouraging overspill into the neighbouring woodland. Observational evidence of sediment deposited along here, with an obvious reduction in flow velocity gave at least anecdotal evidence of the kind of

improvements that NBS aim to make to flows, sediment loads and surrounding habitat diversity. With these kinds of mechanisms encouraged within a river, a reduction in erosion risk downstream, as well as a reduction in downstream flood peaks would be expected given an appropriate density of interventions within a given catchment area. These kinds of brush or log-jam style dams would also be expected to reduce nutrients through sediment settling, floodplain reconnection (and therefore entrapment or uptake of nutrients by soils and vegetation). On January 26th 2025, this dam was also dislodged, apparent from a significant drop in daily average depth.

KPI 20.5 Modelling of KGs of phosphate removed as a proxy of water quality.

Axe – Snowdon Hill

SCALGO determined the area immediately upstream of the ditch's discharge point into the new sediment traps, scrapes and bunds to be 0.59km² (59ha). The following assumptions were made when calculating P removal using the method outlined in CIRIA's "Using SuDS to reduce phosphorous in surface water runoff" (Bradley et al. 2022, available here: <https://www.darlington.gov.uk/media/xr0l1pcx/ciria-report-c815-using-suds-to-reduce-nitrogen.pdf>)

- The site chosen at Snowdon Hill farm has predominantly free draining soils, despite the watershed above which provides the run-off, having impeded drainage.
- The possible P capture mechanisms at the site were:
 - Slow the runoff flow
 - Infiltration into the ground
 - Absorption in soil horizons
 - Uptake by plants
 - Sedimentation on soil surface and leaf surface

By using the Swales methodology and assuming that Snowdon Hill will have the most effect upon the particulate P removal the following calculations regarding the effectiveness of the site interventions were:

Total P entering the site per year from watershed above = 31.43 kg TP/yr

Particulate removal 28% (55% TP in sediment and sediment removal in a swale is assigned and index of 0.5 in CIRIA C753, so 55% of 50% = 28%)

Total removed 28% of 31.43 TP/yr = 8.80 kg TP/yr

Camel

Phosphate removed on the River Camel sites was calculated using the River Camel SAC nutrient neutrality calculator (available [here](#)). The habitat examples available are limited so conversion to 'greenspace' was used as a proxy for the habitat restoration works. The calculator has an option to record Sustainable Urban Drainage System (SuDS) features but, due to the small inputs involved, these had no impact on the result.

The calculator estimated the scrape site at Trethick to reduce total phosphorus generated by that parcel by 0.51kg/yr. The site was unusual in being on a small area of naturally wet soil in the catchment, whereas elsewhere it is freely draining.

The Penvose site, including scrapes and a pond, reduced TP by 0.11kg/yr, compared to the original land use of lowland grazing.

KPI 20.6 Measure the depth/volume of sediment captured by the intervention

Estimated sediment volumes captured by different types of interventions are given in Table 5.7.

Table 5.7 Estimated captured sediment volumes

		Estimated total potential volume (m ³)	Average sediment depth (m)	Estimated sediment volume (m ³)
Chubbs Farm (sample taken 104 days after instalment)	Leaky dam 1	-	0.089	6.16
Snowdon Farm (sample taken 108 days after instalment)	Scrape 1	111.43	0.015	2.64
	Scrape 2	139.85	0.010	2.40
	Scrape 3	148.00	0.010	2.40
	Scrape 4	99.13	0.025	4.96
	Scrape 5	129.32	0.010	1.99
Trethick Farm (sample taken 245 days after instalment)	Sediment trap	3.68	0.230	3.68
	Scrape 1	15.08	0.030	1.13
	Scrape 2	8.82	0.010	0.22
	Scrape 3	20.80	0.010	0.42
	Scrape 4	7.35	0.000	0.00
	Scrape 5	7.72	0.000	0.00

Axe- Snowdon Hill Farm

Sediment had begun to accumulate in each of the scrapes 108 days after Snowdon Farm interventions were installed. The largest volume of sediment and the highest concentration of phosphate (91mgL⁻¹) was observed in scrape 4 and this is most likely due to the features not being connected to the ephemeral stream via the sediment trap at the time of sampling, leading to scrape 1. This probably led to storm water diverting itself around scrapes 1-3 and instead flowing into scrape 4 and 5. Once all features are brought online and the sediment trap is connected, further studies should be undertaken.

Camel -Trethick Farm

At Trethick Farm, four out of six features have successfully trapped sediment after 245 days, reducing the input of sediment and associated nutrients to the downstream watercourse, with the sediment trap capturing over 3m³. The first sediment trap adjacent to the track was completely filled. However, due to the protracted period of operation before monitoring commenced (1 year), it is unclear how quickly this filled. From observational data, it was clear that the rough ground at the top of the field was also helping to trap sediment and associated nutrients (similar to how a buffer strip is expected to perform), this was, however, difficult to quantify.

KPI 20.7 Measure the nutrient content of the sediments via laboratory analysis

Nutrient samples were taken at Snowdon and Trethick Farms after initial instalment. These samples of soil/sediment were taken from the water retention features primarily in the form of scrapes or sediment traps. These samples were then analyzed using standard laboratory analysis (<https://cawood.co.uk/nrm/>).

The nutrient results (Table 5.8) from the sites are outlined below including the Soil Organic Matter (SOM) levels, which is a proxy for the amount of Carbon and organic material within the soil. It is difficult to draw any specific conclusions from this data, but a brief analysis is given below.

Table 5.8 Concentrations of nutrients within the sediment samples.

		pH index	mg L ⁻¹ available element			% Loss on ignition
			P	K	Mg	SOM
Snowdon Farm (sample taken 108 days after instalment)	Scrape 1	6.6	16	201	155	8.3
	Scrape 2	6.8	29.8	296	151	10.5
	Scrape 3	7.2	48.2	374	145	13.3
	Scrape 4	7.8	91	740	140	16
	Scrape 5	7.6	71.6	626	156	13.9
Trethick Farm (sample taken 245 days after instalment)	Sediment trap	7.7	28.4	185	63	3.7
	Scrape 2	6.9	13.8	120	57	5.5

Axe - Snowdon Farm

This system was designed to slow the flow and settle out sediments, leading to the accumulation of sediment-bound phosphorus. Measured plant available phosphorous concentrations increased away from the input source in a series of settlement capture scrapes, until scrape five where there was a small decline in P levels (Table 24). Furthermore, biological activity within the sediment can bind phosphorus. The longer water is held, the more time there is for these P-binding processes to occur, increasing the labile (available) phosphorus in the sediment pool further from the input. It is important to note here that these results are from initial sediment samples that had entered the scrape system, before the two sediment capture pits had been completed and had the opportunity to intercept P from initial sediment deposition. This indicates that some nutrients are accumulating within the scrapes, reducing inputs to the river.

Camel - Trethick Farm

In total the sediment trap removed 105g of available phosphorus (roughly equating to 321g of phosphate). When comparing the concentration of nutrients in the top sediment trap with those measured within the scrapes at the bottom of the field, P, K and Mg all decreased.

KPI 20.8 Measure Soil Permeability/Compaction/Infiltration Rate Using VESS Assessment

Soil permeability and structure/compaction was reviewed as part of the monitoring of sites. VESS analysis (<https://ahdb.org.uk/knowledge-library/how-to-assess-soil-structure>) was undertaken as a standardised method to assess and quantify where possible soil structure. Table 5.9 gives the score per field, soil pit and layer (1 indicated good friable soils structure, with 4 indicating compacted/poor soil).

Table 5.9 Soil VESS scores

Site	Field	Total Depth (cm)	Earth-worm Count	Layer 1		Layer 2		Layer 3		Overall VESS Score
				Depth (cm)	Score	Depth (cm)	Score	Depth (cm)	Score	
Snowdon Farm intervention field	Pit 1	25	0	10	2.5	5	3	10	2	2.4
	Pit 2	25	6	10	2.5	10	2.5	5	2	2.4
	Pit 3	25	9	10	2.5	10	2	5	1.5	2.1
Snowdon Farm conventional field	Pit 1	25	5	10	3	10	2.5	5	2	2.6
	Pit 2	25	3	5	3.5	10	2.5	10	2	2.5
	Pit 3	25	4	10	3	10	2	5	2	2.4
Trethick intervention field	Pit 1	25	6	5	1	10	2.5	10	2	2
	Pit 2	25	5	5	2.5	10	3	10	2	2.5
	Pit 3	25	8	10	1	10	2	5	1.5	1.5

Snowdon Hill

VESS scores for Snowdon Hill Farm were marginally better in the intervention field (averaging 2.3) than the conventional field (averaging 2.5). Whilst this is early in the site development the reduced intensity on the intervention part of the field, compared to the more intensive arable section, means the soils are likely to improve further. That said the VESS score improvement does rely on the soils being given a sufficient break between grazing/management to recover any damage caused.

VESS analysis gives scores for the various soil horizons found within the soil profile layers, which is then averaged for the whole profile. Thus, if a soil has a small (<1cm) layer of capping at the surface (or in isolation within the profile), but the rest of the soil is good, the average for the 40cm profile will be excellent, but the reality from a water infiltration point of view can be much different. VESS is a good method for overall soil profile health and structure but does need some caveats when being used as an indicator of water infiltration capabilities.

In the intervention half of the field, the soil around the sediment pits had a good groundcover of vegetation with few bare patches. Root penetration depth ranged from 10-15cm. The first 0-10cm of the topsoil showed signs of compaction in the form of hardened soil that was difficult to break, and when broken composed of angular shards (some partially rounded) with minimal root penetration past these layers. To the west at the lowest end of the field, the ground was much wetter with a thin layer of standing water. Here the 0-10cm layer was wet and showed signs of compaction, with some grey coloring, indicating that this layer is often saturated with water.

In comparison, the lower layers (~10/15–20/25cm) had a good soil structure with minimal compaction signs, though some did display mild compaction in some areas. Earthworms were present in this field showing that there was a good soil structure beneath the compacted layers.

This trend is typical for livestock grazing and indicates compaction in the top layers due to poaching. Cattle tend to compact soils to around 10cms, whilst sheep usually cause problems in the top 2.5cms. A flock of sheep were present grazing both halves as one field.

In the conventional half of the field, the soil had a medium/sparse top groundcover of vegetation with many patches of hard, bare ground portraying desiccation cracks on the surface. Root penetration depth ranged from 5-6cm. It was observed that this half of the field had a higher stone content in comparison to the intervention half.

The first 0-10cm of the topsoil showed visible signs of compaction, with the soil being hard and taking considerable effort to break. The soil was also compacted around stones, and when broken consisted of angular shards (some partially rounded).

In comparison, the lower layers (~10-20cm) showed marginal signs of continued compaction that lessened with depth. Earthworms were present in this field showing that there was generally a good soil structure beneath the compacted layers.

This trend is typical for livestock grazing and indicates compaction in the top layers due to poaching.

If this compaction can be remediated, the free draining nature of the farm soils should naturally let more water infiltrate. This means that there may be less run-off during the winter, more grass growth during the summer and a longer season for grazing.

Trethick

VESS scores at Trethick Farm varied significantly across the field containing the interventions. This is potentially due to the weight of the machinery where excavation work was undertaken, historic compaction e.g. from cattle or feeding troughs. Two of the pits had good surface structure, suggesting that there has been a period of time for the upper layer of soil to recover, with improved structure. The ecology report identified a longer sward (grass height) in the intervention field. Over time this will help to improve soil structure as these taller plants will have a deeper rooting profile, which will break up compaction over time. In time this will also improve the infiltration of water and slow the surface movement of water.

KPI 20.9 Measuring the Amount of Organic Matter in the Soil and the Carbon:Nitrogen Ratio to Assess Soil Carbon Sequestration Performance

Regarding nutrients at Snowdon Hill Farm (Table 5.9), concentrations of P, K and Mg were significantly higher within the conventional field compared to the intervention field. Part of this change will be due to the reduction in intensive agriculture, meaning reduced nutrient applications.

Table 5.9 Soil Organic matter results for Snowdon Hill Farm

Field Details	Soil pH	P	K	Mg	P	K	Mg	Soil Organic Matter
		Index			mg L ⁻¹ (Available)			[LOI%] Result
Conventional field	6.6	4	3	4	48.8	342	190	9
Intervention field outside of scrape features	6.3	3	2+	4	26.8	183	180	8.4
Scrape 1 accumulated sediment	6.6	2	2+	3	16	201	155	8.3
Scrape 2 accumulated sediment	6.8	3	3	3	29.8	296	151	10.5
Scrape 3 accumulated sediment	7.2	4	3	3	48.2	374	145	13.3
Scrape 4 accumulated sediment	7.8	5	5	3	91	740	140	16
Scrape 5 accumulated sediment	7.6	5	5	3	71.6	626	156	13.9

It is challenging to draw any detailed conclusions from the Trethick site given the data set (Table 5.10), however there can be some comparisons between the field and the scrapes. The intervention field has a suitable level of nutrients at index 2 for P and K and a good/target level of SOM, indicating that the field has been down to grassland for some time. The sediment trap has slightly higher P concentrations which may represent nutrient trapped by the feature from sediment and manure run-off. Both the sediment trap and scrape have a lower SOM. This material is comprised of fine-grained run-off sediment, in comparison to the much richer neighboring topsoil. Carbon would be expected to increase in the features as the depth of sediment builds up over time, if not cleared out.

Carbon sequestration was not directly measured within the intervention sites; however, soil organic matter (SOM) content is a key indicator. The conventional field had higher SOM potentially due to application of manure as fertiliser. The organic matter (OM) content follows a similar format to that of the P concentrations (KPI 20.7). The lighter OM held within the water flow is deposited as water is slowed and passes through the drainage system. This carbon deposition will be held and processed by the soil biological activity. Subject to aeration and time between deposition and removal of deposited sediment, labile carbon will be available for biological uptake and/or transformation. Some will be stored in stable carbon deposits.

Table 5.10 Trethick Farm nutrient results

Field Details	Soil pH	P	K	Mg	P	K	Mg	Soil Organic Matter
		Index			mg/l (Available)			[LOI%] Result
Trethick intervention field	6.2	2	2+	2	18.4	202	94	8.3
Trethick Sediment trap accumulated sediment	7.7	3	2+	2	28.4	185	63	3.7

Trethick sediment	scrape	2	accumulated	6.9	1	1	2	13.8	120	57	5.5
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5.2.2 New Information on Bankability

Overview

Upscaling and accelerating the solution in the Westcountry region has mixed prospects looking forward. Through the formation of nutrient credits and the need for nutrient neutrality in certain catchments, upscaling in these areas has a financial pathway and is likely to be expanded and built upon. This is due to the legislative need to offset housing development and therefore the costing/investment will need to be embedded within the cost of construction by developers and following the sale of property. For the Camel and the Axe, this provides an ongoing opportunity over the coming years.

Bankability review

To assess the extent to which NBS such as ponds, scrapes, leaky dams and wetland restoration currently present an investable proposition to private companies, WRT staff undertook a series of semi-structured interviews with relevant actors across the green finance sector. Participants in the bankability interviews identified 49 barriers currently preventing investment in NBS implementation for climate adaptation and 26 potential solutions. TransformAr project partners divided the barriers and solutions into six key categories (public sector governance, private sector governance, economic, skills & knowledge, socio-cultural, and physical capital). Then, it was prioritized using a decision-support matrix based on the following weighted criteria: scale, complexity, and consensus. Key barriers identified included:

- Lack of high-quality data to prove that Nature-based Solutions perform well enough to make investment decisions at business board level.
- Novelty of nature markets mean investor confidence is low
- Suspicion of green finance schemes in the farming sector
- Poor understanding of demand outside of legislated markets (e.g. legally enforced nutrient offsets)
- Disconnection between different sectors and industries divides efforts to create viable projects
- Private profit models inherently lead to sub-optimal outcomes for nature
- Lack of multi-value decision-making frameworks
- Investable/bankable proposition for private companies operating within traditional finance models

Ultimately, research concluded that Nature-based Solutions do not always meet the threshold for investment by business or investors, given the uncertainty of return in some instances. Participants produced 14 clear calls for action to improve the viability of green finance schemes. Participants reported that, at present, the most viable models for investing in Nature-based Solutions are non-profit models, such as a Community Interest Company or Special Purpose Vehicle. This result highlights the importance of researching the bankability of Nature-based Solutions at sub-national scale, as, whilst some barriers were consistent with international consensus, others were specific to the green finance context of the Westcountry region.

Investors usually focus on the UK’s urban centres, leaving the Westcountry with lower investment levels. The Southwest’s economy is worth about £81.6 billion (€97.1 billion), compared to London’s £562 billion (€669 billion). To attract traditional investors, ecosystem services – like carbon storage or water supply – must generate clear, reliable revenue streams. However, the region, although highly dependent on these services for economic stability, has not yet established large-scale valuations. This lack of clear value makes banks and financial institutions hesitant to invest in expensive, nature-based climate adaptation projects. However, individual companies at the local level often recognize their reliance on specific ecosystem services to keep their businesses running or to manage climate risks. These companies might invest smaller amounts, and if they pool their investments, they could finance large-scale Nature-based Solutions. Each company would then receive a share of the benefits, such as carbon credits or improved water supply, along with extra gains like enhanced reputation or better business performance. Interview participants supported this shared investment approach, as it limits the risk of companies exploiting the environment purely for profit.

In the UK the Green Finance Institute has developed an investment readiness Toolkit (Figure 5.9), which outlines the process from start to finish and is a useful reference for the investment process and requirements. This highlights the important role of governance structure and the legal contracts for green investment which are still early in development and require time to establish.

The **Green Finance Institute’s Investment Readiness Toolkit** provides a step-by-step framework for developing investible nature-based projects, covering eight milestones from scoping to legal contracts. It offers checklists, case studies, and guidance relevant for ecosystem service projects. (see <https://hive.greenfinanceinstitute.com/gfihive/toolkit/>)

Figure 5.9 Investment Readiness Toolkit, Green Finance Institute

Summary

In order to accelerate investment in Nature-based Solutions for climate change adaptation in low investment regions, it is highly important to research the bankability of these solutions with regional actors. Whilst large, international investors may have certain requirements for viable projects (e.g. clear revenue flows, consistent rate of return over long time periods, etc.), smaller companies may consider payment for discrete outcomes, such as reduced flood risk/increased drought resilience, as a viable investment as these could directly impact business resilience going forward. Water and other utility companies in the UK regions are also being asked by the regulator to use a 'Green First' approach ([SWW Green First Framework](#)) when it comes to tackling issues such as waste water network flooding and water quality issues, which will increase the scale of NBS delivery over the next 5 years significantly and help to bring about wider adoption, in a sector that has previously focused on engineering solutions for some time.

As such, alternative funding/finance mechanisms can be viable in the immediate term. In the Westcountry region, actors expressed preference for blended finance models, such as the establishment of a community interest company, to drive forward investment in, and delivery of, Nature-based Solutions. This model prevents profiteering, securing high-quality environmental outcomes, whilst also delivering the desired return on investment.

5.2.3 Comparative Results

As reviewed in section 6.2.2 there are three main areas where a successful nutrient neutrality scheme would have positive impacts. These are: Environmental improvements within the selected sensitive catchments; Economic benefits both to communities from unlocking development and providing alternative income for farmers and land managers; Social benefits of increasing engagement and understanding of rivers and ecosystems, including threats and resilience.

Environmental improvements

As outlined in the sections above, getting detailed or accurate data around NBS can be challenging, particularly when dealing with ephemeral or seasonal flow pathways from upstream. When there is a regular input flow to a NBS and a defined outlet, more robust or physical data can be collected. For the majority of the WRT interventions a hybrid set of measures were utilized, including WQ samples, sediment samples, ecology and fisheries measurements, drone footage along with nutrient modelling tools.

In these scenarios, to gather the multiple and broader benefits of these interventions, a weight of evidence approach is best utilized. By collecting a range of data covering different elements it may be possible to more accurately calculate the wider value/benefit of the NBS.

Overall, the limited time period to collect post intervention data limits our ability to more accurately review the efficiency and capability of the intervention. We can, however, using the modelling tools available such as Farmscoper [ADAS Farmscoper](#) and some of the sediment trapped within interventions, calculate the volume of sediment trapped and P/kg trapped by the interventions. For example, the volume of P kg/year calculated for Snowdon is significant, when considering Nutrient neutrality values and the potential cost per P/kg, which maybe around £15-20k/kg/yr in the Axe catchment for developers and credits.

Economic

The Economic impact of the nutrient trading scheme has not yet been directly delivered or tested on the ground. The underpinning frameworks for contracts and early trading are still under development, with the first credits in the Camel or Axe not yet available. However, both Cornwall Council, responsible for planning in the Camel catchment, and East Devon County Council, responsible in the Axe, have been able to capitalize nutrient neutrality through applying to the Government's Local nutrient mitigation fund [Local-nutrient-mitigation-fund-round-2](#) . Cornwall Council have been able to apply for around £2m and East Devon District Council £4.5m approx. representing a significant investment of around £6.5m in a range of solutions, including constructed wetlands.

As outlined previously, new housing is needed for local people who provide a workforce for sustainable economic growth. Research showed that each £1m investment in housing development supports around 19.9 direct jobs, and 15.6 indirect jobs, as the construction industry has an indirect and induced employment multiplier of 2.23 (Lichfields, 2022).

As outlined previously, when the nutrient credit and offsetting is progressed and trading starts, the following metrics can be used to assess economic impact:

- Value of capitalization (e.g. this is already £6.5m for the Axe and Camel)
- Value of credits traded
- Number of developers/investors and landowners bought into scheme
- Wider value from the multiple benefits of these solutions e.g. biodiversity and slowing water run-off.

Social

Community engagement and awareness raising in the catchments and region has been good with WRT running events directly, adding to existing events and workshops, presenting at existing partnership groups and supporting Westcountry Citizen Science Investigations (CSI) signups. It was estimated that over 5000 people became more resilient through the project, this may be through workshops and partnership meetings, CSI signups, interactions with social media and direct attendance of community events.

Eighty-five actors were involved through the project, which represents significant stakeholder engagement, as many of these actors will be involved in similar activities or have the influence to make changes to their delivery programmed or influence cohorts. Key actors, such as local authorities and water companies were involved early in the project, representing the key stakeholders who are most likely to either capitalize nutrient neutrality, invest, or alter policy so that more NBS can be delivered. The regional water company in the new price review cycle from 2025-2030 are utilizing a 'Green First' approach ([SWW Green First Framework](#)), where NBS needs to be considered as a first option.

The citizen science (CSI) and volunteering activity at the Trust has expanded significantly over the last four years, with a major increase in the number of CSI volunteers along with the number of samples taken. Becoming a CSI volunteer also provides an important communication pathway so that a greater awareness of climate change issues can be communicated along with the benefits of climate change adaptation and the solutions implemented.

5.2.4 Challenges and Mitigations

Changes from ICW and ICWM to on-farm NBS were agreed due to the constraints around land purchases required for ICW, and regulatory issues around the use of ICW on farms to mitigate. However, these solutions primarily manage diffuse inputs from multiple sources, and no changes were made to the expected KPIs for water quality and phosphate reductions, which are much harder to measure for individuals on farm NBS, without a single input source and output point.

There were ongoing challenges and delays around the development of the nutrient credit, and this eventually led to certain sites being delayed beyond the project, such as at Slaughterbridge, which will prove to be an interesting riparian buffer case study, when funded by the Local Authority. Other sites were delayed in their deployment in the project as it was originally planned that they would attract nutrient credit funding for the landowner. Once it was clear that credit payments would not take place within the project period, it was decided that works should start and sites be branded as NBS climate adaptation solutions, more than solely nutrient credit sites.

A new continuous phosphate WQ sensor developed by SouthWestSensor, which has recently become available, was trialed within this project. The DropSens uses wet-chemistry (micro fluidics) and fully automated colorimetric analysis within the probe body using the Molybdenum Blue method and is one of a small number of commercially available sensors for continuous phosphate measurements. The approach planned for the DropletSens™ phosphate probe was deployment downstream ahead of the scheduled interventions at Chubbs Farm. The DropletSens™ monitor was to be paired with other sensors ([WATR](#)) that used direct measurements of standard WQ parameters, such as electrical conductivity and turbidity, to derive phosphate concentrations. These sensors were to be supplied and installed by the North Devon Biosphere Foundation under their [Smart Biosphere](#) project and would be sited in the two feeder streams upstream of the Chubbs Farm interventions as well as directly downstream of the intervention (alongside the DropletSens™ probe). Due to site complications and funding restrictions with WATR sensors, these were not installed during the project timeframe.

In the context of quantitative monitoring to demonstrate the reduction in phosphate as a result of interventions, there was an insufficient monitoring period prior to the NBS installations to use the continuous monitor for this purpose. However, its deployment under the TransformAr project still allowed some important monitoring to be undertaken to ascertain:

- **Equipment suitability.** Meaning the suitability, both theoretically and practically, of the use of the equipment for monitoring NBS on this scale. We were able to demonstrate the successful deployment of the solar-charged equipment in a small, rural stream with relatively poor signal and wooded banksides. This is the first time WRT has implemented continuous monitoring for phosphate (P). Continuous P monitoring is still rarely done across Europe. In the UK, the legal requirements for nutrient neutrality, led to the requirement to better understand P loads in rivers, and thus improved monitoring methods.
- **A continuous timeseries dataset for phosphorus in field conditions.** Once online, the equipment successfully transmitted 15-minute data remotely to an online platform for viewing and analysis.
- **The relative performance of different instrumentation for P analysis.** Using spot sampling for the measurement of phosphate concentrations in parallel with the SWS DropletSens™ monitor allowed cross-validation of datasets to check the two instruments were in good agreement.
- **Any relationships between phosphate concentrations and electrical conductivity** at the Chubbs site. The relationship between these two parameters can vary depending on phosphorus sources and whether it is present as dissolved or bound to particulate material. Simultaneous deployment of electrical conductivity sensors alongside the SWS DropletSens™ probe meant some

investigation into the usefulness and/or validity of using electrical conductivity (a much easier and cheaper WQ parameter to monitor) as a proxy for phosphate in this context.

5.3 Galicia, Spain

5.3.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

KPI 7 – Coastal Ecosystem Resilience: The intertidal monitoring (INTERM) and mussel raft monitoring (MRM) solutions provided new datasets on sediment dynamics, hydrodynamics, and mussel growth, strengthening ecosystem resilience by supporting adaptive shellfish management.

KPI 17 – Participation in Adaptive Governance: The development of the Resilience Index (RI) engaged more than 20 experts and 100+ stakeholders (fishers, policymakers, NGOs, scientists) through Delphi processes and workshops. This participatory approach improved governance capacity and co-created a roadmap with 17 priority adaptation measures for the aquaculture sector.

KPI 20 – Use of Climate Information: Real-time digital dashboards (<https://utmar.cetmar.org/transformar>) provided producers and scientists with access to continuous environmental and production data. The integration of climate risk scenarios into decision-making tools supported more informed aquaculture operations and planning.

5.3.2 New Information on Bankability

Bankability studies demonstrated that the digitalization of aquaculture management (MRM and RI) offers strong long-term value:

- Low-to-moderate operational costs compared to avoided production losses.
- Improved decision-making reduces risks of biomass loss from temperature shifts and detachment events.
- Stakeholder interest in replication (including companies and administration) confirms scalability and potential for financial support from regional funds.

5.3.3 Comparative Results

- **Sensor data:** MRM documented new correlations between environmental variability (e.g. persistent high temperatures) and mussel detachment, providing actionable knowledge for producers.
- **Stakeholder adoption:** >90% of engaged stakeholders reported increased awareness and intent to use RI outputs in decision-making. Producers accessed the digital dashboard at least bi-weekly, showing active integration of climate information into daily management.

5.3.4 Challenges and Mitigations

The monitoring challenges in Galicia are mainly related to harsh sea conditions, which cause sensor corrosion and fouling, as well as the need to adapt to the working conditions of mussel producers.

Mitigation action were frequent site visits, a robust monitoring strategy, and thorough data analysis to clean sensors and manage data, while maintaining close communication with producers to adapt to their needs.

Challenges and mitigation measures are described in detail for each solution in specific reports.

- Briefing on the development process of the Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM) solution and results. <https://zenodo.org/records/13238570>
- Methodology for the development of a climate change resilience index for mussel aquaculture in Galicia (Spain). <https://zenodo.org/records/12800095>
- Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM) in Ría de Arousa (Galicia). Briefing on the development process of the solution and results. <https://zenodo.org/records/13238528>

5.4 Egaleo, Greece

5.4.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

KPI 13 – Social Co-benefits: Green corridors, pocket parks, and urban greening initiatives improved local environmental quality while creating recreational spaces, contributing to well-being and social cohesion.

KPI 18 – Citizen Engagement via Digital Tools: A digital platform and mobile applications were used to engage citizens in reporting urban heat hotspots and co-designing greening interventions, significantly increasing participatory planning uptake.

KPI 21 – Accessibility and Equity in Adaptation: Interventions specifically targeted vulnerable groups, ensuring equitable access to cooling and green spaces in highly urbanised and heat-prone neighbourhoods.

5.4.2 New Information on Bankability

Bankability assessments highlight that digital engagement tools combined with nature-based solutions (NBS) deliver cost-effective outcomes. The low operational cost of the digital platforms contrasted with significant social and health co-benefits, such as reduced heat stress, lower healthcare costs, and improved liveability.

5.4.3 Comparative Results

Community engagement through digital tools exceeded initial assumptions. Participation rates were higher than expected, with citizens actively contributing data and ideas for green interventions. Positive feedback from residents confirmed that digital co-design processes improved both transparency and trust in municipal decision-making.

5.4.4 Challenges and Mitigations

Community-specific challenges: At the start, some residents were skeptical about engaging through digital platforms, which limited participation.

Mitigation: To address this, the project organized face-to-face workshops and community meetings that complemented the online tools, creating a blended engagement approach and fostering trust.

We also reached out to students and let them experiment with sensors and data collection, while also learning about the climate related parameters. An adaptation story is published on Climate-Adapt on the 'improving of climate awareness among Greek students'

<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/mission-stories/improving-climate-awareness-among-greek-students-story73>

Digital adoption barriers: Older residents and socially vulnerable groups often had limited access to digital devices or lacked the necessary skills to use them effectively.

Mitigation: Dedicated training sessions and parallel offline engagement activities were introduced, ensuring equitable participation and inclusiveness across demographics.

Implementation barriers: In densely built urban areas, space constraints restricted the scope for traditional Nature-Based Solutions. NBS was not a demonstrated solution in Egaleo. It is a future project idea covered in the bankability reports.

Mitigation: Innovative design approaches, such as pocket parks, rooftop greening, and multifunctional urban spaces, were co-created with citizens to overcome spatial limitations and ensure integration into the urban fabric.

5.5 Oristano, Italy

5.5.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

KPI 5 – Flood Risk Reduction: The Smart Gate system was designed to improve adaptive water management in lagoon and coastal areas, increasing water quality and regulating the water levels between lagoon and river mouth. Monitoring shows the gates can efficiently regulate water levels, mitigating risk of eutrophication with benefits for fishing and for the wetland ecological status.

KPI 11 – Biodiversity Increase: By improving water quality and maintaining salinity balance in lagoon ecosystems, Smart Gates and related NBS measures support the recovery of biodiversity, particularly for aquatic vegetation and fish species dependent on stable ecological conditions.

KPI 17 – Participation in Adaptive Governance: Local stakeholders, including fisheries cooperatives and municipal authorities, participated in co-creation workshops. This participatory approach strengthened adaptive governance, improving stakeholder ownership and willingness to integrate Smart Gate management into long-term adaptation strategies.

5.5.2 New Information on Bankability

Bankability assessments highlight that Smart Gate technology presents a cost-efficient adaptive measure compared to large-scale grey infrastructure.

Key findings include:

- Operational costs are moderate, as Smart Gates relies on automated regulation with high maintenance needs.
- Benefits include avoided flood damage, preservation of agricultural and fishing productivity, and ecosystem co-benefits (biodiversity, water quality).
- Financing options under consideration include EU cohesion funds, regional adaptation budgets, and private funds.
- Replicability is high in other Mediterranean coastal lagoons facing similar hydrological challenges.

5.5.3 Comparative Results

As a concrete outcome of the COAST project, the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO) has been established, providing the scientific basis to strengthen future policy decisions on lagoon management. Within this framework, six factsheets have already been produced and made available both on the dedicated [LWO webpage](#) and on Zenodo, ensuring open access and wider dissemination. Other factsheets are in the process of being published. In addition, a [geoportal](#) has been created, offering access to regional datasets already published, now integrated with the monitoring data collected through the project's stations. The geoportal also includes, in a reserved section for administrators, the operational control of the Smart Gate, allowing remote management of the gate's opening and closure.

Another key result has been the strong involvement of stakeholders, with 24 participatory meetings organized, the active participation of 44 officers from public authorities, and the engagement of around 170 people in the activities linked to COAST. This broad participation has reinforced the collaborative dimension of the project and laid the groundwork for more inclusive and shared decision-making processes.

The implementation of the TransformAr monitoring and Smart Gate system has already delivered several of the expected benefits. The integrated platform is fully operational and provides real-time data, enabling evidence-based decision-making and improving the effectiveness of water management interventions.

A result of particular significance has been the strong collaboration established with the local fishing sector. Their active engagement went beyond initial expectations, playing a central role in the co-design of activities and in the dissemination of results, thereby strengthening local ownership of the initiative.

A management plan has been developed to ensure post-project sustainability, outlining the maintenance and management activities, the related costs, the timing, and required competencies. This framework is designed to guarantee that the infrastructure remains functional and continues to generate useful data to support decision-making.

Additional progress has been achieved through the mobilization of new resources: the project has catalyzed funding from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), enabling the planned

installation of further Smart Gate units and extending both the spatial coverage and the long-term impact of the Nature-Based Solution.

At the same time, some expected benefits have not yet been fully realized, as the large-scale restoration works are still ongoing and the completion of system calibration is necessary before ecological and hydrological outcomes can be comprehensively assessed. To bridge this gap and ensure continuity, the capitalization of TransformAr's results is being secured through complementary projects: the Interreg PO Marittimo project RICREA, which guarantees the continuity of the Sardinian Wetlands Observatory in collecting, analyzing and sharing data, and the Interreg EuroMed project Wetland4Change, which continues to use and enrich the lagoon monitoring dataset, ensuring that the platform remains operational and capable of generating actionable insights over time.

5.5.4 Challenges and Mitigations

The TransformAr demonstration experience in the Gulf of Oristano provided several valuable lessons for the future design and deployment of monitoring systems in wetland environments:

- **Limited formal involvement of private stakeholders:** although private actors were engaged during the participatory process, this participation did not translate into formal agreements (i.e. private investments). The bankability report aimed to facilitate the involvement of private actors. Yet, a targeted dialogue with key economic sectors (e.g., fisheries, tourism, agriculture) remains needed, in addition to the development of incentive mechanisms to foster stronger private commitment.
- **Administrative changes at municipal and regional level:** political and institutional turnover slowed down the process and created discontinuities in decision-making. Mitigation measures involve maintaining a broad and diverse network of contacts within administrations, ensuring that technical staff and middle management are consistently involved to guarantee continuity, regardless of political cycles.
- **Limited integration of data platforms at regional level:** the coexistence of existing regional platforms and those newly developed by different projects has hindered data harmonization and reduced the usability of information. Mitigation measures include promoting synergies with ongoing initiatives, aligning data standards, and working towards the interoperability of platforms, thereby ensuring a more coherent and integrated system for long-term monitoring and management.
- **Sensor Selection:** The choice of monitoring equipment must consider both the technical specifications and the environmental context. In highly dynamic and saline ecosystems, self-cleaning sensors and deployment in hydrologically stable locations are recommended to ensure long-term functionality and reduce maintenance frequency.
- **Increased costs for Smart Gate construction:** international crises and related market fluctuations led to a significant rise in material and implementation costs, putting at risk the timely completion of the infrastructure. Mitigation was achieved by securing additional funds, which allowed the project to be completed without compromising its expected functionality and objectives.
- **Site accessibility and maintenance of sensors:** The logistical complexity of accessing monitoring points, especially in lagoon environments with limited infrastructure, underlines the need for the direct involvement of the fishermen to ensure long-term maintenance instead of external service providers, which was the initial plan. The daily presence of fishermen in the lagoon allows them

to oversee the equipment, carry out basic maintenance after targeted training, and reduce overall management costs. This outcome not only strengthens the sustainability of the system but also increases local ownership and engagement compared to initial expectations.

- **Emergency Budgeting:** Extreme weather events and unforeseen delays demonstrated the need to allocate additional funds specifically for contingencies, such as sensor replacement, unplanned repairs, or structural reinforcement of installations.
- **Time management:** The experience also showed that project implementation timelines must account for potential delays due to bureaucratic processes, weather conditions, and coordination among multiple actors. Incorporating buffer periods into the work plan is essential for managing expectations and avoiding compressed testing phases.
- **System Integration:** Effective communication between the different components of the infrastructure—sensors, motor type and IT control system of the Smart Gate—requires joint planning from the outset. Ensuring compatibility and interoperability among these elements, through close collaboration between engineers, biologists, and IT specialists, is key to preventing malfunctions and optimizing system performance.
- **Post-project Management:** To guarantee the long-term functionality of the system, technical meetings were organized within TransformAr with the public authorities responsible for lagoon management. The management plan developed during the project still needs to be formally approved, with responsibilities clearly defined and dedicated financial resources secured for future maintenance.

5.6 Guadeloupe Archipelago, France

5.6.1 Summaries of Particular Deliveries (KPI, Bankability, etc.)

KPI 9 – Behavioral Change: Nudging strategies and awareness campaigns improved water-use efficiency and household preparedness for hurricanes. Citizens showed increased willingness to adopt adaptive practices.

KPI 13 – Social Co-benefits: Community workshops fostered stronger collaboration between households, schools, and local NGOs, generating knowledge transfer and improved resilience culture.

KPI 21 – Accessibility and Equity in Adaptation: Engagement ensured inclusion of vulnerable households and women’s associations, widening access to adaptation benefits across the island.

5.6.2 New Information on Bankability

Bankability studies show that nudging and awareness measures are low-cost and high-return interventions. Reports highlight that modest investments in behavioral change campaigns can generate measurable resilience outcomes, making them attractive for replication and integration into public policies.

5.6.3 Comparative Results

Post-intervention assessments revealed results that surpassed initial expectations. Water savings at household level were higher than projected, reflecting the effectiveness of the implemented measures and the high level of citizen participation. Community engagement also surpassed planned targets, with

high attendance rates and active participation in local events and activities. Furthermore, behavioural changes that closely aligned with improved preparedness for extreme weather events were observed, indicating that awareness-raising and nudging interventions had a tangible impact on resilience.

5.6.4 Challenges and Mitigations

The Guadeloupe mostly focused on the development and testing of the Local Adaptation Fund. More information is published as an adaptation story

<https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/mission-stories/redirecting-local-funding-to-climate-change-adaptation-story49>

Key learnings are:

- **A tailored Local Adaptation Fund** that awards projects following pre-agreed rules is a catalyst for local investment and stimulates innovation on climate change adaptation at local level.
- **The redirection and pooling of financial resources** from existing available budget lines into a common decision-making process is an example of efficient and smart financing. Yet, the transition phase requires careful coordination, particularly in aligning procurement, contracting, and payment procedures across institutions. Engaging private investors remains a challenge, as the return on investment in adaptation solutions is often intangible, but some are willing to contribute out of a sense of responsibility and long-term vision.
- **Co-design and cooperation** between potential funders and decision-makers from the beginning is essential in order to create a trustworthy institutional arrangement.

6.0 Overall challenges, barriers and lessons learned

The monitoring of the impact of the adaptation solutions in the demonstrator regions led to a number of challenges, barriers and lessons learned, from the technical monitoring design and analysis point of view, and the planning, implementation and design point of view.

In general, monitoring is a complex task, starting with the monitoring design, selection of parameters and monitoring devices. Clarity on what and how parameter need to be measured is a time consuming task, resulting in the absence of a baseline situation. Furthermore, to measure the impact of solutions on system resilience, time during the project is too short to actually attribute a change to the impact of the solutions. A further complexity is to assess whether an observed changed actually improves climate resilience or not. The characteristics to monitor 'climate resilience' are still challenging, and the topic of follow-up projects.

The experience highlighted the structural and operational challenges of embedding climate change monitoring into complex, time-constrained demonstrations with largely fixed designs. These challenges were encountered by both demonstrator teams and the monitoring support team, often reflecting misalignments in expectations, resources and technical capacities. The lessons drawn provide a constructive basis for improving future initiatives.

Key challenges encountered:

- Divergent expectations and the inherently different contexts of demonstrators posed challenges for comparability and sometimes created difficulties and misunderstandings in aligning perspectives between monitoring teams and local implementers. The concept of having a harmonious data system to compare the impact of solutions was difficult to fit in the local context of the demonstrators;
- Monitoring the impact of the demonstrators' adaptation solutions require preparatory work (e.g. a baseline monitoring intended to assess the impact of solutions) and closer, continuous support, in order to assess the most suitable way to evaluate impacts while taking into account the specific needs of each demonstrator;
- The wide range of monitoring, data analysis, and evaluation needs meant that the monitoring team should play a central role, to create opportunities for learning by doing and specific training sessions, to strengthen local monitoring capacities;
- Data ownership remained dispersed across partners, and datasets were fragmented, leading to delays in access and making the harmonization of qualitative and quantitative information particularly complex.
- Sensor installation, connectivity, and data processing proved more resource-intensive than anticipated, requiring higher levels of technical support than initially forecast by some demonstrators and the monitoring team within the available timeframe.
- Since demonstrator designs were developed before monitoring requirements could be fully embedded, there was limited alignment. This contributed to dispersed sampling strategies and narrower evidence on efficiency outcomes.
- Impact assessment was constrained by methodological uncertainties: proxies (such as indirect parameters or citizen-science contributions) which took time to establish and were further complicated by the absence of broadly agreed-upon frameworks.

- Monitoring frameworks and KPIs defined early on were sometimes ambitious or not fully aligned with evolving project conditions, resulting in either overabundance of data or lack of data that was difficult to process while also resulting gaps in key areas of information.

Lessons learned

These experiences underline that challenges arose not from a lack of commitment but from the structural difficulty of embedding a common monitoring framework within demonstrators that already had expert-led approaches, established designs, limited project timelines, and competing priorities. First, effective integration requires early planning, coordination, alignment and flexibility. In practice, many sites found it difficult to adjust ongoing activities to accommodate externally defined requirements while maintaining their own established monitoring routines. Second, the duration of the project also restricted the ability to observe long-term effects, especially for some adaptation measures take years to become visible. Third, the monitoring team itself faced difficulties in fully understanding and accommodating the very different nature of the demonstrators, which limited the potential for harmonization.

Recommendations for future projects

By acknowledging these dual-sided challenges, future initiatives can design approaches that facilitate common monitoring frameworks while making the most of demonstrators' existing expertise. generating not only scientifically sound evidence but also empower demonstrators and policy actors

Building on the experience of TransformAr, some important steps were already taken, but further refinements are needed:

- **Dedicated monitoring roles with adaptive capacity:** TransformAr defined a monitoring team from the outset, which was a positive step. Looking ahead, such teams should be equipped to adapt frameworks to different demonstrator contexts and work alongside local monitoring experts with time and channels to build mutual understanding.
- **Data governance operationalized:** Although TransformAr established a clear data management strategy, real-time application was uneven, leaving some datasets underused or disconnected. Future projects should emphasise putting governance agreements into practice, through hands-on technical support, continuous follow-up, and periodic alignment of data flows.
- **Early integration of monitoring requirements:** Demonstrator designs were often completed before monitoring needs could be fully embedded. To avoid costly retrofits and weaker evidence, monitoring design must be integrated into the earliest planning stages and supported throughout implementation.
- **Realistic and flexible KPI frameworks:** Indicators must remain practical under varying project conditions and open to revision when evidence points misalignment. In TransformAr, KPIs were reviewed during the project with strong contributions from demonstrators, which was a positive step. However, the process was not sufficient to align the final set of KPIs to the evaluation needs. This highlights the importance of joint ownership of KPI frameworks by both demonstrators and monitoring teams.
- **Capacity building and training:** Investing in early and ongoing training should be embedded to enhance local ownership of monitoring, reduce dependency on external actors and strengthen policy-relevance. In addition, training should also target the monitoring team itself, ensuring they fully understand the specific context, constraints and objectives of each demonstrator. This dual approach would enable monitoring frameworks to be both technically sound and well-adapted to the realities of implementation.

- **Adequately resourced technical support:** Sufficient budget and expertise for trouble shooting sensor installation, connectivity and processing must be anticipated.
- **Shared and adaptable methodological frameworks:** Developing a common methodological framework that remains flexible to local differences ensures that both direct and proxy indicators are applied consistently while valuing site-specific knowledge.

By bringing together these lessons and recommendations, future projects can be guided to avoid repeating structural gaps where frameworks exist but are not fully operationalized. Monitoring and data systems should be developed not only in design but also through ongoing support, collaborative testing, and continuous adjustment with demonstrators throughout the entire project lifecycle.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

